

Master's Thesis

Development of a 2D Simulative Model for Optimization of a Two-Phase Flow Cooling System

submitted in fulfillment of the requirements for the degree "Master of Science"

Born on	Smita Ashokrao Salunkhe
in	07. January 1999 Maharashtra, India.
Submission date	2. May 2026
Examiners	Prof. Dr.-Ing. habil. Dr. h. c. Uwe Hampel Dr. Hubert Straub
Supervisor	Jacob Andrea, M.Sc.

Prüfungsamt Fakultät Informatik

Anmeldung der Abschlussarbeit / Registration of the Final Thesis

Hiermit beantrage ich, Smita Salunkhe, 5185721
/ (Vorname, Name, Matrikelnummer / first name, surname, registration number) hereby apply
die Zulassung zur wissenschaftlichen Abschlussarbeit im Bachelor- Master- Diplomstudiengang²
to register my final thesis in the Bachelor / Master / Diplom programme²

Computational Modelling and Simulation (Name Studiengang / programme name)

Ich erkläre, dass ich keine für den Abschluss des oben genannten Studiengangs erforderliche Prüfung bereits
endgültig nicht bestanden habe. I declare that I have not definitively failed an examination required for the aforementioned
degree programme.

Themenvorschlag / Proposed topic for the thesis (in Deutsch und Englisch; in German and English) ¹	
Development of a 2D Simulative Model for the Optimization of a Two-phase Flow Cooling System.	
Arbeit in Deutsch ² thesis in German ²	Arbeit in Englisch ^{2,3} thesis in English ^{2,3} <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

1) bei rein englischer Abschlussarbeit kann das Thema nur in englischer Sprache angegeben werden / if thesis in English, the topic may be in English only
2) Bitte Zutreffendes ankreuzen / tick the appropriate box 3) Sofern gemäß PO vorgesehen / in accordance with the examination regulations if applicable

Vorschlag für 1. Prüfer/in / betreuende/r Hochschullehrer/in (Titel, Vorname, Name, Lehrstuhl) / Proposed primary examiner / academic supervisor (title, first name, surname, chair)	Prof. Dr.-Ing. habil. Dr. h. c. Uwe Hampel, Professur für Bildgebende Messverfahren für die Energie- und Verfahrenstechnik
Vorschlag für 2. Prüfer/in (Titel, Vorname, Name, Lehrstuhl) / Proposed secondary examiner (title, first name, surname, chair)	Dr. Hubert Straub Department ME/ECO-ME

09.10.2025 **Smita Ashokrao Salunkhe** Digitally signed by Smita Ashokrao Salunkhe Date: 2025.10.07 09:38:44 +02'00'
Datum / Date Unterschrift Studierende/r / Signature student

Uwe Hampel Digital unterschrieben von Uwe Hampel Datum: 2025.10.13 11:44:09 +02'00' **Hubert_Straub** Digitally signed by Hubert_Straub DN: dc=com, ou=group-akt, o=BOSCH, cn=shu3rt, cn=Hubert_Straub Date: 2025.10.09 14:48:45 +02'00'
Unterschrift 1. Prüfer/in / betreuende/r Hochschullehrer/in / Signature primary examiner / academic supervisor Unterschrift 2. Prüfer/in / Signature secondary examiner

Die fachlichen Voraussetzungen gemäß der für die/den Antragssteller/in gültigen Prüfungsordnung sind erfüllt. The requirements according to the examination regulations valid for the applicant have been fulfilled.

15. OKT. 2025 **Technische Universität Dresden Fakultät Informatik Prüfungsamt**
Datum / Date Unterschrift / Stempel Prüfungsamt / Signature / seal examination office

Nicht vom Studierenden auszufüllen! Not to be completed by the student!
Den Vorschlägen der/des Studierenden wird entsprochen. The proposal of the student is confirmed.
30. OKT. 2025
Datum / Date Unterschrift Prüfungsausschussvorsitzende/r / Signature chairperson examination board

Ausgabetermin: Date of issue:	<u>30.10.2025</u>	Abgabetermin: Submission Deadline:	<u>02.04.2026</u>
---	-------------------	--	-------------------

Prüfungsausschuss des Studiengangs / Examination Board of the Degree Program

Informatik

Antrag auf Verlängerung der Bearbeitungszeit der Abschlussarbeit / Application for an extension of the processing time for the final thesis

Salunkhe

Name / Family Name

Smita

Vorname / First Name

5185721

Matrikel-Nummer / Matriculation Number

Master

Hochschulgrad / University Degree

Thema (Titel) der Abschlussarbeit / Topic (Title) of the final thesis:

Development of a 2D Simulative Model for the Optimization of a Two-phase Cooling System

Prof. Dr.-Ing. habil. Dr. h. c. Uwe Hampel (TU Dresden), Andrea Jacob (Bosch GmbH) , Dr. Straub H

Betreuender Hochschullehrer /Supervising Professor

30.10.2025

Beginn der Bearbeitungszeit / Start of Processing Time

02.04.2026

Abgabetermin /Submission Deadline

30 days

Dauer der Verlängerung / Duration of Extension*

02.05.2026

Neuer Abgabetermin / New Deadline

*Maximale Verlängerungsdauer siehe Prüfungsordnung/Maximum period of extension according to Examination Regulation
Begründung der Verlängerung siehe Rückseite / Reason(s) for the Extension see backpage

****Begründung der Verlängerung / Reason(s) for the Extension**

The requested extension is justified by the failure of a key computational component essential to the thesis.

The multiphase solver initially chosen for the full PHP simulation was found to be incompatible with the physical and numerical requirements of the problem. This issue could not have been reasonably anticipated prior to implementation and only became evident after substantial development work.

As a result, the original simulation framework had to be abandoned, and a new approach based on a simplified geometry and a different solver is currently being developed. This transition necessitates additional time to ensure scientific validity and reproducibility.

09.02.2026

Datum / Date

Smita
Ashokrao
Salunkhe

Digitally signed by
Smita Ashokrao
Salunkhe
Date: 2026.02.09
17:21:58 +01'00'

Unterschrift Student / Signature Student

Zustimmung durch betreuender Hochschullehrer / Approval by Supervising Professor:

Datum / Date

Uwe
Hampel

Digital
unterschrieben
von Uwe Hampel
Datum: 2026.02.10
11:46:22 +01'00'

Unterschrift betreuender Hochschullehrer /
Signature Supervising Professor

Entscheidung des Prüfungsausschusses / Decision of the Examination Board:

Dem Antrag auf Verlängerung wird / The application for extension is

stattgegeben / approved

nicht stattgegeben / not approved

19. FEB. 2026

Datum / Date

Unterschrift Prüfungsausschuss / Sign. Examination
Board

Dieser Antrag ist mindestens 3 Wochen vor dem ursprünglichen Abgabetermin der Abschlussarbeit abzugeben. / This application must be submitted at least 3 weeks before the original deadline of the final thesis.

The English version is the translation of the German original. / Only the German version is legally binding.

Acknowledgement

I want to express my heartfelt gratitude to all the people who supported me throughout the process of completing this Master's thesis.

First and foremost, I would like to thank my supervisor, Andrea Jacob, and Bosch GmbH for the opportunity to work on such an interesting topic. Andrea supported me not only with the administrative aspects of the thesis but also as a guide throughout my technical work. Her continuous motivation, guidance, and encouragement helped me to develop a more research-oriented way of thinking.

I would also like to thank my examiner, Dr. Hubert Straub from Bosch GmbH, whose welcoming and supportive nature helped me remain motivated throughout this work.

I am especially grateful to Prof.Dr.-Ing. habil. Dr. h. c. Uwe Hampel for agreeing to be my examiner at TU Dresden. His vigilance, support, and guidance helped make the process of completing my Master's thesis smooth and manageable.

A special mention goes to Dr.Marcin Opalski from the Faculty of Mechanical and Power Engineering, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, for helping me understand his work on comprehensive numerical modeling and experimental validation of a multi-turn pulsating heat pipe. His support was valuable in helping me understand the physics behind the problem.

Finally, I would like to thank my pillars of support, my mother, my father, and my loving brother, for being my source of motivation throughout my Master's journey. I am also deeply grateful to my friends, who stayed with me through the highs and lows of my Master's journey.

Selbstständigkeitserklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die von mir am heutigen Tag der Professur für Prozessdiagnostik für die Energie- und Verfahrenstechnik eingereichte Masterarbeit zum Thema

*Entwicklung eines 2D-Simulationsmodells zur Optimierung eines
Zweiphasenströmungs-Kühlsystems*

vollkommen selbstständig verfasst und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt, sowie Zitate kenntlich gemacht habe.

Dresden, 30 April 2026

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Smita', with a large, sweeping horizontal stroke above it and three dots to the right.

Smita Salunkhe

Abstract

The ongoing miniaturization of electronic components has driven a steady increase in heat flux and power density, creating a strong demand for efficient thermal management systems. Two-phase heat transfer devices are attractive because they can transport large amounts of heat by absorbing latent heat during evaporation and releasing it during condensation of the working fluid. In particular, passive two-phase cooling systems, such as pulsating heat pipes, offer the additional advantage of self-sustained fluid motion without the need for external pumping power. Their operation is governed by evaporation, condensation, capillary effects, and pressure oscillations between the evaporator and condenser sections.

Pulsating heat pipes use mini- or micro-scale channels, where two-phase flow behavior is strongly influenced by confinement and channel geometry. In this context, a wavy minichannel is of interest because its curvature and periodic variation can alter the flow, deform vapor bubbles, enhance mixing, and improve wall heat transfer. The present work is motivated by the need to study the flow mechanisms relevant to this configuration. For this purpose, a representative two-dimensional numerical model of a single wavy minichannel is developed. The model is used to analyze the dynamics of the gas-liquid interface, bubble transport, liquid film formation, and the influence of channel geometry on flow and heat transfer behavior. The study provides insight into two-phase flow in wavy minichannels and contributes to the understanding of compact cooling systems for electronic thermal management and Pulsating heat pipe applications

Kurzfassung

Die fortschreitende Miniaturisierung elektronischer Bauteile führt zu einer stetigen Zunahme der Wärmestrom- und Leistungsdichte. Dadurch steigt der Bedarf an effizienten Systemen für das Wärmemanagement. Zweiphasige Wärmeübertragungssysteme sind für diesen Zweck sehr interessant, da sie große Wärmemengen durch die Verdampfungswärme des Arbeitsfluids abführen können. Besonders passive zweiphasige Kühlsysteme wie pulsierende Wärmerohre haben den Vorteil, dass sie ohne externe Pumpe funktionieren. Ihre Funktion wird durch Verdampfung, Kondensation, Kapillarkräfte und Druckschwingungen zwischen Verdampfer- und Kondensatorbereich bestimmt.

Pulsierende Wärmerohre verwenden Mini- oder Mikrokanäle. In diesen kleinen Kanälen wird das Zweiphasenströmungsverhalten stark durch die Begrenzung der Strömung und die Kanalgeometrie beeinflusst. In diesem Zusammenhang ist ein wellenförmiger Minikanal von besonderem Interesse, da seine Krümmung und periodische Form die Strömung verändern, Dampfblasen verformen, die Durchmischung verbessern und den Wärmeübergang an der Wand erhöhen können. Die vorliegende Arbeit wird durch die Notwendigkeit motiviert, die für diese Konfiguration relevanten Strömungsmechanismen zu untersuchen. Zu diesem Zweck wird ein repräsentatives zweidimensionales numerisches Modell eines einzelnen wellenförmigen Minikanals entwickelt. Das Modell wird verwendet, um die Dynamik der Gas-Flüssigkeits-Grenzfläche, den Blasentransport, die Bildung des Flüssigkeitsfilms sowie den Einfluss der Kanalgeometrie auf die Strömung und die Wärmeübertragung zu analysieren. Die Studie liefert Einblicke in die Zweiphasenströmung in wellenförmigen Minikanälen und trägt zum besseren Verständnis kompakter Kühlsysteme für das thermische Management elektronischer Bauteile sowie für Anwendungen pulsierender Wärmerohre bei.

Contents

List of Symbols	III
List of Figures	VIII
List of Tables	IX
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background and Motivation	1
1.2 Research Problem and Objectives	3
1.3 Scope and Thesis Structure	5
2 Theoretical Background and State of Art	7
2.1 Introduction	7
2.2 Fundamentals of Pulsating Heat Pipes	7
2.3 Parameters Affecting PHP Performance	12
2.4 State of the Art on Pulsating Heat Pipes	17
2.5 Mini- and Microchannels in Thermal Management	19
2.6 Fundamental Theory of Wavy Microchannel Flow and Heat Transfer	23
2.7 State of the Art on Flow Boiling in Wavy Microchannels	29
2.8 Research Gap	30
3 Numerical Implementation and Mathematical Formulation	32
3.1 Basics of Multiphase Flows	32
3.2 Modeling Approaches in Multiphase Flows	33
3.3 Governing Equations	36
3.4 Numerical Implementation Using the Finite Volume Method	38
3.5 Mathematical Formulation of Two-Phase flows	42
3.6 Solver Framework	58
4 Solver Validation: Growth of Vapor Bubbles in Superheated Liquids	61

4.1	Scriven Bubble Growth Case	61
5	Pulsating Heat Pipe Validation Case	71
5.1	Results and discussion	77
6	Numerical Investigation of Bubble Growth in Straight and Wavy Mini-channels	82
6.1	Objective of the Analysis	82
6.2	Overview of Numerical Method	83
6.3	Problem Definition	83
6.4	Mesh Sensitivity Study	86
6.5	Parametric study	93
7	Conclusion	113
	Bibliography	117

List of Symbols

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CHF	Critical Heat Flux
CSF	Continuum Surface Force
CV	Control Volume
FR	Filling ratio
FVM	Finite Volume Method
MEMS	Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems
MOL	Method of Lines
MPHP	Micro Pulsating Heat Pipe
ONB	Onset of Nucleate Boiling
PHP	Pulsating Heat Pipe
PIV	Particle Image Velocimetry
PLIC	Piecewise Linear Interface Calculation
RDF	Reconstructed Distance Function
VOF	Volume of Fluid

Latin Symbols

Symbol	Description	Unit
A	Amplitude of the wavy channel	m
b	Surface area density	m^{-1}
Bo	Bond number	–
Ca_m	Meniscus capillary number	–
Co	Courant number	–
c_p	Specific heat capacity at constant pressure	$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$

c_v	Specific heat capacity at constant volume	$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
D_h	Hydraulic diameter	m
f	Darcy friction factor	–
g	Gravitational acceleration	m s^{-2}
h_{lv}	Latent heat of vaporization	J kg^{-1}
Ja	Jakob number	–
L	Length of the channel	m
Ma	Mach number	–
Nu	Nusselt number	–
Pr	Prandtl number	–
P_{sat}	Saturation pressure	Pa
q	Heat flux	kW m^{-2}
R	Bubble radius	m
Re	Reynolds number	–
S	Channel spacing	m
T_{ref}	Reference temperature	K
T_{sat}	Saturation temperature	K
U_b	Bubble velocity	m s^{-1}
U_c	Bubble center velocity	m s^{-1}
U_l	Liquid velocity	m s^{-1}
U_{ref}	Reference velocity	m s^{-1}
V_m	Meniscus velocity	m s^{-1}
w	Width of the channel	m
x_c	Bubble center position	m

Greek Symbols

Symbol	Description	Unit
α	Volume fraction, where $\alpha = 1$ for liquid and $\alpha = 0$ for vapor	–
γ	Waviness parameter	–
δ	Liquid film thickness	m
λ	Wavelength of the wavy channel	m
μ	Dynamic viscosity	$\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
ν	Kinematic viscosity	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
ρ	Density	kg m^{-3}
σ	Surface tension	N m^{-1}

τ	Stress tensor	$\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-2}$
χ	Phase-change accommodation coefficient	–

List of Figures

1.1	Overview of classification of thermal management technologies for electronic devices. Adapted from a paper. [91]	2
1.2	Schematic of the working principle of a heat pipe, adapted from [2].	3
2.1	Schematic of the working in the pulsating heat pipe system, adapted from [47].	8
2.2	Schematic of flow patterns observed in a channel of pulsating heat pipes, adapted from [36].	10
2.3	Distribution of the liquid film thickness, δ , in minichannels with different cross-sections. Adapted from [86].	22
2.4	Schematic representation of the sinusoidal wavy microchannel geometry, adapted from [88].	26
3.1	Examples of Multiphase flows from Nature	33
3.2	Modelling approaches in multiphase flows. Adapted from Drew and Passman [66].	35
3.3	Schematic comparison of bubble-size resolution in a computational grid [66].	36
3.4	Volume of Fluid (VOF) representation of a two-phase interface evolution	46
3.5	Non-unique interface reconstruction from identical VOF volume fractions. [68]	48
3.6	multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow solver module structure.	59
3.7	icoBoilingFoam solver module structure.	59
4.1	Schematic of the computational setup for the Scriven case.	63
4.2	Initial fields for the Scriven bubble growth validation case.	64
4.3	Final temperature field showing the vapour bubble at the final bubble radius.	66
4.4	Scriven bubble growth validation for different solvers	68
4.5	Effect of phase-change model on Scriven bubble growth	70
5.1	Adapted 2D replicated geometry of the pulsating heat pipe used in the experiment from the work of Opalski et al. [54].	72
5.2	Detailed update sequence of the fluid region of the solver. Own interpretation and representation.	79

5.3	Phase-change source-term pathway leading to the pressure equation.	80
6.1	Schematic of Wavy geometry used in the present work. The schematic is not to scale.	84
6.2	Structured mesh for the wavy channel: (a) overall mesh with the selected region highlighted and (b) near-wall mesh refinement corresponding to the highlighted region in (a), shown with a zoomed inset.	88
6.3	Mesh-sensitivity comparison based on the dimensionless bubble volume growth rate and normalized bubble volume evolution. Here, V_b is the instantaneous bubble volume, V_{b0} is the initial bubble volume, and T_{ref} is the reference time calculated using the Reynolds number and used to normalize the simulation time.	90
6.4	Schematic representation of the local liquid film thickness δ near the bubble nose in the upper film region of the wavy channel.	90
6.5	Temporal evolution of the bubble inside the wavy minichannel, showing the bubble position and deformation at selected time instants: (a) $t = 0.1$ s, (b) $t = 0.14$ s, and (c) $t = 0.17$ s.	91
6.6	Comparison of the dimensionless liquid-film-thickness profiles near the bubble nose for the coarse, medium, and fine meshes at three representative time instants: $t = 0.11$ s in the entrance region, $t = 0.14$ s in the middle of the heated wavy section, and $t = 0.16$ s near the wavy section exit.	91
6.7	Variation of the minimum liquid-film thickness with bubble position for the coarse, medium, and fine meshes.	92
6.8	Temperature distribution and vapor-bubble growth in the wavy minichannel at $t = 0.14$ s for different imposed wall heat fluxes: (a) $q = 5$ kW m ⁻² , (b) $q = 7.5$ kW m ⁻² , and (c) $q = 10$ kW m ⁻²	94
6.10	Schematic representation of the fixed wall-probe location used for evaluating the local Nusselt number and wall superheat in the wavy minichannel. The dashed vertical line indicates the probe position at the middle of the heated wavy section, while the bubble moves through the channel from left to right.	96
6.11	Comparison of the local Nusselt number and dimensionless wall superheat at the fixed midpoint of the heated section for $q = 5$, $q = 7.5$, and $q = 10$	97
6.12	Flow-field visualization near the bubble nose at $t = 0.12$ s for different heat fluxes.	98
6.13	Schematic representation of the crest and trough locations selected for analysis in the sinusoidal wavy minichannel.	98
6.14	Local Nusselt number versus δ/D_h at $t = 0.140$ s at the crest and trough locations for $q = 10$, $q = 7.5$, and $q = 5$	99

6.15	Bubble motion characteristics for the nominal width case.	101
6.16	Comparison of local thermal quantities evaluated at the fixed heated-wall point $x/D_h = 8.65$ for selected geometry cases.	102
6.17	Crest and trough locations used for the local film-thickness extraction in the wavy section.	104
6.18	Dimensionless film thickness, δ/D_h , as a function of axial position, x/D_h , at selected times.	105
6.19	Dimensionless film thickness, δ/D_h , as a function of normalized time, t/T_{ref} , at the crest and trough locations.	105
6.20	Dimensionless film thickness, δ/D_h , as a function of bubble center position, x_c/D_h , at the crest and trough locations.	106
6.21	Effect of channel width on bubble growth rate and bubble volume ratio at fixed γ . 107	
6.22	Effect of channel width on the wall superheat ratio and local Nusselt number at $\gamma = 0.08$	109
6.23	Effect of channel width on bubble-growth and local thermal quantities as a function of bubble center position.	111

List of Tables

1.1	Classification of parameters influencing PHP thermal performance.	4
2.1	Classification of the main parameters affecting PHP performance, adapted from [47].	12
4.1	Thermophysical properties of water	64
4.2	Initial and boundary conditions for the Scriven benchmark case.	64
5.1	One of the case selected from paper as validation case for present work ($FR = 50\%$, $q = 10 \text{ kW/m}^2$).	73
5.2	Thermophysical properties of ethanol ($FR = 50\%$, $q = 10 \text{ kW/m}^2$).	73
5.3	Initial operating conditions.	74
5.4	Summary of boundary conditions used for the reproduced PHP case.	76
6.1	Summary of boundary conditions used throughout the study.	85
6.2	Thermophysical properties of acetone at saturation conditions.	86
6.3	Summary of mesh resolutions used in the mesh study. Here, Δx denotes the cell size in the streamwise direction and Δy_{wall} denotes the wall-adjacent cell height in the final refined mesh.	87

1 Introduction

This chapter introduces the motivation, research problem, and scope of the present work. It also outlines the thesis's objectives and briefly describes its structure.

1.1 Background and Motivation

The ongoing trend of miniaturization of high-performance electronic devices and advances in semiconductor technology have led to higher power density. However, this has also led to increased challenges in the thermal management of these electronic devices[72][30]. Two main cooling challenges are the removal of high heat flux and the handling of highly non-uniform power dissipation [30]. The current cooling technologies for such high-power-density devices or systems are increasingly failing to meet their high cooling demands imposed by these devices or systems due to limitations in the heat-transfer capabilities of traditional coolants. In electronics cooling, the most conventional passive heat-removal approach is based on heat conduction through a metallic heat spreader or heat sink, which is commonly made of copper because of its high thermal conductivity [71].

Figure 1.2 summarizes the main thermal management strategies used for electronic devices. These approaches can be broadly grouped into heat conduction, closed-loop cooling, solid-state cooling, and open-loop cooling. Heat conduction methods improve heat spreading through high-thermal-conductivity materials and thermal interface materials. At the same time, closed-loop systems use liquid cooling, immersion or spray cooling, heat pipes, and vapor chambers to remove heat from the device. Solid-state cooling methods, such as phase change materials, thermoelectric coolers, and electrocaloric refrigerators, rely on material-based thermal effects. In contrast, open-loop cooling techniques dissipate heat to the surrounding environment through forced or natural convection, radiation, and evaporation.

Limitations in conventional cooling technologies have driven the need for alternative thermal management systems capable of efficiently handling heat fluxes and enhancing heat dissipation to the environment. The emerging cooling methods, based on their effectiveness and the materials

Figure 1.1: Overview of classification of thermal management technologies for electronic devices. Adapted from a paper.[91]

or processes used, can be categorized into active and passive cooling devices. Active systems require a pump or compressor for higher cooling capacity, whereas passive cooling devices rely on capillary or gravitational buoyancy forces to circulate the cooling fluid.[10]

Among passive cooling technologies, heat pipes are regarded as highly efficient heat-transfer devices. They are two-phase sealed systems in which heat is primarily transported by the latent heat of an internal working fluid. As illustrated in Figure 1.2, a heat pipe operates by passing through an evaporator, an adiabatic section, and a condenser. A conventional heat pipe consists of an evaporator, an adiabatic section, and a condenser. Heat supplied to the evaporator causes the working fluid to vaporize, and the resulting vapor flows toward the condenser due to the pressure difference between the heated and cooled regions. At the condenser, the vapor releases latent heat and condenses back into liquid. The return of the condensate to the evaporator is achieved by capillary action, gravity, or oscillatory motion, depending on the heat-pipe configuration.

Due to phase-change heat transfer, heat pipes can transport large heat loads over small temperature differences and therefore exhibit an effective thermal conductivity much higher than that of solid metallic conductors. In addition, they are passive, compact, quiet, and reliable because they do not require external pumps or moving mechanical components. For this reason, heat pipes are widely used in thermal management applications, including electronic cooling, heat recovery, heat exchangers, building systems, and automotive systems. Based on geometry and liquid-return mechanism, heat pipes can be classified into several types, including thermosyphons,

wicked heat pipes, flat heat pipes or vapor chambers, loop heat pipes, micro-heat pipes, rotating heat pipes, and oscillating or pulsating heat pipes.

Figure 1.2: Schematic of the working principle of a heat pipe, adapted from [2].

1.2 Research Problem and Objectives

A pulsating heat pipe (PHP) is a passive two-phase heat-transfer device consisting of a long capillary tube bent into several turns. Similar to conventional heat pipes, it can be divided into an evaporator section, where heat is supplied, a condenser section, where heat is rejected, and, if required, an adiabatic section between them. Pulsating heat pipes are commonly classified into open-loop and closed-loop configurations. In open-loop PHPs, the tube ends are not connected, whereas in closed-loop PHPs, both ends are joined to form a continuous flow path. Previous studies have shown that closed-loop PHPs generally provide better thermal performance than open-loop configurations because the connected loop allows the working fluid to circulate in addition to oscillatory motion. Therefore, a closed-loop pulsating heat pipe without check valves is often preferred for practical applications. In the present thesis, the focus is limited to closed-loop pulsating heat pipes[10].

The thermal performance of PHP is influenced by various parameters directly or indirectly, and a brief classification is given below

They affect the formation and motion of liquid slugs and vapor bubbles, the pressure fluctuations inside the device, and the overall heat transfer capability. Because these parameters interact with each other, PHP's behavior is highly sensitive to specific configurations and operating conditions.

Table 1.1: Classification of parameters influencing PHP thermal performance.

A. Design or Geometrical Parameters	B. Operating Parameters	C. Properties of working fluids
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PHP channel/Tube diameter/width and material • Orientation of PHP • Number of Turns • Design of evaporator and condenser section • Bend effect 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filling ratio • Heat flux/temperature • Dry out conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating temperature range • Sensible heat and latent heat

To investigate the thermal behavior of PHPs, researchers have commonly used experimental, theoretical, and numerical approaches because PHP performance is governed by complex interactions among working-fluid properties, structural parameters, operating conditions, phase-change phenomena, and oscillatory two-phase flow [15, 55]. Experimental investigations provide valuable insights into the behavior of PHPs, but the literature lacks standardization, with significant variations in boundary conditions, device geometry, and measurement techniques. Moreover, experimental investigations are also constrained by practical limitations such as manufacturing complexities and measurement intrusiveness. Additionally, extensive parametric studies require costly, time-consuming modifications to the experimental layout. Thus, experimental approaches provide case-specific and qualitative insights, underscoring the need for complementary numerical modeling tools to offer a cost-effective alternative for the thermal optimization of [55].

Theoretical models used to describe PHP oscillatory behavior include spring-mass-damper systems, equation-based, and semi-empirical approaches. These models represent PHP operation via the motion of liquid slugs and vapor plugs driven by internal pressure, with friction as resistance. They provide rapid performance estimates and design guidance but are less predictive than detailed numerical simulations and depend heavily on available data [15].

Several attempts have been made to create Numerical models to understand PHP behavior, ranging from 1D to 3D formulations. One-dimensional models are computationally efficient; however, they require significant effort and the inclusion of many effects that we do not yet fully understand[55]. In particular, the liquid-film behavior, including its thickness, geometry, and rewetting characteristics, strongly affects evaporation, condensation, and dry-out, while bubble breakup and coalescence remain difficult to predict. All this shows that CFD methods are an important tool that can be used not only to model final devices but also to better understand the physics in PHP. Hence, many studies have been conducted to develop 2D numerical models and, in some cases, explicitly 3D numerical models in PHP [58].

To enhance the heat transfer performance in thermal systems, geometric modifications have been considered. In particular, corrugated surfaces can improve heat transfer by increasing the effective heat transfer area and thinning the thermal boundary layer. Although corrugated configurations have been widely used in heat exchangers, their use in pulsating heat pipes remains relatively limited. Existing studies suggest that geometric modifications can affect PHP thermal behavior, but the influence of localized wavy or corrugated structures within specific sections of the device remains poorly understood. In particular, the effect of a wavy evaporator section on two-phase flow, liquid-film behavior, and overall thermal performance has received only limited attention. This gap motivates the present work, which aims to investigate the role of a wavy evaporator geometry in PHP operation through numerical modeling.

To fill this gap, this thesis aims to develop a two-dimensional numerical model of a pulsating heat pipe with a wavy evaporator section, enabling a novel investigation into the influence of this wavy geometry on two-phase flow behavior, liquid-film dynamics, and thermal performance.

1.3 Scope and Thesis Structure

This thesis focuses on the development of a two-dimensional transient numerical model for investigating two-phase flow and heat transfer in a pulsating heat pipe with a wavy evaporator section. The thesis structure and the main objectives of each chapter are summarized as follows.

Chapter 2 presents the theoretical background and the state of the art relevant to the present work. It covers the fundamentals of pulsating heat pipes, the main parameters affecting PHP performance, the influence of channel geometry, and the underlying behavior of micro/minichannel, including wavy minichannel flow and heat transfer.

Chapter 3 introduces the mathematical formulation and physical modeling framework for two-phase flow. Since PHP operation is governed by multiphase flow and phase-change phenomena, this chapter describes the governing equations, modeling assumptions, interface-capturing approach, surface-tension treatment, phase-change modeling, and numerical implementation.

Chapter 4 presents the benchmark studies used to verify the numerical methodology. In particular, it includes the bubble-growth validation case and assesses the numerical model's capability to reproduce the fundamental physics of interfacial flow and phase change.

Chapter 5 provides the pulsating heat pipe validation case. The numerical model is applied to a PHP configuration, and the resulting outputs are discussed.

Chapter 6 contains the main numerical investigation of bubble growth and two-phase flow in

straight and wavy channels. This chapter includes nominal case analysis, mesh sensitivity, comparison between straight and wavy channels, parameter-sensitivity study, and discussion of the underlying physical mechanisms.

Finally, Chapter 7 summarizes the main conclusions of the thesis, highlights the principal findings and contributions of the work, discusses its limitations, and provides recommendations for future research.

2 Theoretical Background and State of Art

2.1 Introduction

This chapter provides the theoretical background necessary for understanding pulsating heat pipes and their application in miniaturized thermal systems. It first introduces the fundamental operating principles of PHPs, including their flow behavior, oscillation mechanism, and heat transfer processes. Subsequently, the discussion extends to the role of minichannels and the parameters that influence PHP performance. Based on these fundamentals, the current state of the art in experimental and numerical research is reviewed in order to identify existing limitations and research gaps.

2.2 Fundamentals of Pulsating Heat Pipes

This section introduces the fundamental concepts of pulsating heat pipes, including their definition, operating principle, flow behavior, oscillation mechanism, heat transfer processes, and typical applications.

2.2.1 Definition and Working Principle

Pulsating Heat Pipes usually consist of sealed, meandering channels connected end-to-end, first evacuated, and then partially filled with a working fluid which distributes itself naturally in the form of liquid–vapor slugs and bubbles inside, leading to different flow regimes in these channels under different working conditions[33]. For slug–plug flow, it must be run in capillary mode (where surface tension forces dominate fluid behavior in the small channels). With increased heat input, it is possible to transition from slug plug flow to annular flow in the PHP channels. These channels can be thermally insulated in three different zones [47]. Figure 2.1 shows the working principle of a closed-loop multi-turn pulsating heat pipe.

The fundamental process happening in PHP can be explained as follows:

Figure 2.1: Schematic of the working in the pulsating heat pipe system, adapted from [47].

- In the evaporator zone, two different phenomena will occur:
 - Sensible heating of liquid slug if it reaches the evaporator section in sub-cooled condition
 - Heating of liquid slug if reaching saturated conditions
 - Heating causes evaporation mass transfer to contiguous vapor bubbles or creates new bubbles

These phenomena increase local pressure and temperature. The vapor bubble expands, increasing pressure, and, at the same time, the surrounding liquid at the meniscus evaporates into the bubble, further increasing the local pressure. These pressure differences cause PHP to oscillate without a heat pump. This bubble expansion pushes the neighboring liquid slug towards the cooling zone, which, in turn, pushes another vapor plug towards the condenser, where condensation occurs. Since PHP is a closed system, vapor expansion propagates throughout the system, producing a liquid oscillation or pulsation; hence, pulsating heat pipes are also called oscillating heat pipes. Additionally, there is another zone with reduced heat exchange, called the adiabatic zone[47].

Operating Modes

- a. Pure conduction: This is before startup. Visually, there is no motion of bubbles and

liquid slugs. Increasing the power load raises the evaporator temperature. Pressure at the condenser is stable and corresponds to the saturation temperature.

- b. Pulsation: This regime may be obtained in microgravity. No temperature fluctuations in evaporator or condenser; however, some pressure fluctuation.
- c. Startup: Temperature oscillations are recognizable at least in one channel.
- d. Intermittent flow: After the start-up, the temperatures at the evaporator do not stabilize and show stop-overs with rapid increases and strong oscillations.
- e. Full activation: A vigorous two-phase flow can be observed
 - Oscillation: the fluid changes direction with a noticeable amplitude
 - Circulation: the fluid flows in a preferential direction
- f. Dry out: The evaporator temperatures are rapidly increasing.

The performance and operation of PHPs depend on maintaining non-equilibrium conditions within the system. Advantage of working with PHPs is manufacturing cost is low due to a wickless structure; on the other hand, it is difficult to design PHPs as there is no simple way to define their operation regimes for an arbitrary geometry and thermal boundary conditions.[47]

The inner diameter of a pulsating heat pipe is an important design parameter because it controls whether capillary slug-plug flow can be established inside the channel. A common first estimate of this capillary limit is given by the Bond number, defined as

$$Bo = \frac{g(\rho_l - \rho_v)d^2}{\sigma}, \quad (2.1)$$

where g denotes the gravitational acceleration, ρ_l and ρ_v are the liquid and vapor densities, d is the channel inner diameter, and σ is the surface tension.

2.2.2 Flow Patterns

To understand the mechanisms of internal heat and mass transfer, it is essential to visualize the flow patterns in a pulsating heat pipe, as shown in Figure 2.2. Depending on operating conditions, various flow patterns, such as bubble-liquid slug flow, semi-annular flow, and annular flow, may occur.

Figure 2.2: Schematic of flow patterns observed in a channel of pulsating heat pipes, adapted from [36].

Since the alternating sequence of liquid slugs and vapor plugs supports the self-sustained oscillatory motion of the fluid, this is regarded as a characteristic operating mode of PHP. With modifications to the internal heat transfer mechanism, this flow structure gradually transitions to semi-annular or annular flow at higher heat loads. Transparent inserts made of glass, Pyrex, or sapphire, placed in the adiabatic, evaporator, or condenser sections, allow direct observation of these flow regimes; however, they may affect the thermal behavior of PHP. In addition to direct visualization, the internal flow behavior can also be characterized through analysis of temperature and pressure signals.

2.2.3 Heat Transfer Mechanisms

The heat transfer mechanism in PHP is difficult to analyze because many processes occur simultaneously, including evaporation, condensation, bubble motion, slug oscillation, pressure fluctuations, and flow reversal. Researchers usually study PHPs through three main aspects[36][47]:

1. Internal flow dynamics describes the hydrodynamic behavior of two-phase flow. It includes the formation and motion of liquid slugs, bubble nucleation, bubble growth, pressure fluctuations, slug acceleration, and possible breakup of liquid slugs or vapor plugs.
2. Thermal performance: Evaluated through measured temperatures in the evaporator, adiabatic section, and condenser, and is often expressed in terms of thermal resistance or effective thermal conductivity.
3. Heat Transfer behavior: Study of mechanisms by which heat is transported, including latent heat transfer due to evaporation and condensation, sensible heat transfer due to the oscillating motion of liquid slugs, and the role of the thin liquid film surrounding vapor plugs. It also involves analysis of temperature and pressure fluctuations.

The heat transfer mechanisms are identified as follows[47]:

1. Latent heat transfer: which occurs due to vapor condensation and evaporation of the thin liquid film surrounding vapor bubbles; the thin film provides very small thermal resistance and allows efficient phase-change heat transfer.
2. Sensible heat transfer: caused by the oscillatory motion of the liquid slugs, which transport thermal energy between the evaporator and condenser.
3. External convection at condenser: heat is finally rejected to the surroundings.

2.2.4 Liquid Film

One important phenomenon that affects not only heat and mass transfer but also the system's oscillatory behavior is the formation of a liquid film in PHPs. The liquid films in PHP are entirely different from their counterparts in capillary heat pipe[44] and are of purely hydrodynamic origin and appear as a result of the receding of a liquid meniscus, almost independently of the wetting properties of the tube wall. Since both film thickness and film area are strongly influenced by evaporation, and key parameters in the theoretical description of PHP operation. Film thickness can be predicted using classical capillary-flow theory, in which the deposited film results from a balance between viscous forces and surface tension. In the evaporator, continuous heat input causes the film to evaporate, gradually reducing its thickness over time. At the same time, the contact line may recede, meaning that the edge of the wetted region moves and the total film-covered area decreases. Another observation: the film is not highly wedge-shaped but remains relatively uniform, except near the contact line. Viscous forces tend to drag the liquid along the wall, thereby increasing the deposited film thickness, whereas surface tension tends to

minimize the interfacial area and reduce the film thickness. This balance is commonly expressed by the meniscus capillary number,

$$Ca_m = \frac{\mu V_m}{\sigma}, \quad (2.2)$$

where μ is the liquid viscosity, V_m is the meniscus velocity, and σ is the surface tension. The initial film thickness is typically described by the classical Bretherton relation, which shows that the deposited film thickness increases with the meniscus velocity. Although refined models account for additional effects such as finite film thickness, inertial effects, and meniscus acceleration, the dominant dependence on the capillary number remains unchanged. Film deposition also depends on the wall's wetting characteristics. In well-wetted capillaries, which are typical of PHP operation, the deposition of a liquid film by the receding meniscus is therefore commonly expected[47].

2.3 Parameters Affecting PHP Performance

The performance of a pulsating heat pipe is affected by numerous interacting parameters, and the influence of each is still not fully understood. A classification of the main geometrical and operating parameters affecting PHP performance is given in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Classification of the main parameters affecting PHP performance, adapted from [47].

PHP configuration	Geometric/design parameters	Operating conditions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open-loop/closed-loop • Open-end/closed-end • Tubular/flat-plate configuration • Single-loop/multi-turn configuration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inner diameter • Outer diameter • Channel cross-section • Number of turns • Turn radius • Evaporator length • Adiabatic length • Condenser length • Wall material • Surface characteristics • Wettability • Insulation of adiabatic section • Condenser geometry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heat input • Heat flux • Filling ratio • Operating pressure • Operating temperature • Inclination/orientation • Working fluid • Thermophysical properties • Fluid purity • Degassing level • Coolant temperature

In the following, a brief overview is given of the parameters considered most important for the present thesis.

1. Working fluid

Choice of working fluid strongly affects the thermal performance of PHPs. Surface tension is essential for maintaining the liquid slug–vapor plug structure and for supporting capillary-

driven film formation. The density difference between liquid and vapor affects the capillary limit and bubble dynamics, while the liquid density influences the acceleration of liquid slugs under pressure fluctuations. Fluids with high latent heat and high boiling points require higher start-up input power but can be advantageous for heat dissipation at higher temperatures. High liquid viscosity damps the oscillatory motion and generally reduces PHP performance, whereas high specific heat improves sensible heat transport by the moving liquid slugs. Experimental studies confirm that the optimum working fluid depends not only on these properties but also on the channel diameter and operating conditions[55],[47].

2. **Filling Ratio**

The filling ratio is defined as the ratio of the liquid volume to the total internal volume of the PHP[90]. Values around 50% are often considered optimal for many PHP geometries and working fluids. For high heat fluxes and very long channels, a slightly higher range of $50\% < FR < 70\%$ may be preferable. By contrast, performance generally decreases when the filling ratio is too low ($FR < 30\%$) or too high ($FR > 70\%$). At very high filling ratios, vapor bubbles tend to restrict two-phase motion, reducing oscillation intensity and deteriorating thermal performance. A suitable FR value for the PHP design is equal to (50%) for most of the PHP geometries and working fluids.[47],[10].

3. **Orientation and gravity**

Bubble buoyancy, liquid return, and flow stability are influenced by gravity. Gravity is especially important during start-up, whereas at higher heat loads, the influence of orientation on thermal resistance becomes more evident. PHP performance is orientation-dependent because gravity influences slug–plug dynamics and liquid return. This effect becomes weaker as the number of turns increases, since additional turns enhance internal pressure fluctuations and help maintain oscillatory motion [10].

4. **PHP Geometry**

The geometric parameters of a pulsating heat pipe influence its performance by affecting flow stability, pressure drop, start-up behavior, and maximum heat transport capability. Important parameters include the overall channel length, number of turns, evaporator length, adiabatic length, condenser length, and turn radius. Wang et al. [80] reported that increasing the input power reduces the start-up time, while increasing the evaporator-to-condenser length ratio can shorten the start-up process within a suitable range. This is because a shorter condenser section may promote faster establishment of oscillatory circulation. However, an excessively short condenser can provide insufficient cooling at high

heat inputs, leading to vapor accumulation in the evaporator and potentially deteriorating heat-transfer performance. Varying the channel diameter along the PHP can improve thermal performance by promoting flow circulation and reducing sensitivity to gravity. The effect of channel diameter and cross-section is of particular importance in the present focus of the thesis and is discussed in detail in further sections.[10],[55]

Influence of Geometry - Channel Diameter

Among the geometric parameters of a pulsating heat pipe, the inner diameter is one of the most important because it directly governs the formation and stability of the alternating liquid slug–vapor plug structure. For proper PHP operation, the Bond number must be satisfied.

$$Bo < 4. \quad (2.3)$$

Accordingly, the inner diameter should fulfill

$$d < 2\sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{g(\rho_l - \rho_v)}}. \quad (2.4)$$

This criterion indicates that the tube must be sufficiently small for surface tension forces to dominate over gravity and to preserve the slug–plug structure of the working fluid [47, 55]. However, Eq. (2.4) only defines the upper limit of the tube diameter. The internal diameter should also not be too small, because excessive viscous and frictional resistance can suppress the oscillatory motion of the liquid-slug and vapor-plug train between the evaporator and condenser sections. If the thermally generated pressure difference is insufficient to overcome this flow resistance, the PHP may fail to start up or sustain stable oscillations. Therefore, a lower limit of the internal diameter should also be considered. The proposed empirical lower-limit criterion in the literature for effective PHP operation, which can be expressed as [60].

$$d > d_{\min}. \quad (2.5)$$

Using the standard Bond number definition,

$$Bo = \frac{g(\rho_l - \rho_v)d^2}{\sigma}, \quad (2.6)$$

the lower-limit criterion in Eq. (2.5) may equivalently be written as

$$\sqrt{Bo} > 0.7, \quad \text{or} \quad Bo > 0.49. \quad (2.7)$$

Nevertheless, this lower-limit criterion should be regarded as a design guideline rather than a universal rule, because the lower limit of the internal diameter depends on the working fluid, PHP geometry, filling ratio, evaporator and condenser temperatures, gravity condition, and operating conditions [60].

Accordingly, the channel diameter must remain below a critical limit to sustain stable liquid slugs and vapor plugs, and this critical diameter depends on the working fluid's thermophysical properties, especially its density difference and surface tension.

Experimental and numerical studies confirm that the inner diameter strongly affects PHP thermal performance. Experiments and numerical studies performed on PHPs by Babu et al. [5] with different inner diameters using acetone reported that a filling ratio of 60% was favorable. In contrast, a channel diameter close to the critical diameter yielded lower thermal resistance and improved thermal performance. Qu et al. [82] tested silicon-based (micro pulsating heat pipes) MPHPs with hydraulic diameters of 251–394 μm and showed that they can operate below the conventional lower Bond-number limit. This indicates that hydraulic diameter, working-fluid properties, and flow resistance strongly affect MPHP start-up and oscillatory behavior. Wu et al. [61] experimentally examined PHPs with inner diameters of 1, 1.5, and 2 mm and filling ratios from 40% to 70%, and reported that at a filling ratio of about 50% and a heating power of 70 W, the PHP with 1.5 mm inner diameter exhibited the lowest thermal resistance of 0.1184 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{W}$.

In general, increasing the inner diameter reduces the frictional pressure drop along the PHP channels, since the working fluid experiences less resistance from the tube wall. This reduction in flow resistance can decrease dissipative losses, enhance the oscillatory motion of liquid and vapor plugs, improve heat transport, and lower thermal resistance.[16]. However, if the diameter becomes too large, the slug–plug structure may no longer be maintained, and the device may gradually lose its characteristic pulsating behavior. Therefore, the optimum diameter is not simply the smallest or largest, but rather a value that provides a suitable balance between capillary confinement and flow resistance.

Recent studies have also shown that non-uniform channel designs, such as variable-diameter, dual-diameter, and triple-diameter PHPs, can further enhance performance by generating additional capillary pressure differences, improving fluid circulation, reducing start-up time, and decreasing sensitivity to orientation [38]. Nevertheless, an excessive diameter difference may increase flow

resistance or promote dry-out, suggesting an optimal diameter ratio rather than a monotonically increasing benefit. Overall, the literature suggests that the optimal inner diameter of a PHP should be selected in conjunction with the working fluid properties, the filling ratio, and operating conditions to achieve optimal thermal performance.

Because the channel diameter controls the degree of confinement inside the PHP, its influence also provides a natural connection to the broader study of confined two-phase flow in small channels. As the channel diameter decreases, liquid-film behavior, capillary forces, and phase-change mechanisms become more dominant, making the flow characteristics increasingly similar to those observed in mini- and microchannels. For this reason, the discussion of diameter effects in PHPs naturally leads to the fundamentals of two-phase flow and heat transfer in mini- and microchannels.

Influence of Geometry - Channel Cross-section

The channel cross-section is a key geometric parameter because it controls the shape of the liquid-vapor meniscus, the distribution of the thin liquid film, and the hydraulic resistance opposing oscillatory motion. These effects directly influence start-up, circulation stability, thermal resistance, and the maximum allowable heat input. As a result, different cross-sectional shapes, such as circular, square, and rectangular channels, can produce different thermal performances even under similar operating conditions. Although circular channels are widely used in conventional PHP designs, other channel shapes may provide improved fluid distribution, stronger capillary effects, or lower thermal resistance. In addition, non-uniform cross-sections may introduce a capillary pressure imbalance, promoting circulation and reducing sensitivity to inclination due to the additional unbalancing surface tension introduced by the non-uniform cross-section. However, the thermal resistance for the non-uniform closed loop pulsating heat pipe was slightly higher than that of the uniform configuration due to the larger viscous forces associated with the smaller tube size[11].

The comparison between circular and rectangular PHP channels shows that the channel cross-section has a direct influence on thermal performance[84]. The presence of angled corners in rectangular channels promotes stronger capillary effects, leading to a larger fraction of the liquid phase remaining distributed near the tube wall. As a result, heat transfer between the wall and the liquid film becomes more effective than heat transfer between the wall and the vapor plugs. Rectangular channels exhibited 30-40 percent lower thermal resistance than circular channels. Therefore, rectangular channels can improve steady-state thermal performance, though this advantage comes at the cost of a higher start-up requirement strongly influenced by heating

power as studied by author Hua et al[27]

Further examination of uniform and non-uniform cross-sections showed that a closed-loop PHP with a uniform square-channel configuration had lower thermal resistance than a configuration with alternating channel sizes, because the smaller channel sections increased viscous forces[16]. However, the uniform design was more sensitive to inclination and could not operate in the horizontal position, whereas the non-uniform design functioned at all inclinations. This indicates that cross-sectional design involves a trade-off between lower flow resistance and improved circulation stability.

2.4 State of the Art on Pulsating Heat Pipes

Experimental studies remain essential in PHP research because they provide a basis for understanding the device's thermal performance, start-up behavior, oscillation characteristics, and dryout limits [54]. However, such investigations are limited by the inherently complex and chaotic nature of the working-fluid oscillations, which makes the measured thermal response strongly dependent on the operating conditions, geometry, and experimental setup. In particular, conventional wall-temperature measurements using thermocouples may not fully capture the spatial and temporal variations of the evaporator and condenser temperatures, especially during strong transient operation. Consequently, the estimation of equivalent thermal resistance can be sensitive to the number and location of measurement points, the selected averaging time window, and the boundary conditions adopted for heating and cooling. Moreover, different experimental layouts or diagnostic techniques may require modifications to the PHP structure, potentially altering device response and reducing the generality of the results. Therefore, direct comparison between different experimental studies remains difficult, and the reported performance trends may not readily extend to other PHP geometries, working fluids, or operating conditions[55].

The reviewed literature shows that experiments are particularly important for observing phenomena that are still difficult to model accurately, such as interface motion and phase distribution in the evaporator, adiabatic, and condenser sections. Several numerical studies were validated against experiments, and in many cases, good agreement was reported for thermal resistance and overall operating behavior. However, the author also points out that most validated studies are conducted under operating conditions far from dryout, whereas experiments close to dryout are more difficult to interpret and remain necessary to improve the physical understanding of PHP operation.

Numerous studies have been conducted on numerical models of pulsating heat pipes. Pouryoussefi

and Zhang [57] conducted a series of 2D and 3D simulations using Ansys Fluent and the VOF method to understand thermal performance behavior of PHP; however, they did not experimentally validate the results. Ferrari et al. [17] used the VOF method, introduced instability corrections at the liquid-vapor interface, employed the Schrage model for evaporation and condensation, and studied the effect of liquid film thickness on mass transfer. Their findings showed that mass transfer is strongly dependent on the thickness of the liquid film, and that a minimum liquid film thickness significantly enhances the heat transfer coefficient. In their study, the circular channel was modeled in 2D, while the square channel was modeled in 3D.

Jung et al. [31] performed a numerical analysis of five interconnected single-loop PHPs. They examined the impact of simplifications and the differences between 2D and 3D approaches. Their analysis used conjugate heat transfer between the solid and liquid in Fluent. The text does not state a final numerical result, but it clearly says they compared 2D versus 3D behavior and validated the model geometry using the experiment. Błasiak et al. [8] used the VOF method with an additional MULES algorithm to reproduce a sharp liquid-vapor interface. Their goal was to compare and experimentally validate different models of mass transfer between the liquid and vapor phases. They tested four models.

Opalski extended the numerical model of Błasiak et al. [8]. The earlier model focused mainly on flow structure, whereas the new one also accounts for conjugate heat transfer and links phase-change intensity to temperature. The extended model was implemented in OpenFOAM. The novelty is a comprehensive PHP model that accounts for conjugate heat transfer during phase change using the VOF method.

Moving to explicitly 3D numerical models, Wang and Bai [78] modeled and validated a geometry that differs from classical PHPs, in which the condenser and evaporator were placed horizontally at different heights and connected by an inclined adiabatic zone. This configuration required a three-dimensional grid. They used the VOF method and the Lee model. Their results showed that the height difference between the condenser and evaporator plays an important role in the stable operation of the PHP. Mucci et al. [87] used the VOF model with Lee's evaporation model. Even though the mesh was less detailed, the results showed excellent agreement with experimental results. They also developed a transparent visualization of flow structures in PHPs using a three-dimensional CFS model in ANSYS Fluent. That 3D model accurately represented the circulating motions and closely matched the experimental heat transfer rates. Magnini et al. [44] performed calculations in Fluent using the VOF method. Both phases were modeled as incompressible. Their work focused on modeling a growing Taylor bubble. They used the Schrage model for mass transfer by evaporation and condensation. They also used the height function

method to calculate the interface curvature. The passage does not state a final performance result; it mainly describes the model setup and focus.

For modified PHP geometries, Wang et al. [81] investigated a single PHP loop with corrugated walls. This was done by comparing the thermal performance of different fill ratios. The study helped achieve a better understanding of the effect of filling ratio on PHP performance.

2.5 Mini- and Microchannels in Thermal Management

Pulsating heat pipes, although discussed at the device level, are governed by liquid-vapor interactions in narrow channels. Also, from an application perspective, modern thermal systems require compact and highly efficient cooling solutions. To manage high heat fluxes within limited space, micro-scale devices such as micro heat exchangers and micro cooling systems are increasingly used in electronics. This trend has driven the adoption of mini- and microchannels in advanced thermal technologies, including Pulsating Heat Pipes [7]. Since the present thesis investigates not only pulsating heat pipes but also minichannels, it is essential to develop a clear understanding of the theoretical background and thermofluid behavior of minichannels.

Definition of mini- and microchannel

There is no universally accepted definition of small, mini-, or microchannels in two-phase flow, because the transition from macro- to micro-scale behavior depends not only on channel size but also on the dominant physical mechanisms [33]. Since systematic experiments over many closely spaced diameters are difficult, most studies consider limited size ranges, and the term micro-scale is often used broadly to describe channels where conventional two-phase flow behavior changes significantly [49]. Existing classifications are generally either geometric or physics-based. Geometric classifications use fixed ranges based on hydraulic diameter, $D_h = 4A_c/P_w$, or surface-area density, b . For example, compact, meso-, and micro-scale heat exchangers have been associated with $b \geq 700$, 3000, and 15000 m^2/m^3 , respectively, corresponding approximately to compact channels of $D_h = 1\text{--}6$ mm, mesochannels of $D_h = 0.1\text{--}1$ mm, and microchannels of $D_h = 0.001\text{--}0.1$ mm [33]. Mehendale et al. classify channels as conventional for $D_h > 6$ mm, compact for $1 < D_h \leq 6$ mm, meso for $100 \mu\text{m} < D_h \leq 1$ mm, and micro for $1 \mu\text{m} < D_h \leq 100 \mu\text{m}$ [49], while Kandlikar and Grande define conventional channels as $D_h > 3$ mm, minichannels as $200 \mu\text{m} < D_h \leq 3$ mm, microchannels as $10 \mu\text{m} < D_h \leq 200 \mu\text{m}$, transitional channels as $0.1 \mu\text{m} < D_h \leq 10 \mu\text{m}$, and molecular nanochannels as $D_h \leq 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ [32].

To understand the hydrodynamic and thermal behavior of mini- and microchannels, it is useful to begin with single-phase flow, since the governing mechanisms are simpler than in two-phase systems. Parameters such as pressure drop, friction factor, heat transfer coefficient, entrance effects, and axial conduction are commonly first examined under single-phase conditions before extending the analysis to two-phase flow with phase change [4].

Before examining the available literature, some basic dimensionless and transport parameters should be introduced. The Reynolds number, Re , is a dimensionless parameter that represents the ratio of inertial forces to viscous forces in the flow and is commonly used to characterize the flow regime as laminar, transitional, or turbulent. It is defined as

$$Re = \frac{\rho U D_h}{\mu}, \quad (2.8)$$

where ρ is the fluid density, U is the mean flow velocity, D_h is the hydraulic diameter, and μ is the dynamic viscosity [70].

The Darcy friction factor, f , quantifies the frictional pressure loss along the channel. It relates the pressure gradient to the dynamic pressure of the flow and is defined as

$$f = \left(\frac{-dp}{dx} \right) \frac{2D_h}{\rho U^2}, \quad (2.9)$$

where $-dp/dx$ is the pressure drop per unit channel length, D_h is the hydraulic diameter, ρ is the fluid density, and U is the mean flow velocity [70].

In heat-transfer analysis, the Nusselt number, Nu , is used to express the ratio of convective to conductive heat transfer across the fluid layer near the wall. It is defined as

$$Nu = \frac{h D_h}{k}, \quad (2.10)$$

where h is the convective heat-transfer coefficient, D_h is the hydraulic diameter, and k is the thermal conductivity of the fluid [70]. [70].

Two-Phase Flow and Flow Boiling in Microchannels

The increased importance of surface tension and confinement effects explains why two-phase flow in mini- microchannels differs significantly from that in conventional macrochannels[75], [74]. In microchannels, the small hydraulic diameter results in capillary forces dominating; thus, liquid stratification is often suppressed, and channel orientation is of secondary importance. The typical range of interest in microchannel flows is Reynolds numbers from 100 to 4000. Hence,

flow pattern transition theories with turbulent liquid flows cannot be expected to apply directly to a similar transition for laminar conditions.

Flow regime identification in mini- and microchannels is challenging because observations are often subjective, and similar structures may be named differently. Despite this, common regimes such as bubbly, slug/elongated bubble, churn or semi-annular, annular, and dryout/mist flows are frequently reported [24]. These regimes depend strongly on channel size and operating conditions, including working fluid, pressure, heat flux, mass flux, vapor quality, and heated length [24]. In R-134a microchannel boiling, Revellin et al.[63] showed that increasing vapor quality promotes transitions from bubbly to slug flow and then to semi-annular or annular flow. Overall, bubbly flow is usually short-lived in microchannels, while slug and annular flows are the most relevant regimes for evaporation heat transfer.

In microchannels, the formation of elongated bubbles confined by the channel walls influences evaporation heat transfer. Under these conditions, a thin liquid film is deposited between the bubble interface and the wall, and its transient evaporation has been identified as a dominant heat-transfer mechanism. This differs from conventional macroscale flow boiling, where nucleate boiling and convective evaporation are often assumed to dominate. In microchannel slug flow, the slug flow regime subsequently gives way to annular flow. The evaporation and local dryout of the thin liquid film, therefore, play a major role in determining the heat-transfer characteristics of microchannels[63]. This evaporation process is commonly interpreted using the three-zone model proposed by Thome et al.[75], in which the flow is represented by a liquid slug zone, a thin evaporating liquid-film zone surrounding an elongated bubble, and a dry vapor zone with relatively weak heat transfer. Within this framework, the liquid film is the most important region for evaporation heat transfer, and its thickness and temporal evolution strongly affect local heat transfer and dryout behavior.

Effective Parameters of Straight Microchannels and Geometric Enhancement for Heat Transfer

Previous studies on straight microchannels have demonstrated that geometric parameters, including channel width, hydraulic diameter, aspect ratio, and cross-sectional shape, significantly influence both pressure drop and heat transfer characteristics[33]. One of the most effective passive approaches for enhancing heat transfer in microchannels is geometric optimization. In general, microchannel geometric optimization can be classified into three broad categories: cross-sectional geometry optimization, wall geometry optimization, and complex structural optimization. However, since the present thesis addresses both cross-sectional variation and wavy

wall geometry, the following discussion focuses primarily on these two geometric modification strategies, which are most directly related to the present work's scope.

Among the geometric parameters of straight microchannels, cross-sectional size is particularly important because it directly determines the hydraulic diameter and influences thermal boundary-layer development and, in two-phase flow, bubble growth and motion. As a result, hydraulic diameter becomes a key parameter for evaluating thermo-hydraulic performance. Its influence is more complex under flow-boiling conditions. Experiments on rectangular microchannels with hydraulic diameters of 100, 150, 200, and 250 μm showed that hydraulic diameter significantly affects both pressure drop and heat transfer, though the trends are not always monotonic. At small hydraulic diameters, geometric confinement strongly restricts bubble development and alters the prevailing flow patterns, thereby promoting elongated bubbles, liquid-film dryout, flow instability, and deterioration of heat transfer. This indicates that cross-sectional size is not merely a geometric quantity, but a parameter that strongly governs the two-phase flow structure and overall thermal behavior of the microchannel.

Figure 2.3: Distribution of the liquid film thickness, δ , in minichannels with different cross-sections. Adapted from [86].

Among the various microchannel configurations, rectangular cross-section channels have received the greatest attention and have been studied extensively as a conventional design. Surveyed publications through the end of 2018 indicate that more than 50% of reported microchannel geometries are rectangular. Consequently, the aspect ratio of a rectangular microchannel is an important cross-sectional parameter because it defines the relationship between channel width and depth, which directly influences liquid-film distribution, bubble dynamics, and heat transfer. Under flow-boiling conditions, its effect is not straightforward. Experimental studies indicate that, even at constant hydraulic diameter, variations in aspect ratio can significantly alter

thermal performance, and the resulting trends are not always monotonic. With recent advances in fabrication techniques, a wider range of channel shapes, including rectangular, triangular, circular, elliptical, and trapezoidal sections, has become feasible for practical applications. In particular, triangular channels may enhance heat transfer by restricting bubble expansion and promoting thin-film evaporation in the corner regions. In contrast, rectangular channels often offer strong heat transfer performance but may require higher pumping power. However, the reported results are not fully consistent, as the performance of each shape also depends on hydraulic diameter, channel dimensions, and operating conditions.

Straight microchannels typically exhibit laminar flow, weak mixing, and developing thermal boundary layers, which reduce heat transfer along the flow direction[86]. For this reason, wall-geometry modification has emerged as an important passive strategy for improving thermo-hydraulic performance. By modifying the channel wall geometry, it is possible to disturb the flow, promote redevelopment of the thermal boundary layer, increase interaction between the near-wall fluid and the core region, induce local recirculation, and strengthen secondary flow and velocity gradients[70],[86].

Among different wall-geometry modification strategies, wavy microchannels have received considerable attention as an effective means of improving thermo-hydraulic performance. The periodic waviness of the channel wall alters the flow path, inducing repeated flow disturbances that enhance fluid mixing and interrupt thermal boundary-layer growth. Therefore, wavy microchannels are a promising configuration for enhancing heat transfer through wall-geometry design.

2.6 Fundamental Theory of Wavy Microchannel Flow and Heat Transfer

Although the primary focus of this thesis is on two-phase flow in wavy microchannels, an understanding of single-phase flow behavior is essential for interpreting the underlying mechanisms in two-phase systems. Accordingly, this section presents a condensed discussion of the fundamental flow physics in wavy microchannels, based on both experimental and numerical studies. The emphasis is placed on the main physical mechanisms and key findings reported in the literature.

2.6.1 Single-Phase Flow Structure in Wavy Channels

The physical basis for flow instability in wavy channels can be traced to earlier studies on curved and rotating flows. Taylor showed that the flow between rotating cylinders becomes unstable

beyond a critical condition and develops periodic vortex structures. Görtler[20] demonstrated that curvature over a concave surface can destabilize the boundary layer and generate vortices, while Dean showed that curvature in bent pipes induces secondary motion and flow instability. These classical studies established that curvature can strongly modify the structure of laminar flow. The same physical ideas were later extended to wavy channels. Goldstein et al.[18] first observed longitudinal vortices in triangular wavy ducts, while Gaiser et al.[52] showed that similar centrifugal-force-driven instabilities also occur in sinusoidal wavy channels. Nishimura et al.[52] reported that, at low Reynolds numbers, the flow remains essentially two-dimensional, whereas at higher Reynolds numbers transverse vortices undergo periodic roll-up and oscillation, causing the flow to become three-dimensional. In narrow sinusoidal channels, Taylor–Görtler vortices were also observed. Depending on the channel spacing, it was further identified that two main instability mechanisms. The first is shear-layer instability, in which a large recirculation vortex forms, and the shear layer between this vortex and the main flow becomes unstable. The second is centrifugal instability, in which the concave curved wall generates Taylor–Görtler-type vortices. Instability is first observed in the downstream region and then shifts upstream as the Reynolds number increases. In addition, the vortices formed between the upper and lower walls may adopt either a stable or an unstable arrangement, depending on the channel geometry and flow conditions[21].

In laminar microchannel flow, heat-transfer enhancement is closely related to improved fluid mixing. Wavy channels provide a simple planar method for promoting such mixing, because their smooth alternating curvature can alter Dean-vortex structures and induce secondary motion along the flow direction. They are also compact and relatively easy to fabricate, especially with small wave amplitudes and narrow channel spacing [73]. Here, a wavy microchannel is defined as a channel with a smoothly undulating wall or centerline, typically sinusoidal, producing alternating curvature along the streamwise direction.

To describe flow behavior in wavy channels, several basic terms are first introduced. Mixing refers to the exchange between the near-wall fluid, particularly within recirculation zones, and the core flow. The Reynolds number at which the onset of mixing shifts from one wavelength to another is referred to as the *transitional Reynolds number*; in this context, transition does not necessarily indicate turbulence. The reattachment point is the location downstream of a separated recirculation bubble where the main flow reattaches to the wall.

Sinusoidal wavy channels were introduced as smoother alternatives to triangular corrugated passages, aiming to reduce the hydraulic penalty associated with sharp corners while still promoting flow disturbance. Their altered transport behavior is mainly caused by wall curvature,

which induces centrifugal effects, flow separation, and recirculation zones within the wave troughs. At low Reynolds numbers, the flow remains steady and largely follows the channel geometry. As the Reynolds number increases, the flow in wavy channels may pass through several regimes, including laminar, periodic, quasiperiodic, and turbulent. This transition is associated with self-sustained oscillations and the development of vortical structures within the troughs of the wavy walls. In addition, the flow may become three-dimensional, with both spanwise and streamwise vortices contributing to fluid exchange between the near-wall and core regions [29].

The curvature-induced centrifugal effects can destabilize the flow and generate secondary structures such as Taylor–Görtler vortices and spanwise vortices. These vortical motions enhance lateral mixing and modify the velocity and temperature fields within the channel. In addition, the periodic acceleration and deceleration imposed by the wavy geometry promote repeated redevelopment of the hydrodynamic and thermal boundary layers. The strength and structure of these effects depend on both flow conditions and channel geometry, particularly wave amplitude, wavelength, phase shift, and Reynolds number. Together, flow separation, recirculation, secondary vortices, and boundary-layer redevelopment explain the heat-transfer enhancement observed in wavy channels, although this improvement is generally accompanied by an increase in pressure drop [89].

Parameters that determine the strength of waviness

As shown in Figure 2.4, the geometry of a sinusoidal wavy microchannel is commonly described by the wave amplitude A , wavelength or pitch L , channel spacing S , and channel height H . These parameters can be expressed in dimensionless form as the corrugation aspect ratio $c = \frac{2A}{L}$, the spacing ratio $e = \frac{S}{2A}$, and the flow cross-sectional aspect ratio $a = \frac{S}{H}$. Together, these dimensionless groups characterize the severity of wall waviness and the degree of flow confinement inside the wavy channel [41].

Effects based on dimensionless parameters

1. Effect of Relative Amplitude

The effect of the relative amplitude (A/H) on the onset of mixing is more complex. As the relative amplitude increases, the initial onset of instability occurs at lower Reynolds numbers. However, the subsequent upstream movement of the mixing region from the channel exit toward the inlet takes place over a wider Reynolds-number range. By contrast,

Figure 2.4: Schematic representation of the sinusoidal wavy microchannel geometry, adapted from [88].

channels with smaller relative amplitude exhibit a narrower transition range, meaning that once mixing begins, it spreads more rapidly through the channel. Consequently, relative amplitude affects both the initial appearance of instability and the rate at which the unstable region propagates upstream [73, 41].

2. Effect of Wavelength

Lin et al. [40] showed that modifying the wavy channel geometry by decreasing the wavelength in the flow direction can reduce thermal resistance and improve temperature uniformity on the heated wall. This improvement is mainly attributed to the formation of vortical structures in the channel cross-section, which enhance coolant mixing and strengthen convective heat transfer between the fluid and channel walls.

Effect of Waviness, Reynolds Number and Aspect Ratio

1. Effect of Reynolds number

As studied by Zhang et al. [88], the Reynolds number controls whether the flow remains smooth or develops recirculation and swirl. As Re increases, flow separation begins downstream of the wave peak, followed by reattachment before the next wave peak. This creates recirculation cells in the troughs. At moderate and high Reynolds numbers, such as $Re = 100, 400,$ and 600 , these vortices become stronger and occupy a larger portion of the channel. This produces better thermal mixing, a more uniform core temperature, thinner boundary layers, and sharper wall-temperature gradients, thereby increasing the Colburn factor and heat-transfer coefficient. However, the same vortex growth also increases wall

shear stress, leading to a higher friction factor and pressure drop. The paper identifies two main regimes: a streamline or no-swirl regime at low Re , and a swirl-flow regime as Re increases toward about 1000.

2. Effect of waviness

The waviness is called gamma, γ , and is defined in the paper as

$$\gamma = \frac{2A}{L}, \quad (2.11)$$

where A is the wave amplitude and L is the wavelength.

Also, the waviness, called $\gamma = 2A/L$ in the paper and often equivalent to γ for wave severity, measures how strong the wall curvature is, and has been studied by Zhang et al. [88]. A larger γ means a larger wave amplitude relative to the wavelength, so the channel has stronger curvature. Increasing γ strengthens centrifugal effects and causes vortex formation at lower Reynolds numbers. This means that stronger waviness destabilizes the flow earlier and promotes stronger mixing. As γ increases, recirculation zones expand, boundary layers become thinner, and heat transfer improves significantly. Therefore, increasing γ generally improves heat transfer but also increases frictional losses, so the design must balance thermal enhancement with the pressure-drop penalty.

3. Effect of aspect ratio

The aspect ratio controls the degree of flow confinement and affects both heat transfer and pressure drop. Increasing the aspect ratio generally increases the Nusselt number because the hydrodynamic and thermal boundary layers become thinner. However, the pressure drop also increases significantly, especially as the contraction region narrows. Therefore, a higher aspect ratio can improve heat transfer, but an optimum aspect ratio is required when the pressure-drop penalty is also considered [19].

Heat Transfer Enhancement Mechanisms

Heat transfer in wavy channels is governed by two main effects: conventional thermal development and geometry-induced mixing. Wang et al.[77] showed that heat-transfer enhancement in wavy passages is limited in the steady-flow regime, but increases significantly after the onset of self-sustained oscillatory flow. This enhancement is attributed to the destabilization of the laminar thermal boundary layer and stronger exchange between the near-wall fluid and the core flow. Once the trough vortices interact with the core flow, heat transfer increases due to stronger

exchange between the recirculating near-wall fluid and the core region. Thus, heat transfer in wavy channels is closely linked to the spatial development of flow instability and macroscopic mixing.

The study conducted by Manglik et al.[88] further showed that increasing both the wall waviness γ and the inter-fin spacing ratio ε improves heat transfer in the swirl-flow regime, although the benefit of increasing ε becomes limited beyond a critical value, after which the separated region no longer expands significantly.

Overall, the studies reviewed above show that single-phase flow in wavy channels is governed by curvature-induced separation, recirculation, vortex formation, and mixing, all of which strongly affect heat transfer and pressure-drop characteristics. The onset and spatial development of these mechanisms depend on the Reynolds number and geometric parameters such as phase shift, wavelength, amplitude, wall waviness, and spacing ratio. These findings are important for the present work because, in two-phase flow, the same geometry-induced flow structures are expected to influence further bubble motion, interface deformation, liquid-film distribution, phase arrangement, pressure drop, and heat transfer. Therefore, understanding single-phase flow in wavy microchannels provides the physical basis for interpreting the more complex two-phase behavior discussed in the following section[73, 4].

2.6.2 Two-Phase Flow in Wavy Microchannels

In confined microchannel flow boiling, vapor bubbles nucleate at the heated wall and rapidly expand until their size becomes comparable to the channel dimensions. As a result, bubble growth, elongation, and the formation of a thin liquid film between the bubble and the wall play a major role in determining the local heat-transfer mechanism. In contrast to macroscale boiling, the confined nature of the flow makes bubble dynamics, liquid-film thickness, and dryout behavior strongly geometry-dependent.

In contrast to single-phase flow and heat transfer in wavy channels, gas-liquid multiphase flows and heat transfer in wavy channels have been rarely studied. The experimental study by Nilpueng et al. [51] investigated upward gas-liquid multiphase flow in wavy channels with different phase-shift angles between the channel walls. Depending on the superficial velocities of the liquid and gas phases, bubbly, slug, and churn flow regimes were identified. The authors developed two-phase flow pattern maps for three phase-shift configurations and measured the overall pressure drop along the wavy channel. A study by Ahmadpour et al.[3] investigated the thermal-hydraulic performance of gas-liquid multiphase flow in a vertical sinusoidal wavy channel, both in the presence and absence of phase change. The authors numerically examined two different cases: an

adiabatic air–water flow without mass transfer and a condensing R134a flow inside a corrugated channel. The flow was modeled as three-dimensional, unsteady, and turbulent, and the numerical results were validated against available experimental data. In the R134a condensing case, the channel waviness enhanced the condensation heat transfer coefficient. However, this improvement was accompanied by a considerable increase in pressure drop, especially at higher mass fluxes.

When the channel wall is wavy, these mechanisms are further modified by the periodic variation of wall curvature and local flow acceleration. The wavy geometry can alter bubble deformation, recirculation patterns, pressure distribution, and liquid-film transport, thereby changing the local evaporation process and the overall thermo-hydraulic performance. Therefore, the study of two-phase flow in wavy microchannels requires not only the understanding of confined bubble growth and thin-film evaporation, but also the additional influence of geometry-induced instability and mixing.

The fundamental difference between two-phase flow in straight and wavy microchannels lies in the influence of the sidewall geometry on the evolution of the boiling flow. In microchannels, vapor bubbles quickly grow to a size comparable to the channel dimensions, so the local channel shape directly affects flow-pattern transition, liquid redistribution, and bubble confinement. As a result, key boiling characteristics such as ONB, CHF, heat transfer coefficient, and flow-boiling instability become sensitive to the wavy geometry. Thus, in wavy microchannels, the two-phase behavior must be understood as the combined effect of microchannel confinement and periodic sidewall-induced flow modification[83].

2.7 State of the Art on Flow Boiling in Wavy Microchannels

Flow boiling in microchannels has attracted considerable attention for high-heat-flux thermal management because it combines the compactness of microscale passages with the large latent-heat transport capability of phase change. However, conventional straight microchannels often suffer from flow instability, early dryout, and large pressure-drop fluctuations. Therefore, modified channel geometries, such as sinusoidal or wavy microchannels, have been explored to enhance liquid-vapor mixing, promote bubble departure, improve local heat transfer, and delay critical heat-flux conditions [32].

Ma et al. [42] experimentally investigated flow boiling performance in sinusoidal wavy microchannels with secondary channels fabricated by the MEMS technique. Using pure acetone as the working fluid, they compared the thermal-hydraulic behavior of this geometry with that of conventional rectangular microchannels over a wide range of mass fluxes. Their results showed

that the wavy microchannels with secondary channels promoted earlier boiling incipience at lower wall temperature, delayed the onset of critical heat flux, and achieved significantly higher heat transfer coefficients, especially at high mass flux. However, these thermal improvements were accompanied by a higher penalty in two-phase pressure drop. Odumosu et al.[53] numerically investigated vapor-bubble flow boiling and heat transfer in wavy microchannels, with validation against previous results for straight microchannels. The results showed that increasing the channel waviness significantly altered bubble dynamics, leading to faster bubble growth and motion, as well as enhanced heat transfer. In particular, the local Nusselt number in the wavy channel was reported to be up to 2.6 times higher than that in the straight channel. The study also demonstrated the influence of Weber, Capillary, and Jakob numbers on bubble size, growth rate, and liquid-film development, thereby providing important insight into the heat-transfer enhancement mechanism in wavy microchannels.

2.8 Research Gap

A comprehensive review of the existing literature on pulsating heat pipes (PHPs) and wavy microchannels reveals several critical research gaps. While these gaps stem from scientific inquiry, they also highlight the practical challenges engineers and designers face in optimizing thermal systems.

The application of wavy geometry, specifically in the evaporator section of PHPs, has not been fully researched. Despite the significant advantages of geometric modification in enhancing heat transfer in thermal systems, its focused application in the evaporator section of PHPs remains largely unexplored. This gap not only represents a scientific opportunity but also underscores a practical need for improved thermal management in real-world devices. Wang et al. [81] explored a single PHP loop with corrugated walls featuring a phase shift, aiming to validate their numerical model using a relatively simple geometry. Their findings advanced the understanding of thermal performance across various fill ratios. However, the specific influence of a localized wavy or corrugated evaporator section on PHP operation remains unclear. Addressing this gap could lead to tangible improvements in device efficiency and reliability, which are critical to end users.

Existing experimental and numerical studies on modified wavy channels disproportionately emphasize single-phase flow over two-phase flow. Consequently, the understanding of bubble dynamics, phase distribution, interface evolution, and heat transfer enhancement in two-phase wavy microchannels remains limited. In particular, the behavior of the liquid film remains poorly

understood, even though it plays a crucial role in interfacial heat transfer.

In response to these identified gaps, the present research pursues two primary objectives. The first is the development of a *two-dimensional numerical model of a PHP with a wavy evaporator section* to investigate how local geometric waviness influences PHP thermal behavior systematically. The second is the creation of a *two-dimensional numerical model of a wavy microchannel* to deepen our understanding of the mechanisms of two-phase flow and heat transfer within such geometries. By addressing both the scientific and practical dimensions, this study aims to advance knowledge of modified PHP configurations and to contribute to a broader understanding of two-phase flow in wavy channels, ultimately benefiting researchers and practitioners alike.

3 Numerical Implementation and Mathematical Formulation

This chapter gives overview of methods to simulate two-phase flow in minichannels. Within these approaches, a single fluid-framework is employed, and unified set of mass, momentum and energy equations is solved. The main features of the Volume of Fluid method for modeling two-phase flow and associated heat and mass transfer in minichannels are presented in this chapter.

3.1 Basics of Multiphase Flows

Multiphase flow is defined as a flow system in which two or more distinct phases coexist and move simultaneously. A phase is understood as a thermodynamic state of matter, such as a solid, liquid, or gas. In many engineering systems, these phases may coexist and interact within the same flow domain. The term mixture is commonly used to describe two or more phases flowing together and does not necessarily imply that the phases are uniformly mixed.

Multiphase flow is defined as a fluid flow system in which two or more distinct phases coexist and move simultaneously with phase separation occurring at a scale much larger than the molecular level. Multiphase flows can take many forms. Two-phase flows can be classified according to the state of the different phases, such as gas-liquid mixture, gas-solid mixture, liquid-solid mixture, and immiscible liquid-liquid [85]. Among these, gas-liquid flows from thermal and fluid engineering perspectives are of particular importance. Applications include a wide range of interfacial configurations, such as dispersed, separated, or transitional flow structures.

Classification of multiphase flows based on phase morphology yields two types of phases. Firstly, the Disperse Phase: the first phase is dispersed as non-contagious, isolated regions within the second phase (the continuous phase). This system is called a disperse-continuous flow. The other is a continuous phase, in which the phase is continuous throughout the domain, and there is a single well-defined interface with the second phase; such systems are called continuous-continuous flows. Gas-liquid flows can exist in a number of different forms-the motion of gas bubbles in the

liquid phase or the motion of liquid droplets in the gas phase.

In the present thesis, attention is focused on gas–liquid two-phase flow, where the interface between the gas and liquid phases is resolved using the Volume of Fluid (VOF) method [85].

Examples of multiphase flows, based on different classifications are listed below[85].

Figure 3.1: Examples of Multiphase flows from Nature

3.2 Modeling Approaches in Multiphase Flows

A wide range of physical behaviors, including free-surface motion, dispersed bubbles and droplets, solid particles, interface deformation, breakup, coalescence, phase change, and turbulence, are in multiphase flows. Since these phenomena occur over a broad range of spatial and temporal scales, their treatment is much more complex than single-phase flows. It is possible to perform fully resolved simulations in which all relevant scales are directly computed; however, such a detailed description of flow physics comes at the computational cost associated with this level of resolution and is restricted to relatively simple configurations, low-Reynolds-number flows, or systems containing only a limited number of particles, droplets, or bubbles.

For most practical engineering applications, a macroscopic description based on appropriate models is therefore required, which makes possible to simulate large-scale, highly turbulent, and geometrically complex multiphase systems at a significantly reduced computational cost. However, the predictive capability of such methods depends strongly on the quality of the closure relations used to describe unresolved physical processes, including interfacial exchange of mass , as a result multiphase-flow simulations are heavily model dependent, and the choice of modelling

approach must be made according to the physical nature of the problem under consideration.

Challenges in modelling multiphase flows

One particular challenge arises when the interface separating the phases is extremely thin, highly deformable, and often discontinuous. Important fluid properties such as density and viscosity may change abruptly across the interface creating strong gradients that are difficult to represent accurately in a numerical framework. In addition, the interface exerts surface tension forces, which can strongly affect the flow dynamics, especially at small scales.

Another source of complexity is the topological changes that occur in multiphase systems. Interfaces may stretch, merge, break up, or disappear over a broad spectrum of length and time scales. Moreover, separated flow regions, dispersed bubbles or droplets, and even solid particles may coexist within the same physical problem. The situation becomes even more complex when phase change, chemical reactions, or combustion are present, since these phenomena introduce additional couplings between momentum, heat, and mass transfer.

Main modelling strategies

Depending on the nature of the multiphase system and on the degree of detail required, different modelling approaches can be employed. One class includes of Eulerian-Lagrangian approach in which in which the carrier phase is treated as a continuum in the Eulerian frame, while dispersed particles, droplets, or bubbles are tracked individually in a Lagrangian manner. Suitable for dilute dispersed systems, where the discrete phase occupies a relatively small volume fraction and the trajectories of the individual dispersed elements are of interest[14].

Eulerian–Eulerian approach, in which two or more phases are treated as interpenetrating continua and solved in the Eulerian frame. This approach is well suited for dense dispersed flows or systems containing a large number of bubbles, droplets, or particles, for which individual tracking would be computationally impractical. Within this framework, different formulations may be used depending on whether the flow is separated by a distinct interface or consists of a dispersed phase distributed throughout the carrier fluid, as shown in Fig. 3.3 [12].

Figure 3.2: Modelling approaches in multiphase flows. Adapted from Drew and Passman [66].

For systems with phases separated by a well-defined interface, interface-resolving techniques are used. The interface can be represented directly on the computational mesh. When the interface is associated with a free surface or with bubbles and droplets that are larger than the local mesh scale, it can be represented directly on the grid. In this situation, the interface geometry can be reconstructed with sufficient accuracy, and methods such as VOF can be successfully employed.

On the other hand, when bubbles, droplets, or particles are smaller than the computational grid size, the interface can no longer be resolved explicitly, as shown in Fig. 3.3. In that case, the dispersed structures become sub-grid-scale features, and their effect on the carrier phase must be introduced through suitable models rather than through direct interface resolution. Therefore, the choice between interface-resolving and dispersed-phase modeling approaches is largely determined by the relative size of the interfacial structures compared to the mesh resolution.

This section explains a class of multiphase formulations in which the interface is resolved directly rather than treated only in an averaged or approximate manner. Since the interface motion is computed explicitly enough, no empirical closure laws are needed for interfacial effects. However, accurately resolving the interface requires a much finer grid than that used in other multiphase flow formulations. Their advantage, however, is that they provide very detailed information about the local flow physics near the interface, often beyond what experiments can measure directly.

The two main assumptions in these formulations are as follows: First, the interface is treated as sharp, meaning it is assumed to have zero thickness, but physically the interface actually has a finite transition thickness; however, at the continuum scale, the thickness of the interface is so small that it is reasonable to idealize it as infinitely thin. Secondly, molecular forces acting at

Figure 3.3: Schematic comparison of bubble-size resolution in a computational grid [66].

the interface are represented at the continuum level by surface tension, which is concentrated on that sharp interface.

There are two ways to describe the interface; the focus in this thesis is limited to where the interface is represented implicitly by an indicator or marker function defined over the whole domain. This leads to a single fluid formulation, where one set of governing equations is solved everywhere, while local material properties and interfacial forces depend on the value of the indicator function[43].

3.3 Governing Equations

The basis of the model for simulating two-phase flows is the continuity equation and the conservation equations for momentum and energy.

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{u}) = 0 \quad (3.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \vec{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{u} \vec{u}) = \nabla \cdot \tau + \vec{f} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho e)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho e \vec{u}) = \nabla \cdot (\tau \cdot \vec{u}) - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} + \vec{f} \cdot \vec{u} \quad (3.3)$$

The following assumptions are used to simplify the set of equations (3.1) to (3.3).

- The material properties are constant.

The material properties are taken at the saturation condition, i.e. the equilibrium between liquid and vapor phase, corresponding to the pressure level at which the simulation is performed. The actual temperature and pressure can locally differ from the saturation values. However, these deviations are typically significantly smaller than 10% of the absolute value of the temperature or pressure. Therefore, all material properties are assumed to be independent of temperature and pressure.

- The fluid is incompressible.

The liquid phase is incompressible. As the maximum flow velocity within the vapor phase usually does not exceed a few meters per second, the Mach number

$$Ma = \frac{u}{\sqrt{\kappa R_{\text{gas}} T}} \quad (3.4)$$

is sufficiently small to neglect compressibility effects. Therefore, both phases can be treated as incompressible and the velocity field is divergence-free.

- The fluid is Newtonian.

For the fluids used in the simulations in the present thesis, the stress tensor τ in Eq. (3.2) depends linearly on the pressure, the divergence of the velocity field, and the rate of deformation:

$$\tau = - \left(p + \frac{2}{3} \mu \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \right) I + \mu \left[\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T \right] \quad (3.5)$$

For an incompressible fluid, this equation can be simplified because the velocity field is divergence-free:

$$\tau = -pI + \mu \left[\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T \right] \quad (3.6)$$

- Fourier's law can be applied for the heat flux.

According to Fourier's law, the heat flux vector \mathbf{q} in Eq. (3.3) depends linearly on the temperature gradient and the thermal conductivity k of the fluid:

$$\mathbf{q} = -k \nabla T \quad (3.7)$$

- Viscous dissipation and the power supply or release due to volumetric forces are negligible.

As discussed above, the flow velocity and, consequently, the shear stress are rather low. Therefore, the effect of viscous dissipation, $\nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\tau} \cdot \mathbf{u})$, and the power supply or release due to volumetric forces, $\mathbf{f} \cdot \mathbf{u}$, in Eq. (3.3) are negligible compared to the conductive and convective heat transport and the heat consumption or supply due to evaporation or condensation.

Applying the above assumptions, the general formulation of the mass, momentum, and energy conservation equations can be simplified to the following set of equations[37]:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (3.8)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho\mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{u}\mathbf{u}) - \nabla \cdot \left(\mu \left[\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T \right] \right) = -\nabla p + \mathbf{f} \quad (3.9)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho cT)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho cT\mathbf{u}) - \nabla \cdot (k\nabla T) = 0 \quad (3.10)$$

3.4 Numerical Implementation Using the Finite Volume Method

The numerical solution is obtained using OpenFOAM as the computational framework. Based on the Finite Volume Method (FVM), the governing partial differential equations are discretized over the computational domain and converted into a system of algebraic equations:

$$A \cdot x = b \quad (4.1)$$

An important characteristic of the finite volume method (FVM) is its conservative formulation. Since the governing balance equations are integrated over each control volume, the resulting discrete equations also satisfy the conservation of the respective quantities, such as mass, momentum, and energy[66].

General methodology includes the following steps[66]:

1. The computational domain is subdivided into control volumes (Cells)
2. For each of these control volumes, the governing balance equations are written in integral form

3. The integrals are then evaluated using numerical approximation
4. The field values and their gradients at specific locations are approximated by interpolation from values stored at cell centers or nodes
5. This procedure results in a system of algebraic equations that is assembled and solved to obtain a numerical solution

3.4.1 Overview of the Finite Volume Method Formulation

To illustrate the basic idea of the FVM, the general transport equation can be taken as the starting point given as belows: The starting point of the finite volume discretization is the subdivision of the computational domain Ω into a finite number of non-overlapping subdomains V_i ($i = 1, \dots, N$), referred to as control volumes (CVs), together with the associated nodes at which the unknown variables are evaluated. The union of all control volumes must cover the entire computational domain.

To illustrate the basic idea of the FVM, the general transport equation can be taken as the starting point, given as below:

$$\underbrace{\int_{V_P} \frac{\partial \rho \phi}{\partial t} dV}_{\text{Temporal term}} + \underbrace{\int_{V_P} \nabla \cdot (\rho u \phi) dV}_{\text{Convective term}} - \underbrace{\int_{V_P} \nabla \cdot (\rho \Gamma_\phi \nabla \phi) dV}_{\text{Diffusion term}} = \underbrace{\int_{V_P} S_\phi(\phi) dV}_{\text{Source term}} \quad (4.2)$$

This transport equation is solved for the variable of interest ϕ in a given domain, subject to appropriate boundary and initial conditions. Since the transport equation is of second order, for good accuracy the order of discretization should be equal to or higher than the order of the differential equation.

After having defined the control volumes (CVs), the balance equations describing the problem are formulated in integral form for each CV. Normally, these equations are directly available from the corresponding continuum mechanical conservation laws (applied to a CV), but they can also be derived by integration from the corresponding differential equations. By integration of (4.1) over an arbitrary control volume V and application of the Gauss integral theorem, one obtains:

$$\int_S \left(\rho u_i \phi - \alpha \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_i} \right) n_i dS = \int_V f dV \quad (4.3)$$

where S is the surface of the control volume and n_i are the components of the unit normal vector to the surface. The integral balance equation (4.3) constitutes the starting point for the further discretization of the considered problem with a finite volume method (FVM).

It should be noted that up to this point, no approximation has been introduced, i.e., the flux balance in above equation is still exact. The actual discretization now mainly consists in the approximation of the surface integrals and the volume integral in (4.3) by suitable averages of the corresponding integrands at the CV faces.

We start with the approximation of the surface integrals in (4.3), which, for a cell-centered variable arrangement, is suitably carried out in two steps. Firstly, approximation of the surface integrals (fluxes) by values on the CV faces and secondly, approximation of the variable values at the CV faces by node values[1].

Herein, Gauss' theorem is already applied to transform the volume integral of the divergence terms into surface integrals. The volume and surface integrals in Eq. (3.3) are then replaced by numerical approximations (step 3).

$$\begin{aligned} \int_V \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} dV &\approx \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} \right)_c V_c \\ \int_S (u\phi) dS &\approx \sum_f \phi_f u_f \cdot S_f \\ \int_S D\nabla\phi dS &\approx \sum_f D_f (\nabla\phi)_f \cdot S_f \\ \int_V \dot{\phi} dV &\approx \dot{\phi}_c V_c \end{aligned}$$

Here, the subscripts c and f denote a cell or face of the computational mesh.

The face values appearing in the convective and diffusive fluxes must be obtained by interpolation from the values stored at the centroids of the adjacent control volumes sharing face f . In particular, the approximation of the convective flux requires the evaluation of the transported quantity ϕ at the control-volume faces, while the diffusive flux requires an approximation of the normal gradient of ϕ at these faces based on the values at the neighboring cell centers.

After the spatial discretization, the temporal discretization can be applied to the resulting semi-discrete transport equation. Proceeding in this way corresponds to the Method of Lines (MOL), in which the governing equations are first discretized in space while remaining continuous in time. The subsequent time integration can then be performed using an appropriate temporal discretization scheme. This approach is also employed in OpenFOAM, where the governing equations are discretized in space using the finite volume method and advanced in time using user-selected temporal schemes.

In integral form over the time interval from t to $t + \Delta t$, the semi-discrete general transport

equation can be written as

$$\int_t^{t+\Delta t} \left[\left(\frac{\partial \rho \phi}{\partial t} \right)_P V_P + \sum_f S_f \cdot (\rho u \phi)_f - \sum_f S_f \cdot (\Gamma_\phi \nabla \phi)_f \right] dt = \int_t^{t+\Delta t} (S_c V_P + S_p V_P \phi_P) dt. \quad (4.4)$$

At this stage, different time discretization schemes may be employed, such as the implicit Euler method, the Crank–Nicolson scheme, or other higher-order approaches. A major advantage of the Method of Lines is that the spatial and temporal terms can be discretized independently. As a result, numerical approximations of different orders of accuracy may be chosen for space and time. In addition, individual terms can be treated differently in order to achieve the desired balance between accuracy, stability, and computational effort[66].

Time-Step Control and Spatial Resolution

The temporal and spatial resolution must be chosen such that the relevant physical processes are adequately resolved. The resolution of this decomposition, i.e., the size of the cells and the time steps, must be fine enough to capture the relevant physical processes. Furthermore, the time-step size is constrained by the propagation speed of information on the numerical mesh. This restriction is commonly expressed in terms of the Courant number,

$$Co = \frac{u \Delta t}{\Delta x} \quad (4.5)$$

which measures the distance a fluid parcel travels during one time step relative to the cell size. In two-phase flow simulations, this criterion is particularly important, and the Courant number should generally remain well below unity. In the present work, adaptive time stepping is used to ensure that the prescribed maximum Courant number is not exceeded. Furthermore, local mesh refinement can be used to increase spatial resolution in regions with large gradients or important interfacial transport processes. This is especially relevant for three-dimensional two-phase flows, where the most important flow features are often concentrated near the phase interface rather than in the bulk regions.

The resulting algebraic equation system is solved by iterative pressure-correction methods for the Navier–Stokes equations, where algorithms such as SIMPLE and PISO form the basis of the PIMPLE procedure commonly used for transient simulations.

3.5 Mathematical Formulation of Two-Phase flows

The present study focuses on liquid–vapor slug/plug flow in a minichannel, where confinement effects make surface tension a dominant force in comparison with gravity, which is neglected. Because the flow dynamics are governed to a large extent by the shape and motion of the liquid–vapor interface, an interface-resolving formulation is required. Accordingly, the problem is considered for incompressible Newtonian fluids in a confined domain, with emphasis on surface-tension-controlled interfacial behavior.

3.5.1 Single Fluid Formulation for Two-Phase flow

In the single-fluid formulation, only one set of flow equations is written and solved over the entire computational domain. While the distinction between the phases is introduced through material properties that change abruptly at the phase interface, the whole domain is treated as being a single equivalent fluid. The physical effects associated with the interface are incorporated into the governing equations as source terms localized at the interface, and these are represented mathematically by means of Dirac delta functions. As a result, the jump conditions given by Eqs. (1.11)–(1.14) are replaced by equivalent delta-function source terms, so that the only boundary conditions that must be imposed explicitly are those at the outer boundaries of the computational domain.

The transport equations in the single-fluid formulation are written as

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = \dot{m} \delta_S(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{\Gamma(t)} \dot{m} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_S) ds \quad (3.11)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho \mathbf{g} + \int_{\Gamma(t)} \sigma \kappa \mathbf{n} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_S) ds \quad (3.12)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho c_p T)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho c_p \mathbf{u} T) = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} + \boldsymbol{\tau} : \nabla \mathbf{u} - \int_{\Gamma(t)} \dot{q} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_S) ds \quad (3.13)$$

where $\Gamma(t)$ denotes the interface between the phases, and \dot{q} represents the interfacial heat flux. The term $\delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_S)$ is a multidimensional Dirac delta function, which is non-zero only at the location where $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_S$. Here, $\mathbf{x}_S = \mathbf{x}(s, t)$ is a parametrization of the interface $\Gamma(t)$ [43]. Through this formulation, the interfacial effects are introduced into the bulk conservation equations in a localized manner. For phase-change problems, an additional model is required in order to

describe the interfacial contributions associated with \dot{m} and \dot{q} . In particular, these quantities must be related to an appropriate condition imposed on the interface temperature to properly represent the phase-change process.

Since the governing equations given in Eqs. (3.11)–(3.13) have essentially the same mathematical structure as the single-phase flow equations differing only by the presence of additional source terms, similar numerical solution strategies can be employed. Moreover, these equations are subject to the same type of boundary conditions at the domain boundaries. Nevertheless, the treatment of the interface requires several additional numerical ingredients[43]:

- definition of a phase indicator function $\alpha(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in order to distinguish between the two fluids and thereby evaluate the appropriate local material properties;
- a suitable procedure to update this marker function as the interface moves with time;
- numerical modeling of the interfacial terms represented by the delta functions, including the construction of a suitable approximation of the delta function on the computational mesh;
- reconstruction of the interface geometry in terms of its normal vector and curvature, since these quantities are needed for the calculation of surface tension forces.

In general, the marker function is chosen so that it takes the value unity in one selected primary phase and zero in the secondary phase. It is defined using the delta function as

$$\alpha(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int_{\Omega(t)} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_S) dV \quad (3.14)$$

where $\Omega(t)$ is a control volume. The gradient of the marker function is non-zero only when the control volume contains a portion of the interface $\Gamma(t)$. Therefore, it can be used to identify the interface normal vector, according to

$$\nabla\alpha = \int_{\Gamma(t)} \mathbf{n} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_S) ds = \mathbf{n} \delta_S(\mathbf{x}) \quad (3.15)$$

This relation shows that the gradient of the marker function carries information about the location and orientation of the interface.

Using this indicator-function definition, any generic material property b of the fluid can be expressed as

$$b(\mathbf{x}, t) = b_2 + (b_1 - b_2)\alpha(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (3.16)$$

where b_1 and b_2 are the values of the property in fluid 1 and fluid 2, respectively. In this way, fluid properties such as density, viscosity, and thermal conductivity can be represented within a unified formulation throughout the computational domain.

However, because the marker function defined by Eq. (3.14) produces an abrupt change in material properties across the interface, numerical instabilities may arise when solving the flow equations, especially for large density and viscosity ratios. For this reason, it is common in practical computations to replace the sharp marker function with a smoothed version, thereby improving numerical stability.

The single-fluid formulation is especially convenient for the simulation of two-phase flows on fixed grids. Most modern numerical methods based on this approach originate from the Marker-And-Cell (MAC) method introduced by Harlow and Welch in 1965 [25],[43]; a review is given by McKee et al. [48]. At present, most multiphase CFD solvers with surface tracking rely on the single-fluid formulation rather than the two-fluid formulation, since it avoids the need to explicitly handle a moving interface as a separate boundary between two independently solved fluid domains.

The method used to advect the indicator function divides the numerical schemes based on the single-fluid formulation into two main categories:

- interface tracking methods: the interface is represented by marker points, connected together to form a moving front, which is advected in a Lagrangian manner by the flow field computed on a fixed background grid. In this case, the interface is transported explicitly by moving the marker points, and at each time step the indicator function is reconstructed from their updated positions;
- interface capturing methods: the interface topology is represented implicitly within the indicator-function field, which is advected by solving a conservation equation. The conservation equation for the marker function can be derived by substituting Eq. (3.16), written for the phase density, into the mass conservation equation, Eq. (3.11), leading to the following pure mass and marker-function conservation equations [39], respectively:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (3.17)$$

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \alpha = (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{V}) \cdot \nabla \alpha \quad (3.18)$$

Depending on how the marker function is advected, each method has its own procedure to approximate the delta function and to compute the interface geometry. Among the most widely used approaches are the Front Tracking (FT) method, which belongs to the interface tracking class, and the Level-Set (LS) method, which is an interface capturing approach; both are briefly introduced in the following sections. The Volume of Fluid (VOF) method, which also belongs to the interface capturing class, is described in greater detail, since it is which is employed in the present thesis[43].

3.5.2 Volume of Fluid (VOF) Method

Several numerical approaches have been developed to represent moving interfaces, including moving-mesh techniques, marker-point methods, level-set methods, phase-field models, and Volume of Fluid (VOF) formulations. VOF and level-set methods are most widely used since they can naturally handle large interface deformations and topological changes such as breakup and coalescence. Although the level-set method offers smooth geometric description of the interface it cannot conserve mass, on other hand VOF is inherently mass conservative. But, challenges with VOF include accurate interface reconstruction and advection of interface. The present work uses VOF framework, whose main formulation and numerical implementation are described in following section.[64],[67]

3.5.3 Fundamental VOF equation

The VOF method is widely used for simulating two-phase flows with a sharp interface. The interface is represented implicitly through a phase-indicator function and, in the discrete finite-volume formulation, through the corresponding cell volume fraction as illustrated in Fig. 3.4. Consider a system of two phases occupying a computational domain, described by the velocity field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, the pressure field $p(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and the instantaneous position of the moving sharp interface. Together with the incompressibility condition and the appropriate boundary conditions at the interface and domain boundaries, the Navier–Stokes equations govern the temporal evolution of the velocity and pressure fields[67].

In the VOF framework, the phase distribution may be represented through a discontinuous indicator function. Let phase A be the reference phase and phase B the secondary phase. A Heaviside function $H(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is introduced such that it takes the value unity in phase A and zero

Figure 3.4: Volume of Fluid (VOF) representation of a two-phase interface evolution. The left panel shows the resolved interface, commonly represented by an iso-contour of the volume fraction, such as $\alpha = 0.5$, while the right panel illustrates the underlying computational grid used to solve the phase-fraction transport equation and reconstruct the interface within each control volume. Adapted from paper.[68]

in phase B . The density field can then be written as

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = \rho_A H(\mathbf{x}, t) + \rho_B (1 - H(\mathbf{x}, t)) \quad (3.14)$$

where ρ_A and ρ_B are the densities of phases A and B , respectively. With this representation, the interface evolution in time is determined by the continuity equation. This is the basis of the Volume-of-Fluid (VOF) method, where, in the spirit of the Finite Volume Method (FVM), the equation is integrated over a control volume to account for the change of mass within the volume.

In a finite-volume formulation, the continuity equation is integrated over a control volume. For the i -th computational cell, this yields

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{V_i} \rho(\mathbf{x}, t) dV + \sum_f \int_f \rho(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot d\mathbf{S} = 0 \quad (3.15)$$

where V_i is the cell volume, and the summation extends over all faces f of the cell.

Substituting Eq. (3.14) into Eq. (3.15), the time evolution of the volume fraction is obtained as

$$\alpha_i(t + \Delta t) = \alpha_i(t) - \frac{1}{V_i} \sum_f \int_t^{t+\Delta t} \int_f H(\mathbf{x}, \tau) \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, \tau) \cdot d\mathbf{S} d\tau \quad (3.16)$$

The volume fraction of phase A in cell i is defined as

$$\alpha_i(t) = \frac{1}{V_i} \int_{V_i} H(\mathbf{x}, t) dV \quad (3.17)$$

and represents the fraction of the cell occupied by the reference phase. Accordingly,

- $\alpha_i = 1$ indicates that the cell is completely filled with phase A ,
- $\alpha_i = 0$ indicates that the cell contains only phase B ,
- $0 < \alpha_i < 1$ identifies an interfacial cell.

This equation constitutes the fundamental evolution equation of the VOF method. In this framework, the interface is implicitly represented by the distribution of cell volume fractions over the computational mesh.[43][64]

Volume of Fluid (VOF) methods can be broadly classified into algebraic and geometric formulations, depending on how the phase-indicator function is represented and transported numerically. Algebraic VOF methods are among the earliest interface-capturing approaches and are based on the classical VOF method of Hirt and Nichols. In these methods, the volume fraction is transported using algebraic discretization schemes without explicitly reconstructing the interface geometry. The numerical fluxes are therefore computed directly from the volume-fraction field, which makes the method relatively simple and computationally efficient. Algebraic VOF methods are commonly divided into compressive schemes and THINC-type schemes, where THINC stands for the tangent of the hyperbola for interface capturing. In contrast, geometric VOF methods reconstruct the interface explicitly within each computational cell using the known volume-fraction distribution. The reconstructed interface is then advected by calculating the volume of fluid transported across the cell faces using geometrical procedures. These methods generally provide a sharper and more accurate representation of the interface, but they are more complex to implement than algebraic VOF methods.[50]

The advantages of the VOF method are its relative simplicity, since only one additional transport equation must be solved. At the same time, when geometric flux calculations are used, the method achieves mass conservation at machine accuracy, which is one of its most important strengths. On the other hand, since volume fraction is discontinuous, conventional differential schemes are not well-suited to discontinuous variables, leading to an inaccurate evaluation of interface curvature based on the volume fraction field. For this reason, many improved interface-reconstruction and curvature-evaluation techniques have been proposed in the literature. In the present work, this motivates the adoption of an advanced geometric reconstruction strategy, which is discussed in the following section.[43][64]

However, the major difficulty with VOF is that the volume fraction field alone does not uniquely determine the exact geometry inside a partially filled cell. Since different interface shapes may yield the same set of cell volume fractions, it is helpful to identify how much of a reference phase is present in a cell, rather than the actual phase arrangement in the cell, as shown in Fig. 3.5. In particular, the instantaneous phase distribution at the cell faces is unknown, even though this information is required to evaluate the flux term in the volume-fraction equation. Here, the flux term represents the transport of the reference phase across the faces of a computational cell. Its evaluation requires knowledge of the instantaneous phase distribution at the cell faces, since only the portion of the face occupied by the reference phase contributes to the volume-fraction flux.

Figure 3.5: Non-unique interface reconstruction from identical VOF volume fractions.[68]

For this reason, a subgrid-scale model of the interface must be introduced, or equivalently, the interface must be reconstructed inside each interfacial cell. If the interface is assumed to be locally smooth, then each point on it may be associated with a characteristic length scale given by the local radius of curvature R . When the local cell size Δx is much smaller than R , the interface segment inside an individual cell can be approximated well by a plane. Conversely, when Δx becomes comparable to R , a planar approximation is no longer adequate. Therefore, geometric VOF methods rely on the assumption that the mesh is sufficiently fine to satisfy $\Delta x < R$, within the practical constraints imposed by computational cost.

Also, since the volume fraction field is discontinuous across the interface, standard interpolation schemes are not suitable; low-order schemes tend to diffuse the interface excessively, whereas higher-order schemes may preserve a sharper interface but often introduce spurious oscillations. This is where the computing phase fluxes geometrically in interface and near-interface cells come into the picture. This procedure involves two steps:

- reconstruction of the interface inside the cell by means of a piecewise linear approximation;
- evaluation of the fluxes by geometrically advecting the reconstructed interface along a direction normal to itself.

3.5.4 Interface Capturing

In the VOF method, each computational cell is assigned a volume fraction, α , which represents the portion of the cell occupied by the reference phase. Pure cells have $\alpha = 0$ or $\alpha = 1$, while interfacial cells have values between these limits. Once these discrete volume-fraction values replace the exact interface geometry, the interface is no longer uniquely known. Therefore, an interface reconstruction procedure is required to recover an approximate interface shape inside mixed cells. The main requirement of this reconstruction is that it must remain consistent with the known fluid volume in each cell [64].

3.5.5 Interface Reconstruction Schemes

In geometric VOF methods, the interface within an interfacial cell is commonly approximated as locally planar. Under this assumption, the objective of the reconstruction step is to determine the local position and orientation of the interface at the beginning of each time step. More specifically, the reconstruction procedure provides the interface center position, x_S , and the unit normal vector, \hat{n}_S , for every interfacial cell. In geometric VOF methods, a cell i is typically identified as an interfacial cell if its volume fraction satisfies

$$\varepsilon < \alpha_i < 1 - \varepsilon,$$

where ε denotes a small numerical tolerance, often taken to be on the order of 10^{-8} . By convention, the interface unit normal vector $\hat{n}_{S,i}$ is directed from fluid A toward fluid B. The following subsections describe the reconstruction procedures used to determine x_S and \hat{n}_S [68].

3.5.6 Outline of iso-Alpha Method

In the iso-Alpha approach, cell-centered volume-fraction values are first interpolated to the cell vertices, which enables the construction of an approximately planar iso-surface inside each interfacial cell. The portions occupied by two fluids is then represented by this isosurface that divides the cell into two subcells. However, the placement of this iso-surface inside the cell is dependent on choice of the iso-value, if same iso-value is chosen for each cell, then the reconstructed interface pieces in neighboring cells will connect continuously, however it does not preserve the correct cell volume fraction. To satisfy the local volume conservation, isoAlpha therefore determines an individual isovalue for each cell such that the reconstructed surface cuts the cell into subvolumes matching the known phase fraction. As a consequence, the reconstructed

interface is locally volume-consistent, although it is not strictly continuous across cell faces[68].

Algorithm 1: isoAlpha interface reconstruction procedure. Summarized and taken from paper. [68].

Determine the set of interfacial cells $\mathcal{I} = \{i \mid \varepsilon < \alpha_i < 1 - \varepsilon\}$;

foreach $i \in \mathcal{I}$ **do**

Interpolate the surrounding cell-centred volume fractions to each vertex v of cell i :

$$\alpha_v = \frac{\sum_{k \in C_v} w_k \alpha_k}{\sum_{k \in C_v} w_k}$$

where C_v denotes the set of cells connected to vertex v , and w_k are inverse-distance interpolation weights;

- Select candidate isovalues from the range of interpolated vertex values in cell i ;
 - Construct a trial isosurface inside cell i for a given isovalue;
 - Compute the volume of the subcell generated by the trial isosurface;
 - Adjust the isovalue until the reconstructed subcell volume matches the phase volume prescribed by the cell volume fraction α_i ;
 - Compute the centroid $\mathbf{x}_{S,i}$ and unit normal $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{S,i}$ of the final isosurface;
-

The interface reconstruction in an interfacial cell as an internal iso-surface based on values of the interpolated volume fraction field. For a trial isovalue, the intersections of the isosurface with the cell edges are determined by linear interpolation, and the resulting cut points are connected to form an internal polygonal face, referred to as the *isoface*. The position of the isoface is adjusted such that the subcell volume generated by the cut is consistent with the known cell volume fraction. Once a volume-consistent isoface has been obtained, its geometric properties are used to define the local interface position and orientation.

If the reconstructed isoface consists of N_v ordered vertices \mathbf{x}_k , an average point is first introduced as

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{1}{N_v} \sum_{k=1}^{N_v} \mathbf{x}_k. \quad (3.18)$$

The face area vector is then obtained from a triangular decomposition of the polygon,

$$\mathbf{n}_f = \sum_{k=1}^{N_v} \mathbf{n}_{f,k}, \quad (3.19)$$

where

$$\mathbf{n}_{f,k} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{x}_{k+1} - \mathbf{x}_k) \times (\bar{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{x}_k), \quad (3.20)$$

with $\mathbf{x}_{N_v+1} = \mathbf{x}_1$. The corresponding unit normal vector is

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}}_f = \frac{\mathbf{n}_f}{|\mathbf{n}_f|}. \quad (3.21)$$

The centroid of the isoface is finally computed as

$$\mathbf{x}_f = \sum_{k=1}^{N_v} \frac{|\mathbf{n}_{f,k}|}{|\mathbf{n}_f|} \frac{\mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{x}_{k+1} + \bar{\mathbf{x}}}{3}. \quad (3.22)$$

These quantities provide the local interface orientation and position within the cell[68]. The advantage of the iso-Alpha using the interpolated volume fraction makes the method computationally fast, but it is less accurate.

3.5.7 Outline of PLIC-RDF Method

Young and coworkers made a major advance in volume-tracking techniques by developing piecewise-linear reconstruction methods. Interface is constructed within each cell as a linear segment in two dimensions or a planar surface in three dimensions. While the interface position is determined by enforcing consistency with the prescribed cell volume fraction, the interface orientation is determined from an estimate of the interface normal. Family of methods based on this approach are known as PLIC (Piecewise Linear Interface Calculation).[64]

In VOF methods, the volume fraction field typically varies sharply across the interface, often over the width of a single computational cell. As a result, quantities that depend on accurate spatial derivatives of the volume fraction, such as interface normals and curvature, are difficult to evaluate accurately. For this reason, a signed distance function is reconstructed (RDF- Reconstructed Distance Function) from the volume fraction field, since it provides a smoother and more suitable representation for derivative-based geometric calculations[67],[68].

In plic-RDF method, the interface is reconstructed from the volume fraction, usually as linear interface per cell with piecewise linear reconstruction (PLIC method)[62][68]. The interface inside a mixed cell is approximated by a plane[68]. Because of this, plicRDF gives a more accurate estimate of interface orientation; it is slower than isoAlpha. The Algorithmic overview of the method is given below.

Algorithm 2: Algorithm for PLIC-RDF. Summarized and taken from paper[67].

```

foreach  $i \in \mathcal{I}$  do
  if previous-time-step normals are used and  $\beta_i < 10^\circ$  then
    | Initialise  $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{S,i}$  by interpolation from the previous time step;
  else
    | Initialise  $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{S,i} = \nabla\alpha_i/|\nabla\alpha_i|$ ;
  for  $iter = 1$  to  $maxIter$  do
    foreach  $i \in \mathcal{I}$  do
      if  $\beta_i < 30^\circ$  then
        | Compute the projected vertex coordinates  $d_v = \mathbf{x}_v \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{S,i}$  for all vertices  $\mathbf{x}_v$  of
        | cell  $i$ ;
        | Reconstruct a planar interface in cell  $i$  such that the cut volume satisfies
        |  $\Lambda(d^*) = \alpha_i$ ;
        | Evaluate the interface centre  $\mathbf{x}_{S,i}$  of the reconstructed plane;
      Compute the reconstructed distance function  $\psi$  in all interfacial cells and their point
      neighbours using  $\mathbf{x}_S$  and  $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_S$ ;
      Evaluate  $\nabla\psi$  in the interfacial cells using a least-squares gradient method;
      Compute the updated interface normal  $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_S^{new} = \nabla\psi/|\nabla\psi|$ ;
      Compute the residuals  $res$  and  $res_{curv}$  from the difference between  $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_S$  and  $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_S^{new}$ ;
      if  $res < tol \vee res_{curv} < tol_{curv}$  then
        | break;
      else
        | Set  $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_S = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_S^{new}$ ;

```

3.5.8 Geometric Interface Advection in iso-Advectord

The second step of the VOF algorithm is propagation. Once the interface has been reconstructed, its motion by the underlying flow field must be modeled by a suitable advection algorithm. In the iso-Advectord method, the geometric advection step computes the phase volume transported across each cell face during a given time step. In the first approximation for the method, since values for velocity are available at only beginning of time interval, the velocity is assumed to remain constant over the time step and is represented by a suitable face flux evaluated at t^n . This helps to express the transported phase volume as product of volumetric face flux and the time integral of the portion of face occupied by the considered phase. The main task in the advection procedure is not only to evaluate the total face flux, but also to determine how the area of the face submerged in a given liquid evolves during one time step.

In iso-Advectord, the reconstructed interface geometry from the upwind cell adjacent to a face is used to estimate the submerged area of that face. Isoface represents the interface inside the cell; isoface motion during the timestep is approximated from the local velocity field. More

specifically, the velocity is interpolated to the centroid of the isoface, and its component along the interface normal is used to define the normal speed of interface propagation. Based on this speed, the times at which the moving isoface reaches the face's vertices can be estimated. These so-called vertex arrival times divide the time step into several subintervals, within each of which the face–interface intersection line sweeps the face in a geometrically simple manner. Hence, the submerged face area can be expressed piecewise as a quadratic function of time, and its temporal integral can therefore be evaluated analytically. This yields the transported phase volume across the face in a geometrically consistent way.

Phase transport through each internal face is evaluated once and then used consistently for both cells sharing that face, ensuring global conservation. Since the interface is reconstructed locally in each cell rather than globally over the mesh, neighboring cells may predict slightly different interface positions on their common face. This mismatch introduces a small geometric inconsistency and therefore represents an approximation in the method.

Additionally, to keep volume fraction within physically meaningful limits, a bounding step is introduced. Although the scheme is generally accurate for well-resolved interfaces and timesteps satisfying the CFL condition, numerical errors may arise. In such situations, the method redistributes the face fluxes such that the volume fraction is brought back to bounds, and if redistribution is not enough, a stronger correction, such as clipping the volume fraction, is adopted. Further, the current implementation assumes that only one isoface exists inside a cell. In case of highly non-planar faces or interface collision or topological change where two separate interfaces may exist inside the same cell the method may be inadequate, however despite limitations, the method remains accurate and conservative[67],[64].

3.5.9 Surface Tension Modeling

The imbalance in intermolecular forces at a fluid interface gives rise to surface tension. Hence, the interface behaves as if under tension, generating localized forces that act on the surrounding fluid. These forces play a major role in many interfacial phenomena, including capillary flows, droplet dynamics, cavitation, and spray formation. In numerical simulations, however, treating surface tension at sharply defined, topologically complex interfaces directly is difficult. To address this, Brackbill et al. [9] introduced the Continuum Surface Force (CSF) model, in which surface tension is reformulated as a continuous body force distributed over a thin transition region around the interface. This approach simplifies the numerical treatment of interfacial forces and enables the simulation of complex, time-dependent interface motions in both two- and three-dimensional flows[62].

In a single-fluid formulation on a fixed grid, it is more convenient to represent the capillary force as a volumetric source term in the momentum equation rather than as a force acting on a geometrically sharp boundary. For this reason, the surface tension force is reformulated as

$$\mathbf{f}_{\sigma,v}(\mathbf{x}) = \sigma\kappa(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})\delta_S(\mathbf{x}),$$

where σ is the surface tension coefficient, κ is the local curvature, \mathbf{n} is the unit normal vector to the interface, and $\delta_S(\mathbf{x})$ is a surface delta function that concentrates the force within the finite-thickness interfacial region.

The most widely used formulation of this type is the Continuum Surface Force (CSF) model introduced by Brackbill et al[9]. In the CSF approach, surface tension is interpreted as a continuous force distributed across the interface region identified by the marker function of the chosen interface-capturing method. Accordingly, the volumetric force is written as

$$\mathbf{f}_{\sigma,v}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\rho(\mathbf{x})}{\langle\rho\rangle} \frac{\sigma\kappa(\mathbf{x})\nabla\tilde{\alpha}(\mathbf{x})}{[\alpha]}, \quad (1.39)$$

where $\tilde{\alpha}$ denotes a smoothed indicator function and $[\alpha]$ is its jump across the interface. The density correction factor $\rho/\langle\rho\rangle$, with $\langle\rho\rangle = (\rho_1 + \rho_2)/2$, does not modify the total magnitude of the applied force, but redistributes it preferentially toward the higher-density phase. In the VOF formulation, the indicator function is the volume fraction α , so that $\tilde{\alpha} = \alpha$ and $[\alpha] = 1$. Consequently, the capillary force is localized in the narrow transition region where $\nabla\alpha \neq 0$. This allows the pressure field to vary smoothly across the interface while retaining the effect of surface tension in the momentum balance. However, it should be emphasized that the CSF formulation requires an accurate evaluation of the local interface curvature κ , so the overall quality of the surface tension model depends strongly on the accuracy of the underlying interface reconstruction and curvature calculation[43].

Even though the CSF model is convenient, its implementation is numerically sensitive because it requires accurately computing quantities such as curvature κ and consistently discretizing the surface tension force on the grid. If this balance is not achieved, spurious velocities, also known as parasitic currents, may appear near the interface. These currents are purely numerical errors. These small unphysical velocities near the interface may lead to artificial interface deformation. In addition, they can increase momentum transport near the interface, thereby artificially enhancing the predicted heat transfer. Harvie et al. [26] showed that spurious currents do not necessarily vanish under mesh refinement unless a consistent discrete balance is achieved between the pressure-gradient term and the capillary-force term [43].

3.5.10 Curvature Model

As mentioned in the previous section, the computation of the surface tension force requires the curvature κ . In this work, the curvature is evaluated using the gradAlpha method, which is therefore briefly described in this section. The method is based on the Continuum Surface Force (CSF) formulation of Brackbill et al. [9]. It computes curvature directly from the volume fraction field. The procedure consists of two steps :

- First, the interface normal is obtained from the normalized gradient of the volume fraction field:

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}}_\alpha = \frac{\nabla\alpha}{|\nabla\alpha|}. \quad (3.23)$$

This expression gives the local interface orientation, because the gradient of α points in the direction of the steepest change across the interface.

- Second, these normals are interpolated from the cell centers to the cell faces, normalized again, and the curvature is evaluated as the divergence of the face-normal field:

$$\kappa = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \nabla \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_\alpha dV \approx \frac{1}{V} \sum_f \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\alpha,f} \cdot \mathbf{S}_f, \quad (3.24)$$

where V is the cell volume, the summation is performed over all faces of the cell, and \mathbf{S}_f denotes the outward face area vector.

However, its accuracy depends on how accurately the gradient of α is evaluated. Since α changes sharply across the interface, numerical gradients can be noisy, reducing the accuracy of curvature calculation and contributing to spurious currents. For this reason, the model's accuracy can be improved by using a suitable gradient reconstruction scheme for the volume-fraction field. This provides a more accurate estimate of $\nabla\alpha$, especially on unstructured or distorted meshes[68].

3.5.11 Phase Change Modeling

Thermal boundary condition at the vapor-liquid interface

One common approach in CFD models for evaporating flows is to impose a constant interfacial temperature equal to the saturation temperature. However, this assumption is not always valid. Hardt and Wondra argued that deviations of the interfacial temperature from the saturation temperature may become important, especially at small length scales. One of the simplest models accounting for such deviations is Tanasawa's model, in which the heat flux depends linearly on the excess temperature at the phase boundary. To illustrate this, they referred to the model

of Tanasawa, in which the evaporation heat flux is assumed to depend linearly on the excess interface temperature above saturation,

$$j_e^h = a_e (T_i - T_{sat}), \quad (3.25)$$

where j_e^h is the evaporation heat flux density, T_i is the temperature of the phase boundary, and T_{sat} is the saturation temperature. The evaporation heat-transfer coefficient is given by

$$a_e = \frac{2\nu_e}{2 - \nu_e} \frac{h_e^2 \rho_v}{\sqrt{2\pi R T_{sat}^{3/2}}}, \quad (3.26)$$

where ν_e is the evaporation coefficient, h_e is the enthalpy of evaporation, R is the gas constant for water, and ρ_v is the vapor density. To quantify the deviation of the interfacial temperature from the saturation temperature, a simple one-dimensional situation is considered in which a vapor–liquid interface is located at a distance d from a solid wall at constant temperature $T_0 > T_i$.

Using

$$j^h = j_e^h = k \frac{T_0 - T_i}{d}, \quad (3.27)$$

where j^h is the heat flux from the wall to the interface and k is the thermal conductivity, one obtains the dimensionless deviation of the interfacial temperature from the saturation temperature:

$$\frac{T_i - T_{sat}}{T_0 - T_{sat}} = \frac{1}{1 + a_e d / k}. \quad (3.28)$$

This relation shows that the deviation of the interfacial temperature from the saturation temperature increases with decreasing length scale d . This helps to conclude that at small length scales, the interface temperature can differ noticeably from saturation temperature, and this cannot be neglected[23].

The local phase equilibrium at the interface is affected by several additional physical effects; for example, curved interfaces create a Laplace pressure, which shifts the local phase equilibrium at the interface. Van der Waals forces between the wall and the liquid can also affect phase equilibrium and may lead to the formation of a thin adsorbed liquid film.

In the single-fluid formulation, interfacial effects are introduced into the governing equations as localized source terms. For phase-change problems, additional closure relations are therefore required to model the interfacial mass and heat transfer terms. Hence, a dedicated phase-change model is needed to describe \dot{m} , \dot{q} , and the corresponding interface-temperature condition[43]. The role of the phase change module is to provide the source terms required by the governing equations. It mainly comprises two parts: the energy source term model, and the second part is

the mass source term model[68].

The phase-change model serves as the basis for the evaporation and condensation treatment by computing the interfacial heat transfer associated with phase change. The resulting heat-transfer contribution is then used to define the corresponding source terms in the governing equations.

Schrage Model

The Schrage model is treated as an interface heat-resistance model. The difference between the local phase-change temperature and the saturation temperature at the interface drives the phase change [68]. The model assumes that the interface offers a finite thermal resistance, R_{int} , from which the heat transfer is computed. By dividing the temperature difference across the interface by this resistance, the interfacial heat flux is obtained. The phase-change heat flux is determined from the deviation of the local liquid and vapor temperatures from the saturation temperature. The total interfacial heat flux is written as

$$q_{pc} = q_{pc}^l + q_{pc}^v = \frac{T_l - T_{sat}}{R_{int}} + \frac{T_v - T_{sat}}{R_{int}}, \quad (3.29)$$

where T_l and T_v denote the liquid- and vapour-side temperatures, respectively. The interfacial resistance coefficient is given by

$$R_{int} = \frac{2 - C_{acc}}{2C_{acc}} \frac{T_{sat}^{3/2} \sqrt{2\pi R_{gas}}}{\rho_v L^2}, \quad (3.30)$$

where C_{acc} is the accommodation coefficient, R_{gas} is the specific gas constant, ρ_v is the vapour density, and L is the latent heat.

HardtWondra Model

The evaluation of the interfacial heat flux is the first step in the phase-change treatment considered in the present study. This heat flux is obtained from the energy source-term model, which is based on a linearized Schrage-type formulation. Phase change produces a discontinuity in the velocity field across the interface, since mass is removed from one phase and added to the other. In the numerical formulation, this effect is represented through a localized phase-change contribution in the governing equations.

If this contribution is imposed directly at the sharply defined interface, numerical difficulties may arise. In particular, strong local pressure and velocity oscillations can occur, potentially smearing or deforming the interface and reducing the robustness and physical reliability of the simulation.

The Hardt–Wondra model addresses this issue by regularizing the sharply localized phase-change contribution. Instead of applying it only at the interface, the contribution is distributed over a narrow region around the interface using a smoothing procedure.

The first step in the approach is to smooth the sharp mass source term by solving a Laplacian equation. The source term is spread over a finite number of cells in the vicinity of the interface, where smearing is controlled by a numerical diffusion coefficient based on local cell size. Laplacian smoothing preserves the total volume integral of the source term and is therefore conservative. The source terms inside the immediate interface region are set to zero in order to avoid any oscillations in pressure and velocity. However, this truncation violates the conservative nature of Laplace smoothing. Therefore, in the next step, the source terms of the liquid and gas parts are scaled in such a way that the volume integral matches the initial volume integral in the gas and liquid phases. Finally, the sign of the source term in the liquid region is reversed to account for mass loss from the liquid phase, while the vapor side retains the sign corresponding to mass gain. As a result, two source-term distributions of opposite sign are obtained on the two sides of the interface, and the overall integral of the mass source term remains zero[23].

The main advantage of the Hardt-Wondra model is that it is comparatively straightforward to implement and can be applied to arbitrary cell shapes. However, its accuracy depends on sufficiently fine resolution in the interfacial region. Nevertheless, the approach provides a practical and stable way of incorporating phase-change mass transfer into fixed-grid interface-capturing simulations[23].

3.6 Solver Framework

In the present scope of the thesis, two different OpenFOAM-based solvers were employed in the present work, namely `multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow` and `icoBoilingFoam`. The reason for using two solvers is that they address different levels of physical complexity and are therefore suited to different parts of the investigated two-phase flow problem.

The first solver considered in the present work is part of the TwoPhaseFlow Library [68], whose solver module structure is shown in Fig. 3.6. For the most general solver, `multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow`, the transport of the volume fraction field α is described by the following equation:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}\alpha) - \dot{\alpha}_{pc} = \alpha \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} + \alpha(1 - \alpha) \left(\frac{\psi_v}{\rho_v} - \frac{\psi_l}{\rho_l} \right) \frac{Dp}{Dt} \quad (3.31)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the velocity field, ψ is the compressibility. The terms on the right-hand side account for volumetric changes due to heating or compression and may be neglected in the incompressible

limit. In addition, the possibility of employing different interface advection methods, such as MULES or isoAdvector, is of particular relevance, since the numerical representation of the interface directly affects the sharpness of the phase boundary and, consequently, the prediction of phase-change processes[68].

Figure 3.6: multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow solver module structure.

Figure 3.7: icoBoilingFoam solver module structure.

The second solver employed in this work is icoBoilingFoam, which is based on the work of Municchi et al. on conjugate heat transfer effects during flow boiling in microchannels. The solver was developed for the simulation of boiling flows in OpenFOAM. Governing equations for incompressible two-phase flow with heat transfer and phase change are solved within the solver.

In this formulation, the evolution of the volume fraction field is coupled with the continuity, momentum, and energy equations in the fluid region.

In the present work, the discussion is limited to the solver components essential for interpreting the numerical results: the phase-change model, the available interface reconstruction schemes, and the surface-tension models.

4 Solver Validation: Growth of Vapor Bubbles in Superheated Liquids

This chapter presents the Scriven bubble growth case, which is used in the present work as a benchmark for validating the employed numerical solvers. In this case, analytical solutions are available for the temporal evolution of the bubble radius and the temperature field in the surrounding liquid.

Consequently, in this chapter, the theoretical problem is first defined together with the underlying assumptions. This is followed by a description of the computational domain, boundary conditions, and relevant solver settings. Finally, the numerical results obtained with the considered solvers are compared with the analytical reference solution, and the implications for solver validation are discussed.

4.1 Scriven Bubble Growth Case

The Scriven bubble-growth problem describes the expansion of a vapor bubble in a superheated liquid. When the vapor pressure inside the bubble exceeds the ambient pressure of the surrounding liquid, the bubble expands. This process is governed by the interaction of surface tension, liquid inertia, and the pressure difference across the liquid–vapor interface.

In the early stages of growth, due to resistance to deformation by the surface tension forces, the bubble expands slowly. Additionally, the resistance comes from the displaced liquid and the thermal energy required for the evaporation at the interface. For the bubble to expand, it needs evaporation at the liquid-vapor interface that requires latent heat. This energy is drawn from the liquid in the immediate vicinity of the interface, thereby decreasing the local temperature. As the vapor pressure depends on the interface temperature, the reduction in temperature reduces the vapor pressure inside the bubble. Bubble growth is eventually limited by the rate at which latent heat can be supplied to the bubble interface from the surrounding liquid. At later stages, the bubble growth enters an asymptotic regime in which the further expansion of the bubble is

controlled by the heat supply to the liquid-vapor interface. Analytical solutions for the bubble radius and the corresponding temperature distribution can be used as reference solutions for solver validation.

To obtain an analytical description of the problem, the following assumptions are made:

1. A spherical vapor bubble grows in a quiescent, superheated liquid of infinite extent.
2. The bubble is considered spherical throughout its growth.
3. Both the liquid and vapor phases are assumed to be effectively incompressible on the relevant time scale, and viscous effects are neglected.
4. The vapour density is small; hence, inertia effects inside the bubble are ignored, and the vapour pressure is considered uniform.
5. Temperature gradients within the vapor are assumed to be negligible due to the vapor density being small; hence, inertia effects inside the bubble are ignored, and the vapor's rapid thermal diffusion.
6. The temperature at the liquid–vapour interface is the saturation temperature [69, 56].

The analytical bubble radius is given by

$$R(t) = 2\beta\sqrt{a_l t}, \quad (4.1)$$

where R is the bubble radius, t is time, a_l is the thermal diffusivity of the liquid, and β is the dimensionless bubble-growth constant.

The growth constant β is related to the Jakob number Ja by

$$\beta = Ja\sqrt{\frac{3}{\pi}}. \quad (4.2)$$

The Jakob number is defined as

$$Ja = \frac{(T_\infty - T_{sat})\rho_l c_{p,l}}{\rho_v h_{lv}}, \quad (4.3)$$

where T_∞ is the far-field liquid temperature, $c_{p,l}$ is the liquid specific heat capacity, and h_{lv} is the latent heat of vaporization. Here, T_∞ is the bulk liquid temperature, T_{sat} is the saturation temperature, ρ_l and ρ_v are the liquid and vapour densities, respectively, $c_{p,l}$ is the specific heat capacity of the liquid at constant pressure, and h_{lv} is the latent heat of vaporization.

In addition, an analytical expression is available for the temperature field in the liquid surrounding

the growing bubble. It is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 T(r, t) = T_\infty - 2\beta^2 & \left(\frac{\rho_g [\Delta h_{ev} + (c_{pl} - c_{pg})(T_\infty - T_{sat})]}{\rho_l c_{pl}} \right) \\
 & \times \int_{1-R/r}^1 \exp \left(-\beta^2 \left[(1-x)^{-2} - 2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_l}{\rho_g} \right) x - 1 \right] \right) dx
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.4}$$

where $T(r, t)$ is the liquid temperature at radial position r and time t , and T_∞ is the bulk liquid temperature.

4.1.1 Computational Setup

A two-dimensional axisymmetric computational setup is used, based on the case provided by the authors of the TwoPhaseFlow framework [68, 68]. A schematic representation of the setup is shown in Fig. 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Schematic of the computational setup for the Scriven case.

The numerical simulation is initialized at a time t_0 at which a vapour bubble with radius $R = 50 \mu\text{m}$ is seeded. The liquid volume fraction is initialized as $\alpha_l = 0$ inside the bubble and $\alpha_l = 1$ in the surrounding liquid. This initialization corresponds to $t_0 = 3.3 \times 10^{-4}$ s.

The initial temperature field is not assumed to be spatially uniform. Instead, it is derived from the analytical temperature distribution at the initial time t_0 . The computational domain is discretized with a uniform 400×400 cell mesh, corresponding to a spatial resolution of $\Delta = 1.25 \mu\text{m}$. With the initial bubble radius $R_{b,0}$, this gives a resolution of $R_{b,0}/\Delta = 40$. The corresponding initial liquid volume-fraction field is shown in Fig. 4.2a.

Working fluid here is water and the thermophysical properties are summarized below in table Table 4.1.

Figure 4.2: Initial fields for the Scriven bubble growth validation case.

Table 4.1: Thermophysical properties of water

Property	Liquid phase	vapour phase
Density, ρ [kg m^{-3}]	958.4	0.585
Kinematic viscosity, ν [$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$]	2.922×10^{-7}	2.11×10^{-5}
Thermal conductivity, κ [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]	0.671	0.0203
Specific heat capacity, c_p [$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]	4216	2030
Saturation temperature, T_{sat} [K]	373.15	
Latent heat, h_{lv} [J kg^{-1}]	2.26×10^6	
Gas constant of vapour, R [$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]	461.5	

The initial and boundary conditions used for both validation cases are summarized in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Initial and boundary conditions for the Scriven benchmark case.

Field	Initial value	faceWall	outlet	front	back
T	mapped from T01.csv	symmetryPlane	zeroGradient	wedge	wedge
p_{rgh}	uniform 0	symmetryPlane	fixedValue (0)	wedge	wedge
\mathbf{U}	uniform (0,0,0)	symmetryPlane	zeroGradient	wedge	wedge
α_l	seeded bubble / liquid field	symmetryPlane	zeroGradient	wedge	wedge

The Scriven bubble growth validation case was simulated using water as the working fluid in both the liquid and vapour phases. In both solver setups, the surface tension coefficient was set to zero so that capillary effects were neglected and the bubble growth was governed mainly by thermal diffusion and phase change. The saturation temperature was set to $T_{sat} = 373.15$ K, the

latent heat to $h_f = 2.26 \times 10^6 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$, and the vapour gas constant to $R = 461.5 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. For the Schrage-based cases, the evaporation accommodation coefficient was set to $\sigma_{evap} = 0.1$. The temporal discretization was performed using the first-order Euler scheme. The phase-fraction convection term was discretized using a van Leer scheme together with interface compression. In both solvers, the interface advection was performed using `isoAdvection`, and the curvature evaluation was based on the `gradAlpha`. The simulations were advanced using adaptive time stepping with a prescribed maximum Courant number of $C_{o_{max}} = 0.2$ and an initial time-step size of $\Delta t = 1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$.

For the first set of simulations, `icoBoilingFoam` was used as the solver. In this case, the phase-change treatment was based on the Schrage-type formulation. The volume-fraction transport was solved with `isoAdvector` enabled, and the interface reconstruction and curvature evaluation were based on the `gradAlpha` approach. The main convective terms were discretized using bounded limited-linear schemes, while the phase-fraction equation used a van Leer scheme together with interface compression.

For the second set of simulations, the `multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow` solver was used for the same Scriven bubble growth validation case in order to compare its behaviour with `icoBoilingFoam`. In this solver, separate thermophysical descriptions were defined for the liquid and vapour regions. Three different phase-change formulations were investigated, namely the Schrage model, the `implicitGrad` model, and the `selectedGradExplicit` model. The gradient terms were evaluated using the `Gauss linear` scheme, while the laplacian and surface-normal gradient terms were treated using orthogonal schemes. The interface was reconstructed using the `gradAlpha`. The phase-change mass-transfer regularization was based on the Hardt–Wondra model.

Figure 4.3 shows the final temperature field together with the vapour bubble at its final radius.

4.1.2 Sensitivity to the Evaporation Coefficient

The purpose of the Scriven benchmark in the present work is not limited to a pure validation of the numerical implementation against the analytical solution. In addition, the case is used to assess the sensitivity of the employed solvers to the evaporation coefficient, which directly affects the interfacial mass-transfer rate in the phase-change model.

Figure 4.3: Final temperature field showing the vapour bubble at the final bubble radius.

Evaporation coefficient

One important parameter in the Schrage Model is the chi accommodation coefficient, or evaporation coefficient, which represents how efficiently molecules crossing the liquid-vapor interface participate in phase change. From a physical point of view, not every molecule emitted from the liquid necessarily enters the vapor phase. In the original formulation of the Schrage model distinguished between a condensation coefficient and an evaporation coefficient. χ represents the fraction of molecules at the liquid-vapor interface that effectively undergo phase change, while the remaining fraction is reflected. In many practical implementations, the evaporation and condensation coefficients are assumed equal, such that

$$\chi_e = \chi_c = \chi, \quad (4.5)$$

with

$$0 < \chi \leq 1. \quad (4.6)$$

A larger value of χ implies that the liquid-vapor interface is more efficient in transferring mass between the phases, which leads to a higher predicted evaporation or condensation rate. For this reason, the accommodation coefficient is one of the most influential parameters in Schrage phase-change models. At the same time, this coefficient is not well established in the literature, and reported values show considerable scatter. As an illustration, the review by Marek and Straub [46] highlights the large dispersion of experimental results reported for water. They

concluded that the accommodation coefficient lies between 0.1 and 1 for jets and moving films, but remains below 0.1 for stagnant liquid surfaces. For water evaporation, [13] recommended values in the range of 0.02 to 0.04, whereas Rose [65] suggested values close to unity for dropwise condensation. Wang et al. [79] reported a value of $\chi = 1$ for non-polar liquids. Hardt and Wondra [23] as well as Magnini et al. [43] also used $\chi = 1$ in film-boiling studies. For evaporating falling films, Kharangate et al. [35] recommended $\chi = 0.1$, while noting that values up to 1 may still provide acceptable predictive accuracy, although they may influence numerical stability. In the literature, $\chi = 0.5$ has been used; Kartuzova et al. proposed a much smaller value, $\chi = 0.01$, for turbulent phase change in a cryogenic storage tank. Huang et al. [28] used $\chi = 0.03$ for bubbly flow of R141b in a serpentine tube. These examples show that χ should not be regarded as a fixed constant, but rather as a model parameter whose appropriate value depends strongly on the physical system under consideration. Therefore, in the present study, the values $\chi = 0.1, 0.5$, and 1.0 were selected to investigate the sensitivity of the numerical predictions to the evaporation coefficient over a representative parameter range.

For this reason, simulations were carried out for different values of the evaporation coefficient in both `icoBoilingFoam` and `multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow`, and the resulting bubble radius evolution was compared with the analytical Scriven solution.

4.1.3 Results and Discussion

For `icoBoilingFoam`, six cases were evaluated to study the influence of the evaporation coefficient χ and the reconstruction scheme. In particular, the benchmark was repeated for $\chi = 1.0, 0.5$, and 0.1 using both `gradAlpha` and `plicRDF`. For the `multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow`, four additional cases were considered. These were used to compare the effect of the reconstruction scheme and different phase-change models, namely `implicitGrad`, `Schrage`, and `selectedExplicitGrad`, while keeping $\chi = 0.1$ fixed. In this way, the benchmark was used both as a validation case and as a comparative study of solver sensitivity to phase-change and interface-treatment settings.

The figures below show the Scriven bubble case studied using both solvers, `icoBoilingFoam` and the `multiregionphasechangeflow` solver. The phase change model used in both solvers was the `Schrage` model.

In the Scriven solution, bubble growth is governed primarily by heat diffusion in the surrounding liquid. In contrast, in the numerical phase-change models employed in the present work, the efficiency of interfacial mass transfer is accounted for by the evaporation coefficient γ . By varying the evaporation coefficient χ , the sensitivity of the numerical solution to interfacial

kinetics can be assessed. This also allows examination of whether the bubble-growth behavior approaches the thermally controlled analytical Scriven solution.

The results obtained with both solvers are shown in Fig. 4.4. Both solvers reproduce the general bubble-growth trend, but their sensitivity to the evaporation coefficient χ differs. For `icoBoilingFoam`, Fig. 4.4a shows that the predicted bubble growth deviates more noticeably from the Scriven solution as χ increases. Shown in Fig. 4.4b, this implementation shows closer agreement with the analytical solution and a weaker dependence on gamma, which suggests that this implementation better reproduces the thermally controlled growth regime assumed by Scriven.

Figure 4.4: Scriven bubble growth validation for a vapour bubble growing in a superheated liquid. The temporal evolution of the bubble radius predicted by (a) `icoBoilingFoam` and (b) `multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow` is compared with the analytical Scriven solution. The numerical results are shown for different values of the evaporation coefficient χ .

Both solvers use a regularization procedure based on the Hardt–Wondra approach to distribute the phase-change contribution over a narrow region around the interface and thereby reduce pressure oscillations and interface smearing. However, the solvers differ in the way the interfacial phase-change rate is evaluated before this regularization step. In `icoBoilingFoam`, the evaporation rate is introduced through a Schrage-type source-term formulation, in which the evaporation coefficient χ directly affects the mass transfer across the interface. This can make the predicted bubble growth more sensitive to the selected value of χ . In `multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow`, the Schrage model is implemented as an interfacial heat-resistance model. In this formulation, the phase-change heat flux is driven by the temperature difference between the local phase temperature and the saturation temperature. The corresponding source terms are treated implicitly in the discretized energy equation, which improves numerical stability.

A physically consistent benchmark response is not completely insensitive to χ , but rather has a weak sensitivity once χ becomes sufficiently large. In that regime, the interface is no longer the dominant resistance, and the bubble-growth rate should be governed mainly by liquid-side heat transfer, as assumed in Scriven's theory. Based on the Scriven benchmark, `multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow` is considered the more suitable solver for the subsequent investigations in this thesis. This choice is not intended as a universal ranking of solver accuracy for all boiling or phase-change problems; rather, it reflects the fact that, for the present thermally controlled benchmark, `multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow` provides closer agreement with the analytical solution.

The value $\chi = 0.1$ was chosen because it provides a conservative estimate of the evaporation coefficient and reduces the risk of overpredicting the interfacial mass flux. Since the Scriven problem is mainly heat-transfer controlled, the numerical solution should show only limited sensitivity to χ once the interfacial resistance is sufficiently small. Therefore, a physically consistent response is not complete independence from χ , but rather a weak sensitivity, with the solution tending toward the analytical Scriven curve as the interfacial resistance becomes less restrictive.

Figure 4.5 compares the different phase-change models available in `multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow`, while keeping the solver framework unchanged. The comparison includes the evolution of the bubble radius and the corresponding radial temperature profiles. For the temperature-profile comparison, the profiles were extracted at approximately the same bubble radius in order to avoid comparing temperature fields corresponding to different interface positions.

As shown in Fig. 4.5a, all three phase-change models reproduce the general diffusion-controlled bubble-growth trend. The Schrage model initially overpredicts the bubble radius, but its deviation decreases as the simulation progresses and it approaches the analytical Scriven solution at later times. In contrast, the `implicitGrad` and `explicitGrad` models show smaller deviations during the early stage, but increasingly underpredict the bubble radius at later times. The `implicitGrad` and `explicitGrad` models are gradient-based phase-change models, in which the evaporation rate is obtained from the temperature gradient near the interface. These models assume that the interface is at the saturation temperature and that heat is transported across it primarily by diffusion. However, the essential difference between these two models lies in the numerical treatment of this heat-flux contribution.

The radial temperature profiles provide additional insight into the local behaviour of the different phase-change models, as shown in Fig. 4.5b. For `explicitGrad`, the phase-change contribution is evaluated explicitly from the current temperature field. As a result, the model is more sensitive to local numerical errors near the interface, which is reflected by a sharper localized deviation in

Figure 4.5: Effect of different phase-change models on the Scriven bubble growth validation case using `multiRegionPhaseChangeFlow`. The bubble-radius evolution is compared with the analytical Scriven solution in (a), while the radial temperature profiles are compared in (b).

the temperature profile. In contrast, `implicitGrad` retains the same gradient-based physical idea, but treats the phase-change contribution implicitly in the discretized equation. This improves numerical stability and leads to a smoother temperature response near the interface. The Schrage model introduces phase change through an interfacial heat-resistance formulation. Therefore, it can reproduce the global bubble-radius evolution well, while still showing a different local temperature structure in the interfacial region. Thus, the bubble-radius plot mainly reflects the global accuracy of the predicted phase-change rate, whereas the temperature-profile comparison reveals local differences in how the phase-change models treat heat transfer and interfacial source terms.

From this it can be concluded `implicitGrad` is more accurate, followed by the Schrage model, which also agrees with [68]. The benchmark therefore mainly confirms that the gradient-based formulation is well suited for reproducing the assumptions of the Scriven problem. However, the intended application in the present work involves transient and non-equilibrium interfacial conditions, for which the Schrage model is considered more appropriate. For this reason, the Schrage model was selected for the subsequent simulations.

5 Pulsating Heat Pipe Validation Case

This chapter covers the validation setup for Pulsating Heat pipes. It details the creation of a 2D numerical model based on existing literature. The goal is to replicate the thermo-dynamical behavior of Pulsating Heat pipes, matching both qualitative and quantitative results from the reference case, thereby establishing a foundational setup for the final model. The chapter discusses the reference case, mesh generation, and the final validation results.

5.0.1 Reference Case and Computational Setup

The reference case was adapted from the work of Opalski et al. [54], who presented an OpenFOAM-based CFD model for pulsating heat pipes with phase change and coupled heat transfer between the fluid and solid domains. Their work provides a complete pathway from benchmark cases to a multi-turn pulsating heat pipe, validated against an original experiment. Therefore, it provides a clear basis for understanding the dynamic behavior of pulsating heat pipes. The final multi-turn PHP case, using ethanol as the working fluid, was investigated over a temperature range of 20–90 °C for filling ratios of 50%, 62.5%, and 75%. The model was validated using quantities such as pressure, temperature at selected measurement points, and thermal efficiency derived from the experimental data. The paper validated quantities such as pressure, temperature at selected measurement points, and thermal efficiency derived from the experimental data. The corresponding two-dimensional geometry is shown in Fig. 5.1.

An effort was made to reproduce the validation case using exclusively the information presented by Opalski et al. [54]. Where specific model details were not sufficiently described in the publication, these aspects were treated as limitations of reproducibility and are discussed in terms of their possible influence on the replication results.

Figure 5.1: Adapted 2D replicated geometry of the pulsating heat pipe used in the experiment from the work of Opalski et al. [54].

In the original study, the evaporator and condenser sections were made of copper. In contrast, the adiabatic section was fabricated from borosilicate glass, enabling the authors to investigate conjugate heat transfer and to compare the numerical model with experimental measurements of pressure, temperature, and thermal efficiency.

The authors investigated multiple combinations of filling ratios and heat flux values. However, in the present thesis, only one case is considered for reproduction, corresponding to a filling ratio of 50% with a heat flux of 10 kW/m^2 . The main operating parameters of the selected validation case are summarized in Table 5.1, while the thermophysical properties of ethanol used for this case are listed in Table 5.2.

The temperature-dependent density and viscosity correlations are given in Eqs. (5.1)–(5.4). The polynomial coefficients were obtained from saturation-property data generated using the CoolProp thermodynamic library [6].

Table 5.1: One of the case selected from paper as validation case for present work ($FR = 50\%$, $q = 10 \text{ kW/m}^2$).

Parameter	Unit	Value
Working fluid	–	Ethanol
Filling ratio	%	50
Heat flux	kW/m^2	10
Coolant temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	20
Total volume	ml	12.75

Table 5.2: Thermophysical properties of ethanol ($FR = 50\%$, $q = 10 \text{ kW/m}^2$).

Property	Unit	Value
$c_{p,l}$	$\text{J/kg}\cdot\text{K}$	2.8417×10^3
k_l	$\text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}$	1.5569×10^{-1}
$c_{p,v}$	$\text{J/kg}\cdot\text{K}$	1.6629×10^3
k_v	$\text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}$	1.9754×10^{-2}
h_{vap}	J/kg	8.6317×10^5

$$\rho_l = 1.3019 \times 10^3 T^0 - 3.5500 T^1 + 9.2794 \times 10^{-3} T^2 - 1.0685 \times 10^{-5} T^3, \quad (5.1)$$

$$\rho_v = -1.7043 \times 10^2 T^0 + 1.6726 T^1 - 5.5137 \times 10^{-3} T^2 + 6.1108 \times 10^{-6} T^3, \quad (5.2)$$

$$\mu_l = 4.2416 \times 10^{-2} T^0 - 3.2526 \times 10^{-4} T^1 + 8.5007 \times 10^{-7} T^2 - 7.5237 \times 10^{-10} T^3, \quad (5.3)$$

$$\mu_v = -2.7249 \times 10^{-6} T^0 + 4.9606 \times 10^{-8} T^1 - 4.8315 \times 10^{-11} T^2 + 3.7770 \times 10^{-14} T^3. \quad (5.4)$$

Boundary Conditions

Below is the summary of the Boundary conditions mentioned in the paper.

Table 5.3: Initial operating conditions.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Filling ratio	%	50
Heat flux	kW/m ²	10
p_{sat}	kPa	71.45
T_{sat}	K	342.97
T_{evap0}	K	327.9
p_0	kPa	38.23

Another simplification was introduced in the way the heat flux was applied at the evaporator wall. A conventional temperature-gradient boundary condition is not suitable for a multiphase domain, as it often assumes that heat transfer occurs only through the liquid phase. However, in a pulsating heat pipe, the computational cells adjacent to the heated wall may contain liquid, vapor, or a mixture of both phases.

To account for this, a modified heat-flux boundary condition was applied. In this approach, the wall temperature gradient is evaluated using the local phase volume fractions and the thermal conductivities of both the liquid and vapor phases. This allows heat to be supplied to the evaporator without imposing a fixed wall temperature, while providing a more appropriate representation of heat input in the two-phase region.

The corresponding expressions are given as follows:

$$-\nabla T = \frac{q}{\alpha_l k_l} \quad (3)$$

$$-\nabla T = \frac{q}{\alpha_v k_v} \quad (4)$$

$$-\nabla T = \frac{q}{\alpha_v k_v + \alpha_l k_l} \quad (5)$$

where α_l and α_v represent the liquid and vapor volume fractions, respectively, and k_l and k_v denote the thermal conductivities of the liquid and vapor phases, respectively. The boundary conditions were defined separately for each physical section of the pulsating heat pipe to account for the distinct thermal roles of the evaporator, condenser, and adiabatic regions. At the evaporator wall, a prescribed temperature condition was applied to represent the heat input

section of the pulsating heat pipe. The evaporator temperature was set to 347 K, which is approximately 5 K above the saturation temperature of the working fluid. This thermal condition provides the driving force for evaporation near the heated wall. A no-slip condition was applied at the solid surface, ensuring that the fluid velocity at the wall remained zero. The wetting behavior of the liquid phase was represented using a contact-angle condition with a static contact angle of 90°, corresponding to neutral wetting. The pressure boundary conditions were selected to maintain consistency with the wall fluxes and the incompressible two-phase flow formulation.

At the condenser wall, a fixed temperature of 293.15 K was imposed, corresponding to a cooling bath temperature of 20°C. This boundary represents the heat-rejection section of the PHP, where thermal energy is removed from the working fluid. As a result, vapor condensation can occur near the cooled wall. The same no-slip condition was applied at the condenser wall, and the same contact-angle treatment was used to describe the interaction between the liquid phase and the solid surface. The pressure conditions were kept consistent with those used at the evaporator wall.

The adiabatic wall sections represented the thermally insulated parts of the PHP connecting the evaporator and condenser regions. No heat transfer through these walls was allowed, so the temperature gradient normal to the walls was assumed to be zero. The velocity field was again subjected to a no-slip condition at the solid surface. Therefore, the adiabatic sections allowed only internal redistribution of heat, pressure, and phase motion within the channel, without any external heat addition or heat removal.

The front and back boundaries were treated as two-dimensional boundaries. This was done because the reproduced case was modeled as a two-dimensional domain. Consequently, gradients and fluxes in the out-of-plane direction were neglected, and the numerical solution was constrained to remain two-dimensional.

The initial temperature field was set uniformly to 327 K throughout the computational domain.

The initial multiphase distribution was prescribed through the liquid volume fraction field. The default condition was defined as liquid throughout the entire computational domain, with

$$\alpha_l = 1. \quad (5.5)$$

Vapour plugs were then imposed at selected positions within the PHP channel by assigning the liquid volume fraction to zero in these regions:

$$\alpha_l = 0. \quad (5.6)$$

The vapour volume fraction was consequently obtained from

$$\alpha_v = 1 - \alpha_l. \quad (5.7)$$

The imposed vapour regions were distributed in different sections of the PHP, including the vertical legs, bend regions, and header section. Geometrically, the vapour plugs were initialized using cylindrical regions with spherical end caps, which allowed elongated vapour pockets to be placed inside the liquid-filled channel. As a result, the initial condition consisted of a predefined liquid–vapour slug-plug arrangement rather than a single-phase liquid field. This prescribed multiphase distribution provided the initial interface locations from which the transient evaporation, condensation, pressure fluctuations, and oscillatory flow behaviour developed during the simulation.

The boundary conditions used for the reproduced PHP case are summarized in Table 5.4. The imposed conditions correspond to no-slip walls, prescribed thermal conditions at the evaporator and condenser, insulated adiabatic walls, and two-dimensional boundary conditions at the out-of-plane boundaries.

Table 5.4: Summary of boundary conditions used for the reproduced PHP case.

Boundary	T_{ethanol}	T_{vapour}	\mathbf{U}	α_{ethanol}	p	p_{rgh}
Evaporator wall	fixedValue	zeroGradient	noSlip	constantAlpha ContactAngle	zeroGradient	fixedFluxPressure
Condenser wall	fixedValue	fixedValue	noSlip	constantAlpha ContactAngle	zeroGradient	fixedFluxPressure
Adiabatic wall	zeroGradient	zeroGradient	noSlip	constantAlpha ContactAngle	zeroGradient	fixedFluxPressure
Front and back	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty	empty

Numerical Framework

The numerical model presented by Opalski et al. [54] was developed in C++ using the OpenFOAM v2106 platform, specifically employing the interFoam solver. The authors implemented the Lee phase-change model. This solver is an enhancement of the model previously established by Błasiak et al. [8]. However, in the present study, the solver choice is multiregionPhaseChangeFlow based on a previous study on the benchmark.

Opalski et al. [54] used the Galusinski–Vigneaux (GV) criterion to control the transient time step. This criterion is specifically related to the numerical treatment of two-phase flows dominated by interfaces. However, it is not available as a standard time-step control criterion in the OpenFOAM solver framework used in the present work. Its use would therefore require an additional custom

implementation and verification. Since the present validation step aims to establish a stable baseline reproduction of the reference case, the GV criterion was not implemented. Instead, the time step was controlled by the Courant number, the standard time-step control parameter in OpenFOAM for transient simulations.

The liquid–vapor interface was captured using the Volume of Fluid (VOF) method, in which the phase-fraction field is solved to represent the distribution of liquid and vapor within the computational domain. In the reference model, the phase-fraction equation was solved using the MULES algorithm together with an interface-compression term. This approach helps maintain the boundedness of the phase fraction and limits numerical diffusion of the interface. However, it does not provide the same geometrically sharp interface representation as geometric VOF methods.

In the present study, the fluid-domain governing framework, including the VOF formulation and MULES-based phase-fraction treatment, was retained. However, the Lee phase-change model was replaced by the Schrage model. The solid-domain heat transfer described in the reference paper was not included, and the numerical setup was kept as simple as possible.

5.1 Results and discussion

5.1.1 Outcome of Simulation

Multiple attempts were made to run the above validation case, but a rapid, unphysical pressure rise occurred at the start of the transient calculation. It was challenging to initiate pulsating heat pipe behavior, and the case could not be run in a stable, physically meaningful manner. Despite multiple attempts with alternative numerical settings, the simulation remained unstable. Therefore, the validation case was considered unsuccessful.

Below are the three reasons which could be the case why the simulation was unsuccessful

1. Pressure update sequence in the solver

To understand the origin of the pressure instability, the solver’s update sequence was examined. The initial focus of the analysis was to determine whether the local pressure and temperature fields were being updated appropriately, since the operation of a pulsating heat pipe depends strongly on the instantaneous local thermodynamic state.

To understand the possible origin of the pressure instability, the solver’s update sequence was examined. The main objective was to verify that the pressure and temperature fields

were updated in a consistent order, as the operation of a pulsating heat pipe is strongly influenced by the local thermodynamic state of the working fluid.

In the pressure equation, the pressure is not treated as a single global value. Instead, it is solved as a local field, with values updated in each computational cell. The pressure is reconstructed from the modified pressure field, which is also evaluated locally. Since the density is coupled to the pressure field, changes in pressure also affect the local density distribution. Therefore, attention was focused on the main fluid-region update sequence used at each transient time step.

The solver sequence shows that the fluid properties, surface-force terms, and saturation properties are updated before the pressure-correction step is completed. The momentum and temperature equations are also solved before the phase-change source terms are corrected. This indicates that the pressure field is updated during the solution procedure, but the phase-change model may use pressure and saturation information from an earlier stage of the same iteration. The final pressure correction is applied only afterward to enforce pressure-velocity consistency.

Therefore, the instability is not necessarily caused by the absence of a pressure update. Rather, it may be related to the order in which pressure, temperature, saturation properties, and phase-change source terms are evaluated within each time step. In a pulsating heat pipe, even small local pressure variations can significantly affect the saturation temperature and the resulting evaporation or condensation rate. If the phase-change model uses pressure information that is not fully consistent with the final corrected pressure field, this can introduce numerical sensitivity and contribute to pressure oscillations or instability during the transient simulation.

Figure 5.2: Detailed update sequence of the fluid region of the solver. Own interpretation and representation.

2. Closed-volume correction

Even though the pressure field is solved locally in each computational cell, an additional correction is applied when the domain is treated as a closed compressible volume. This correction is used to maintain overall mass conservation in the closed system. After the local pressure solution, a uniform pressure adjustment is applied across the domain to maintain the total mass consistent with the system's initial mass.

This step is important because small local pressure and density changes can accumulate during the transient calculation. In a closed domain, there is no inlet or outlet through which mass can enter or leave the system. Therefore, the solver must ensure that the integrated mass of the computational domain remains conserved. The closed-volume correction acts as a global adjustment that restores this consistency after the local pressure field has been updated.

3. Phase-change source-term pathway to the pressure equation

Examination of the solver formulation showed that the phase-change source term is strongly

coupled with the pressure equation. During the solution procedure, the energy associated with evaporation and condensation is converted into a mass source term, which is then distributed near the liquid-vapor interface. This final source term enters the pressure equation and directly affects the local pressure response.

Therefore, large or rapidly varying phase-change rates can produce strong local pressure changes, especially during the initial stage of the simulation when the thermal and phase fields are still adjusting. This behavior provides one possible explanation for the rapid and unphysical pressure increase observed in the validation case.

Figure 5.3: Phase-change source-term pathway leading to the pressure equation.

Alongside the way the phase-change source term interacts with the pressure equation, there are likely other reasons for the pressure instability we saw. One key reason is the use of polynomial equations to describe how the fluid's properties change with temperature and pressure. These polynomial fits can become numerically sensitive, especially when the local temperature or pressure varies rapidly or approaches the limits of the fitted range. When that happens, things like density, latent heat, or heat capacity can suddenly jump, which makes the pressure swing even more and makes the simulation less stable.

Although these reasons could not be isolated independently in the present study, the code structure indicates that they are plausible contributors to the observed pressure instability. Their combined effect is considered sufficient to explain why the validation case failed to

produce a stable and physically meaningful solution.

6 Numerical Investigation of Bubble Growth in Straight and Wavy Mini-channels

6.1 Objective of the Analysis

As discussed in the previous chapter, the validation study for the PHP did not yield a satisfactory simulation outcome. However, the main objective of the present research remains unchanged: to understand how a wavy geometry in the heated or evaporator region affects the flow's thermal-hydrodynamic behavior. In particular, the interest lies in how the geometric waviness influences bubble growth, liquid film thickness around the bubble, and the associated heat transfer characteristics.

To retain this objective while avoiding the numerical difficulties encountered in the full PHP configuration, the problem is reformulated as a simplified single mini-channel model. The selected mini-channel preserves the main geometric characteristics of the original PHP channel while replacing the closed oscillatory system with an open-flow configuration. This simplification allows for more clearly isolating the influence of the wavy heated section while also reducing the numerical complications associated with closed-domain simulations.

Studies have established that the slug flow regime (elongated bubble), due to its efficient heat transfer, is an optimal operating condition for micro heat exchangers. Bubbles in slug flow regimes are characterized by a thin liquid film between the bubble and the channel walls; the film's thickness controls the heat transfer mechanism. Slug flow has been studied extensively in straight mini-micro channels experimentally and numerically; however, in wavy geometry channels, experimental studies are limited. In that sense, numerical simulations can be useful for understanding local film thickness profiles and the heat transfer mechanism, which are not readily accessible in experimental setups[17][53]. Hence, in the present work, a single bubble, representative of the slug flow regime, is initialized in the wavy minichannel, and a numerical study is performed. The present chapter, therefore, focuses on a numerical investigation of bubble growth in a straight and wavy mini-channel, where the wavy section represents the heated

evaporator-like region of interest.

The chapter has three main aims. Firstly, the numerical model is assessed through a mesh sensitivity study to determine an appropriate computational resolution. Second, a parametric study is carried out to examine the effects of heat input and geometric parameters. Secondly, the heat flux, channel width, and waviness amplitude are varied systematically, and the resulting behavior is compared with that of a straight channel. Through this approach, the chapter seeks to provide physical insight into how wavy channel geometry modifies two-phase flow behavior and thermal performance.

6.2 Overview of Numerical Method

In the present study, the open-source CFD platform OpenFOAM is used to perform the flow-boiling simulations with the `icoBoilingFoam` solver. Since the detailed mathematical formulation and physical modeling have already been presented in Chapter 3, only this brief summary is included here to provide the numerical context for the case analysis and comparison. The numerical model is based on an incompressible two-phase volume-of-fluid (VOF) formulation. The interfacial mass transfer associated with evaporation and condensation is described using the Schrage phase-change model. In the present study, this force is modeled using Brackbill's continuum surface force (CSF) approach.

6.3 Problem Definition

The computational domain considered in the present study is a wavy mini-channel constructed by extruding a two-dimensional sinusoidal channel profile in the spanwise direction. The channel has a total length of 46 mm, consisting of a 10 mm straight inlet adiabatic section used to allow the bubble to attain a steady-state motion, a 26 mm-long wavy middle section as a heated or evaporator region, and a 10 mm straight outlet section, again an adiabatic section.

The upper and lower channel walls in the two-dimensional generating plane are defined as

$$y_{\text{lower}}(x) = -\frac{w}{2} + AW(x) \sin \left[\frac{2\pi(x - x_{\text{start}})}{\lambda} + \phi \right],$$

$$y_{\text{upper}}(x) = +\frac{w}{2} + AW(x) \sin \left[\frac{2\pi(x - x_{\text{start}})}{\lambda} + \phi \right],$$

where w is the channel width, $\lambda = 4$ mm is the wavelength, A is the wave amplitude, ϕ is the

Figure 6.1: Schematic of Wavy geometry used in the present work. The schematic is not to scale.

phase angle, and $x_{\text{start}} = 10$ mm denotes the beginning of the wavy section. The sinusoidal wall definition and waviness parametrization adopted in the present study follow the geometric formulation reported by Odumosu et al. [53]. According to the present geometric definition, the characteristic hydraulic diameter is taken in general form as

$$D_h = 2w.$$

which is consistent throughout the analysis.

A vapor bubble is initialized near the inlet of the mini-channel as a capsule-shaped region, consisting of a cylindrical core with spherical caps at both ends. The initial bubble dimensions are defined using a fixed reference length, $L_{\text{ref}} = 1.00$ mm, instead of the hydraulic diameter, since the hydraulic diameter changes with the channel width. The initial bubble radius is kept fixed at $R_{b,0} = 0.585$ mm for all channel-width variations. Accordingly, using the fixed reference length $L_{\text{ref}} = 1.00$ mm, the 10 mm straight inlet and outlet sections correspond to $10L_{\text{ref}}$ each, while the 26 mm wavy heated section corresponds to $26L_{\text{ref}}$. The total channel length of 46 mm therefore corresponds to $46L_{\text{ref}}$.

6.3.1 Boundary Conditions

Throughout the study, the inlet condition is prescribed in dimensionless form by fixing the liquid Reynolds number as given in Eq. (6.1):

$$Re_l = \frac{\rho_l u_{in} D_h}{\mu_l}, \quad (6.1)$$

Using the same liquid properties, the corresponding liquid Capillary number is defined as

$$Ca_l = \frac{\mu_l u_{in}}{\sigma}, \quad (6.2)$$

where σ is the surface tension coefficient.

For the range of channel geometries considered in the present study, the resulting Capillary numbers remain small. Therefore, surface tension is expected to play an important role in the interfacial deformation, while inertia still contributes to bubble transport and elongation through the imposed Reynolds number. Since bubble dynamics in mini- and microchannels are commonly characterized using dimensionless groups such as Re and Ca , this formulation provides a consistent basis for comparing the investigated cases.

At the heated wall, a fixed-temperature gradient boundary condition is imposed, equivalent to a constant wall heat flux according to Fourier's law. The straight inlet and outlet wall sections are treated as adiabatic. The liquid used in the present study is acetone, with its thermophysical properties summarized in Table 6.2. The phase fraction is defined such that $\alpha_l = 1$ in the liquid region and $\alpha_l = 0$ in the vapor region. Accordingly, the initially imposed bubble is represented by $\alpha_l = 0$, while the surrounding liquid is initialized with $\alpha_l = 1$. A summary of the boundary conditions held constant throughout the case analysis is given in Table 6.1, while the thermophysical properties of acetone at saturation conditions used in the simulations are listed in Table 6.2.

Table 6.1: Summary of boundary conditions used throughout the study.

Boundary	Temperature, T	Velocity, U	Pressure, p / p_{rgh}	Phase fraction, α_l
Inlet	Fixed value	Fixed value	Zero gradient	Fixed value ($\alpha_l = 1$)
Outlet	Zero gradient	Outlet / zero gradient	Fixed value (reference)	Outlet / zero gradient
adiabatic1	Zero gradient	No-slip wall	Zero gradient	Zero gradient
heatedWall	Fixed gradient (constant heat flux)	No-slip wall	Zero gradient	Zero gradient
adiabatic2	Zero gradient	No-slip wall	Zero gradient	Zero gradient
front	empty	empty	empty	empty
back	empty	empty	empty	empty

Table 6.2: Thermophysical properties of acetone at saturation conditions.

Symbol	Liquid	Vapor
T_{sat}	329.22 K	
P_{sat}	0.10130 MPa	
ρ	748.96 kg m ⁻³	2.2673 kg m ⁻³
c_v	1.6054 kJ kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	1.3547 kJ kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
c_p	2.2293 kJ kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	1.5673 kJ kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
k	142.65 mW m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	16.750 mW m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
μ	233.11 μ Pa s	8.8497 μ Pa s
ν	0.0031125 cm ² s ⁻¹	0.039032 cm ² s ⁻¹
Pr	3.6431	0.82803
h_{lv}	501.43 kJ kg ⁻¹	
σ	18.857 mN m ⁻¹	

6.4 Mesh Sensitivity Study

Local heat transfer measurements combined with flow visualization are important for understanding the dominant mechanisms of flow boiling in mini- and microchannels. However, there is still no general agreement on the dominant heat-transfer mechanism in microchannel flow boiling [33]. Thome and Consolini [76] described the heat-transfer process according to the flow regime, including liquid-film evaporation and convection in liquid slugs during slug flow. They also emphasized that a dependence of the heat-transfer coefficient solely on heat flux is not sufficient to confirm nucleate boiling dominance, since thin-film evaporation and bubble frequency can also be influenced by heat flux. Hence, resolving the vapour bubble, the liquid film, and the interface between the bubble and the liquid film is of central importance.

A particular difficulty arises from the difference in length scales. The elongated vapour bubble is typically of millimetre scale, whereas the liquid film between the bubble and the wall can be only a few micrometres thick. Consequently, a mesh that appears sufficiently fine to represent the overall bubble motion may still be too coarse to resolve the near-wall liquid film. This limitation has been reported in previous numerical studies. Qian et al. [59] used Fluent to model Taylor bubble formation in a T-junction microchannel for a two-dimensional planar geometry with a cross-sectional width ranging from 0.25 to 3 mm, and stated that the grid resolution was not fine enough to capture the liquid film. Kashid et al. [34] studied liquid-liquid slug flow experimentally

using micro-PIV and numerically using interface-capturing CFD techniques, and reported that the wall film was not captured even though the mesh was fine.

For this reason, a mesh-independence study is necessary in the present work to ensure that the numerical grid is sufficiently fine to resolve the interfacial structure and near-wall liquid film, while maintaining an acceptable computational cost [22, 53]. Following the approach adopted by Gupta et al. [22], the near-wall mesh requirement may be estimated using Bretherton’s liquid-film thickness correlation, with a recommendation of at least five computational cells across the film thickness.

The computational domain is discretized using a structured, body-fitted hexahedral mesh, as shown in Fig. 6.2, generated with a custom Python-based mesh-generation code rather than the standard `blockMesh` utility in OpenFOAM. In this approach, the channel geometry is first constructed in two dimensions, and the geometry and mesh points were generated using a Python script, which provided a practical way to define the wavy wall shape before converting the mesh for use in OpenFOAM, as it was easier to implement than defining the complete sinusoidal geometry directly in `blockMesh`. After generating the base mesh, additional near-wall refinement was applied using the OpenFOAM `refineMesh` utility to increase resolution near the wall and improve representation of the thin liquid film surrounding the vapor bubble.

Below is the summary table for the mesh resolutions. Here, Δx denotes the cell size in the streamwise direction, and Δy_{wall} denotes the wall-adjacent cell height in the final refined mesh.

Table 6.3: Summary of mesh resolutions used in the mesh study. Here, Δx denotes the cell size in the streamwise direction and Δy_{wall} denotes the wall-adjacent cell height in the final refined mesh.

Mesh	Aspect Ratio	$D_h/\Delta x$	Δy_{wall} (m)
Coarser	63.78	274	2.69×10^{-7}
Medium	63.88	411	1.34×10^{-7}
Fine	63.99	866	6.39×10^{-8}

6.4.1 Results and Discussion

To assess mesh dependence, results obtained with the coarse, medium, and fine meshes are compared under the same operating conditions in the wavy channel. The comparison focuses on the main quantities of interest in the present study, the mesh’s ability to capture the liquid film thickness. Since these features depend strongly on the resolution of the near-wall liquid film and interfacial region, the variation of the numerical results with mesh refinement provides a direct

(a) Overall structured mesh for the wavy channel.

(b) Structured mesh near the upper wall of the wavy channel, with an inset showing the boundary-layer refinement.

Figure 6.2: Structured mesh for the wavy channel: (a) overall mesh with the selected region highlighted and (b) near-wall mesh refinement corresponding to the highlighted region in (a), shown with a zoomed inset.

indication of whether the adopted grid is sufficiently resolved.

The bubble enters the heated wavy channel region at time $t=0.1s$ and hence starts the evaporation process, which leads to bubble growth. Figure 6.3 compares the predictions obtained using the coarse, medium, and fine meshes in terms of the normalized bubble volume, V_b/V_{b0} , and the dimensionless bubble volume growth rate, $d(V_b/V_{b0})/d(t/T_{ref})$, where V_b is the instantaneous bubble volume, V_{b0} is the initial bubble volume, and T_{ref} is the reference time scale defined as $T_{ref} = D_h^2/(Re \nu_l)$. These two quantities are selected because they directly reflect the sensitivity of the predicted interfacial dynamics to mesh resolution, particularly in the near-wall region where the thin liquid film develops. Figure 6.3a shows dimensionless bubble volume growth rate with dimensionless time, while Fig. 6.3b presents normalized bubble volume ratio against time.

From Fig. 6.3, it can be inferred that the coarse mesh consistently predicts faster bubble growth and larger bubble volume, indicating that it is not sufficiently resolved for the present flow-boiling problem in the wavy minichannel.

The grid convergence analysis of Magnini et al. [45] highlights that mesh resolution becomes particularly critical once evaporation begins. In the heated region, the wall heat flux generates a superheated thermal boundary layer, and evaporation starts when the vapor-liquid interface reaches this region. Since the interface remains close to saturation temperature, large temperature gradients occur across the thin liquid film between the bubble and the heated wall. If the liquid film is not sufficiently resolved, these gradients are inaccurately discretized, causing an overprediction of the evaporation rate and faster bubble growth, which can be seen in Fig. 6.3. Therefore, resolving the liquid film and the near-wall thermal boundary layer is essential for reliable flow-boiling simulations. This overall trend agrees qualitatively with the findings of Magnini et al.[45] for elongated bubble motion with evaporation in a horizontal straight channel of circular cross-section, where an insufficient mesh resolution within the liquid-film region led to faster bubble growth because of inaccuracies. However, they were able to achieve mesh independence by later refining, and the same can be seen in a study done by Odumosu et al[53].

Therefore, further two refined meshes with $D_h/\Delta x = 411$ and $D_h/\Delta x = 866$ were considered. The mesh-dependency analysis based on V_b/V_{b0} was quantified using the mean signed percentage difference between successive mesh levels. The mean signed difference decreased from 6.03% for the coarse-medium comparison to 1.48% for the medium-fine comparison. This reduction indicates that the average deviation between successive mesh levels decreases with mesh refinement. Since the medium-fine difference is relatively small on average, the medium mesh can be considered a reasonable computational compromise, while the fine mesh remains the most reliable among the tested meshes.

But, strict mesh independence has not been achieved, and further mesh refinement from $D_h/\Delta x = 866$ is needed. This would result in an unrealistic jump in cell aspect ratio, particularly near the curved wall regions of the wavy minichannel, which, in turn, would lead to failure to resolve the vapor bubble and liquid interface. In addition, the smaller cell size imposed a more restrictive time-step requirement under the CFL condition, resulting in a substantial increase in computational cost. Since a clear convergence trend is not yet achieved from the global quantities alone, the liquid-film thickness is examined further to assess whether the near-wall interfacial region is sufficiently resolved[53].

Figure 6.3: Mesh-sensitivity comparison based on the dimensionless bubble volume growth rate and normalized bubble volume evolution. Here, V_b is the instantaneous bubble volume, V_{b0} is the initial bubble volume, and T_{ref} is the reference time calculated using the Reynolds number and used to normalize the simulation time.

Figure 6.6 compares the dimensionless liquid-film-thickness profiles near the bubble nose for the coarse, medium, and fine meshes at three representative time instants. The film thickness is expressed as δ/D_h , where δ denotes the local distance between the bubble interface and the channel wall, and is plotted against the dimensionless axial coordinate $(x - x_N)/D_h$, where x_N is the bubble nose position as shown in Fig. 6.4. Only the upper film region in the vicinity of the bubble nose is considered, so that the influence of mesh refinement on the resolution of the thin liquid film in the wavy channel can be examined more directly.

Figure 6.4: Schematic representation of the local liquid film thickness δ near the bubble nose in the upper film region of the wavy channel.

The selected time instants correspond to different stages of bubble motion through the channel: at $t = 0.11$ s the bubble is located in the entrance region, at $t = 0.14$ s it is in the middle of the heated wavy section, and at $t = 0.17$ s it is near the end of the channel, as shown in the Fig. 6.5

Figure 6.5: Temporal evolution of the bubble inside the wavy minichannel, showing the bubble position and deformation at selected time instants: (a) $t = 0.1$ s, (b) $t = 0.14$ s, and (c) $t = 0.17$ s.

Compared with global quantities such as bubble growth rate or bubble volume, this representation provides a more localized assessment of mesh sensitivity in the interfacial near-wall region.

Figure 6.6: Comparison of the dimensionless liquid-film-thickness profiles near the bubble nose for the coarse, medium, and fine meshes at three representative time instants: $t = 0.11$ s in the entrance region, $t = 0.14$ s in the middle of the heated wavy section, and $t = 0.16$ s near the wavy section exit.

Figure 6.6 compares the dimensionless liquid-film-thickness distribution near the bubble nose for the coarse, medium, and fine meshes at three representative time instants. The results show

that the predicted film-thickness profiles differ noticeably among the three mesh levels at all times considered. In particular, both the profile shape and its axial variation with $(x - x_N)/D_h$ remain sensitive to mesh refinement. The coarse mesh exhibits the largest deviation, especially in the steep increase of film thickness toward the bubble nose and in the overall profile shape. The medium and fine meshes show closer agreement than the coarse mesh, but they still do not collapse onto a single curve, indicating that the detailed liquid-film distribution near the bubble nose is not yet fully mesh independent. These results indicate that the detailed liquid-film profile near the bubble nose remains dependent on mesh resolution. However, compared with the coarse mesh, the medium mesh provides a more consistent representation of the overall film-thickness variation.

Figure 6.7 shows that the minimum dimensionless liquid-film thickness remains within a narrow range for all three mesh levels, indicating that this quantity is only weakly affected by mesh refinement. The medium and fine meshes yield very similar values across the considered bubble positions, whereas the coarse mesh shows a noticeable increase at the farthest downstream location. This suggests that the coarse mesh becomes less reliable as the bubble advances through the channel, while the medium and fine meshes provide a more consistent prediction of the minimum film-thickness scale.

Figure 6.7: Variation of the minimum liquid-film thickness with bubble position for the coarse, medium, and fine meshes.

A comparison between the medium and fine meshes further shows that the deviation in the minimum dimensionless film thickness decreases along the selected bubble positions, reducing from approximately 0.40% to 0.33% and finally to 0.19%. This indicates that the characteristic

minimum film-thickness scale predicted by the medium mesh remains very close to that of the fine mesh. Although the fine mesh provides the highest spatial resolution, its computational cost is significantly higher. In the present simulations, the coarse, medium, and fine meshes required approximately 1, 2, and 3 days of computation, respectively. Therefore, considering the small deviation between the medium and fine meshes and the substantially higher cost of the fine mesh, the medium mesh is selected for the subsequent simulations as a suitable compromise between accuracy and computational efficiency. Hence, although some mesh sensitivity may remain in the detailed local film profile, the minimum film thickness is already reasonably well captured by the medium mesh.

6.5 Parametric study

6.5.1 Influence of Heat Flux

To isolate the effect of heat flux on flow boiling in the sinusoidal wavy minichannel, a heat-flux sensitivity study was conducted while keeping the channel geometry fixed. The channel width, waviness amplitude, and waviness ratio were maintained at $w = 1.33$ mm, $A = 0.32$ mm, and $\gamma = 0.08$, respectively, while the applied heat flux was varied as $q'' = 5, 7.5, \text{ and } 10$ kW/m². This section examines how increased heat flux influences bubble growth, interface development, and local heat transfer within the heated wavy region.

A bubble grows when it enters the heated wavy section of the microchannel, where a constant heat flux is imposed, as shown in the Fig. 6.8.

Figure 6.9a shows the normalized bubble volume, $V_b/V_{b,0}$, as a function of the normalized streamwise bubble-center position, x_c/D_h . Thus, the bubble volume is reported relative to the instantaneous streamwise position of the bubble center as it moves through the heated wavy region. As the bubble travels downstream through the heated, wavy section, its volume increases due to evaporation. The growth rate becomes stronger with increasing imposed heat flux, indicating that higher heat input promotes faster vapor generation and bubble expansion. Figure 6.9b presents the normalized bubble nose velocity using U_{ref} calculated using Re , U_b/U_{ref} on the y-axis against the normalized bubble center position on the x-axis, x_c/D_h .

The combined behavior shown in Fig. 6.9a and Fig. 6.9b indicates that increasing the heat flux enhances bubble growth. The bubble enters the heated wavy region at approximately $t = 0.1$ s and reaches the middle of the wavy channel at $t = 0.14$ s, as depicted in Fig. 6.5. With increasing heat flux, the evaporation rate increases, leading to faster bubble growth and larger bubble

Figure 6.8: Temperature distribution and vapor-bubble growth in the wavy minichannel at $t = 0.14 \text{ s}$ for different imposed wall heat fluxes: (a) $q = 5 \text{ kW m}^{-2}$, (b) $q = 7.5 \text{ kW m}^{-2}$, and (c) $q = 10 \text{ kW m}^{-2}$.

volumes. This effect also generally increases with heat flux, with the highest velocities observed for $q = 10 \text{ kW/m}^2$. However, the velocity does not increase smoothly along the channel; instead, it exhibits pronounced spatial fluctuations as the bubble travels through the wavy section.

These oscillations can be attributed to the geometric confinement imposed by the sinusoidal channel. As the bubble elongates at higher heat flux, it occupies a larger portion of the wavy section, and its motion becomes increasingly affected by local curvature, variations in cross-sectional confinement, and deformation of the vapor-liquid interface. Similar effects of wavy geometry on elongated vapor-bubble growth, deformation, and heat transfer were reported by Odumosu et al. [53]. Therefore, the behavior observed in Fig. 6.9a can be interpreted as the combined effect of enhanced vapor generation, which increases the mean bubble velocity, and geometry-induced confinement, which produces local accelerations and decelerations within the wavy minichannel. Therefore, the behavior observed in Fig. 6.9b can be interpreted as the result of a competition between enhanced vapor generation at higher heat flux and the resistance imposed by the wavy confined geometry.

The heat-transfer performance at the microchannel wall is characterized by the Nusselt number, defined previously in Eq. (2.9). The local heat-transfer coefficient is calculated as

$$h = \frac{q}{T_w - T_{\text{sat}}}, \quad (6.3)$$

where q is the applied wall heat flux, T_w is the wall temperature obtained from the simulations, and T_{sat} is the saturation temperature.

For the dimensionless analysis of bubble motion, the bubble nose velocity and time are normalized using the reference velocity and reference time, respectively. The reference velocity is obtained from the Reynolds-number definition as

$$U_{\text{ref}} = \frac{Re_{\text{ref}} \mu_l}{\rho_l D_h}, \quad (6.4)$$

where $Re_{\text{ref}} = 1000$, μ_l is the liquid dynamic viscosity, ρ_l is the liquid density, and D_h is the hydraulic diameter. The corresponding reference time is defined as

$$t_{\text{ref}} = \frac{D_h}{U_{\text{ref}}}. \quad (6.5)$$

These reference quantities are used to present the dimensionless bubble nose velocity, $U_{\text{nose}}/U_{\text{ref}}$, and dimensionless time, t/t_{ref} , in the subsequent analysis. The local Nusselt number and dimensionless wall superheat shown in Fig. 6.11a and Fig. 6.11b are evaluated at a fixed wall location corresponding to the middle of the heated section of the wavy microchannel. This

fixed-point evaluation captures the transient heat-transfer response due to the passage of the bubble. Plotting these quantities against the instantaneous bubble center position, x_c/D_h , allows the local heat-transfer enhancement mechanism associated with the moving vapor-liquid interface to be examined.

Figure 6.10: Schematic representation of the fixed wall-probe location used for evaluating the local Nusselt number and wall superheat in the wavy minichannel. The dashed vertical line indicates the probe position at the middle of the heated wavy section, while the bubble moves through the channel from left to right.

Figure 6.11a shows the variation of the local Nusselt number at the midpoint of the heated section for different heat flux values, namely $q = 5$, $q = 7.5$, and $q = 10$. Initially, the local Nusselt number is high and then decreases rapidly. After this initial decay, fluctuations appear as the bubble passes through the heated region. It is also observed that the fluctuations become stronger as the heat flux increases. Figure 6.11b shows the corresponding variation of the dimensionless wall superheat, ΔT , at the same location for the same heat flux cases. The wall superheat also changes with bubble passage and reflects the wall's local thermal response to evolving bubble dynamics.

Figure 6.11 shows the variation of the local Nusselt number and the dimensionless wall superheat at the midpoint of the heated section for different heat flux values, namely $q = 5 \text{ kW/m}^2$, $q = 7.5 \text{ kW/m}^2$, and $q = 10 \text{ kW/m}^2$. Initially, the local Nusselt number is high and then decreases rapidly. After this initial decay, fluctuations appear as the bubble passes through the heated region. The corresponding variation of the dimensionless wall superheat, ΔT , at the same location also changes with bubble passage and reflects the wall's local thermal response to evolving bubble dynamics.

These results indicate that the passage of the bubble significantly influences the local heat transfer at the midpoint of the heated wall. As heat flux increases, the bubble grows larger and interacts more strongly with the wall. Increasing bubble size enlarges the interaction area between the bubble and the heated wall, thereby enhancing heat transfer from the wall through the liquid film to the liquid-vapor interface. This intensified heat transfer promotes evaporation and accelerates bubble growth. As a result, the passing bubble induces a stronger local thermal disturbance, which appears as larger fluctuations in both the local Nusselt number and the wall superheat at higher heat fluxes. The local increase in Nusselt number for the $q=7.5$ case is associated with a

Figure 6.11: Comparison of the local Nusselt number and dimensionless wall superheat at the fixed midpoint of the heated section for $q = 5$, $q = 7.5$, and $q = 10$.

local decrease in wall superheat at the midpoint probe. Since the Nusselt number is inversely related to wall superheat at a given heat flux, this results in a temporary rise in Nu. Such a decrease in wall superheat is not observed in the corresponding $q=5$ and $q=10$ cases, which explains why a similar jump does not appear there. This behaviour can be seen in Fig. 6.11a and Fig. 6.11b.

For the $q = 7.5$ kW/m² case, the temporary jump in the local Nusselt number occurs when the bubble has elongated to a position where its nose and liquid region ahead of it interact strongly with the local crest trough geometry of the wavy channel, as shown in Fig. 6.12. At this instant, the wavy geometry promotes local recirculation and secondary flow structures ahead of the bubble. These flow structures can sweep relatively cooler liquid toward the heated wall and disturb the hot near-wall thermal layer. As a result, the local wall temperature decreases temporarily, producing the observed dip in wall superheat and the corresponding rise in the local Nusselt number.

A similar liquid-push effect is not observed for the $q = 5$ kW/m² and $q = 10$ kW/m² cases at the same probe location. This is likely because, at the corresponding instants, the bubble length and position relative to the crest and trough do not produce the same local recirculation-driven liquid renewal near the wall. Consequently, the wall superheat does not exhibit a comparable temporary drop, and no similar jump in the local Nusselt number is observed for these heat-flux cases.

Because local heat transfer at the midpoint is primarily governed by conduction through the liquid film between the bubble and the wall, the film thickness is a key factor. To clarify the role of the liquid film, the crest and trough locations over one wavelength of the wavy channel are examined, as illustrated in Fig. 6.13. The local Nusselt number and the corresponding

Figure 6.12: Flow-field visualization near the bubble nose at $t = 0.12 \text{ s}$ for different heat fluxes.

wall-to-interface distance at these locations are compared in order to identify the effect of local film thickness.

Figure 6.13: Schematic representation of the crest and trough locations selected for analysis in the sinusoidal wavy minichannel.

It is found that the location with the smaller wall-to-interface distance exhibits a higher local Nusselt number, indicating a thinner liquid film and lower local thermal resistance. Therefore,

the crest-trough comparison supports the conclusion that local variations in liquid film thickness caused by the wavy geometry strongly influence the heat transfer between the wall and the bubble.

Figure 6.14: Local Nusselt number versus δ/D_h at $t = 0.140$ s at the crest and trough locations for $q = 10$, $q = 7.5$, and $q = 5$.

At $t = 0.140$ s, as shown in Fig. 6.9 and Fig. 6.14, valid crest–trough data are available for all heat-flux cases in the mid-section of the wavy region of the channel. The results show that, for each heat-flux case, the trough location has a smaller wall-to-interface distance and a higher local Nusselt number than the crest location. This indicates that the waviness of the microchannel affects the thickness of the liquid film between the bubble and the wall. Because of surface tension, the bubble interface tends to remain relatively smooth, whereas the wavy wall produces local variations in the wall-to-interface distance. Consequently, thinner liquid films are formed at specific locations along the wall. Since heat transfer from the wall to the bubble occurs mainly by conduction through the liquid film, a thinner film reduces the local thermal resistance and enhances local heat transfer. Therefore, the crest–trough comparison in Fig. 6.14 supports the conclusion that local liquid-film thinning induced by wall waviness contributes to enhanced heat transfer, although the absolute value of the local Nusselt number is also affected by the imposed heat flux.

At $t \approx 0.12$ s, corresponding to $x_c/D_h \approx 6$ in the midpoint plot, the $q = 7.5$ kW/m² case exhibits a temporary rise in the local Nusselt number. This increase is accompanied by a local reduction in wall superheat, indicating a transient enhancement of heat transfer at the midpoint of the heated section. However, the interface analysis shows that, at this instant, the extracted upper interface for the $q = 7.5$ kW/m² and $q = 5$ kW/m² cases has not yet reached the selected crest and trough probe locations. Therefore, the local wall-to-interface distance cannot be evaluated there, and the temporary Nusselt-number rise in the $q = 7.5$ kW/m² case cannot be directly attributed to

local liquid-film thinning at those probe positions. Instead, this feature is more appropriately interpreted as a pre-passage thermal disturbance associated with the approaching bubble. This disturbance is likely caused by recirculation zones that develop ahead of the bubble nose in the crest and trough regions of the wavy channel. These recirculating flow structures disturb the local thermal boundary layer and enhance mixing near the wall, leading to a temporary reduction in wall superheat and a corresponding increase in the local Nusselt number before the vapor–liquid interface reaches the selected probe locations.

At a later time, $t = 0.140$ s, valid crest–trough wall-to-interface distance data are available for all heat-flux cases. As seen in Fig. 6.14, the results consistently show that the trough location has a smaller wall-to-interface distance and a higher local Nusselt number than the crest location. This supports the conclusion that local liquid-film thinning reduces the thermal resistance between the wall and the bubble, thereby enhancing local heat transfer.

6.5.2 Influence of Waviness Parameter γ

A parametric study was conducted to investigate the influence of channel geometry on bubble dynamics and thermal performance in a wavy microchannel. In the present analysis, the channel width w and waviness parameter γ were systematically varied, while the Reynolds number, wavelength, and imposed heat flux were held constant at $Re = 1000$, $\lambda = 4$ mm, and $q = 5$ kW/m², respectively. The objective of this study is to identify how variations in width and waviness modify the bubble growth characteristics, local film thickness, and heat transfer behavior.

In the first part, the effect of γ or waviness was evaluated for a fixed channel width. In the second part, the channel width was varied while maintaining a constant value of γ .

Firstly, the width of 1.33 mm was selected as the nominal case. For this width, the effect of the waviness parameter γ was investigated for $\gamma = 0.00, 0.02, 0.04,$ and 0.08 . The analysis focuses on the influence of γ on bubble volume growth, bubble velocity, heat transfer characteristics, and film thickness at the crest and trough locations.

Figure 6.15 presents the bubble motion characteristics for different waviness values at the nominal channel width. Figure 6.15a plots the dimensionless bubble center position, x_c/D_h , against normalized time, T/T_{ref} , showing how far the bubble travels downstream with time. Figure 6.15b plots the normalized bubble center velocity, U_c/U_{ref} , against the dimensionless bubble center position, x_c/D_h , showing how the bubble speed changes as it moves along the channel.

Figure 6.15: Bubble motion characteristics for the nominal width case.

Evaporation begins at approximately $x_c/D_h = 4$, where the bubble enters the heated, wavy section of the channel. Before this location, the motion of the bubble is very similar for all cases, indicating that the effect of waviness is weak in the upstream unheated section. After the bubble enters the heated wavy region, the differences between the cases become more visible.

For Fig. 6.15a, the bubble center position increases with normalized time for all waviness amplitudes. Compared with the straight-channel case ($\gamma = 0$), all wavy cases exhibit a slightly larger downstream displacement. The final percentage difference in x_c/D_h is approximately +1.79% for $\gamma = 0.08$, +5.47% for $\gamma = 0.04$, and +2.12% for $\gamma = 0.02$. This indicates that waviness slightly enhances the bubble displacement, although the response is not monotonic with γ . The intermediate waviness case, $\gamma = 0.04$, gives the largest final increase in bubble position.

For Fig. 6.15b, the influence of waviness is more evident in the bubble center velocity. The straight-channel case shows a smoother velocity increase, whereas the wavy cases exhibit stronger fluctuations after entering the heated section. The case $\gamma = 0.04$ gives the largest mean velocity enhancement, with an average increase of approximately 4.77% relative to $\gamma = 0$. The case $\gamma = 0.02$ shows a smaller but more consistent increase, with a mean velocity difference of about 1.77%. In contrast, the highest waviness case, $\gamma = 0.08$, shows a mean velocity increase of about 2.23%. This suggests that stronger waviness can initially enhance bubble motion but may also introduce stronger local resistance or downstream flow disturbances.

Overall, the results show that wall waviness primarily affects bubble motion after the bubble reaches the heated section. The effect on bubble displacement remains relatively small, whereas the effect on bubble velocity is more pronounced. Among the tested cases, $\gamma = 0.04$ provides the strongest overall enhancement in bubble transport.

For the case with the largest waviness, $\gamma = 0.08$, the bubble velocity is initially higher, but at

later times it becomes lower than that of the intermediate-waviness cases. A plausible explanation could be that, although stronger waviness promotes evaporation and accelerates the bubble at first, the elongated bubble subsequently interacts more strongly with the wavy wall over a larger portion of its length. This increases interface deformation and makes bubble motion more unsteady, reflected in the larger fluctuations in the velocity profile and the reduced downstream increase in velocity compared with the moderate-waviness cases.

For the cases with γ ranging from 0 to 0.04, the behavior is more consistent with the expected effect of waviness on the liquid-film thickness near the wall. Increased waviness locally thins the liquid film in the convex wall regions. Since heat transfer from the wall to the bubble is mainly governed by conduction through this film, a thinner liquid layer reduces the thermal resistance and enhances evaporation. The resulting increase in vapor generation promotes faster bubble expansion and, consequently, greater bubble acceleration. Therefore, the higher bubble velocity observed with increasing γ in these cases supports the conclusion that waviness enhances bubble growth by reducing local film thickness, in agreement with Odumosu et al.[53]

Effect on Nusselt number, Nu

To investigate the effect of wall waviness on heat transfer, the wall superheat ratio and the local Nusselt number are evaluated at a fixed point on the heated wall located at $x/D_h = 8.65$. The results are plotted as a function of the instantaneous dimensionless bubble center position, x_c/D_h , in order to show how the local thermal response changes as the bubble passes through the channel.

Figure 6.16: Comparison of local thermal quantities evaluated at the fixed heated-wall point $x/D_h = 8.65$ for selected geometry cases.

Figure 6.16 compares the local thermal response for different waviness amplitudes. In Fig. 6.16a, the dimensionless wall superheat, ΔT , is shown as a function of x_c/D_h , while Fig. 6.16b presents

the corresponding local Nusselt number, Nu . The thermal quantities are not sampled at the bubble center; instead, they are extracted at the fixed wall point $x/D_h = 8.65$ and plotted simultaneously with the bubble center position. Therefore, the figure describes the transient heat-transfer response at this fixed wall location as the bubble moves downstream.

The local Nusselt number in Fig. 6.16b decreases with increasing x_c/D_h for all cases, consistent with the increase in wall superheat shown in Fig. 6.16a. However, the dependence of Nu on waviness amplitude is not uniform over the full range of bubble positions. In the upstream part of the plotted range, the differences between the cases are relatively small, indicating that the local thermal response is only weakly affected by the wall waviness at this stage.

As the bubble moves downstream, the tendency changes and the curves begin to separate. The largest waviness case, $\gamma = 0.08$, produces the highest local Nusselt number over most of the range. Relative to the straight channel, this case increases the mean local Nusselt number by approximately 10.6% and reduces the mean wall superheat ratio by approximately 9.3%. The enhancement is most pronounced in the middle part of the plotted range, where the separation between $\gamma = 0.08$ and the other cases becomes largest.

In contrast, the lower-waviness cases do not show a sustained increase in local Nusselt number. The case $\gamma = 0.04$ gives a nearly neutral overall response, with a mean Nu difference of only about 0.5% relative to $\gamma = 0$. Its behavior also changes with bubble position: it gives higher Nu in the early and middle regions, but lower Nu in the downstream region. The case $\gamma = 0.02$ shows a reduction in the mean local Nusselt number of about 2.4%, and its downstream response is lower than the straight-channel case.

Therefore, the effect of waviness on local heat transfer is position dependent. Increasing γ does not produce the same tendency at all bubble positions. Instead, the results show a transition in behavior: the lower-waviness cases have limited or reversed influence downstream, whereas the largest waviness case, $\gamma = 0.08$, maintains a higher local Nusselt number and lower wall superheat over most of the investigated range.

Effect on fluid film thickness

To examine the effect of wall waviness on the liquid film thickness, the dimensionless film thickness, δ/D_h , was evaluated along the upper part of the bubble interface. The results are presented in three complementary forms. First, the spatial film-thickness distribution is shown as a function of the axial coordinate, x/D_h , with particular attention to $x/D_h = 8.65$, which corresponds to the middle of the wavy region at selected times. Second, the local film thickness

at fixed crest and trough locations is plotted as a function of normalized time, t/T_{ref} . Third, the same local film thickness is plotted as a function of the bubble center position, x_c/D_h . These representations allow the influence of γ to be compared both spatially and during the passage of the bubble through the wavy region.

Figure 6.17 shows the crest and trough locations used for extracting the local film thickness in the wavy section. These two representative points are used in Figs. 6.19 and 6.20 to compare how the film thickness varies locally with increasing waviness, γ .

Figure 6.17: Crest and trough locations used for the local film-thickness extraction in the wavy section.

Figure 6.18 shows the spatial distribution of δ/D_h along the bubble interface at two selected times. The profiles indicate that the liquid film is not affected uniformly by waviness. In the central wall-film region, cases with larger γ generally exhibit a larger film thickness than in the straight channel. The effect is most pronounced for $\gamma = 0.08$, where the profile develops stronger local variations. The rapid increase of δ/D_h near the ends of the plotted profiles is associated with the rounded front and rear parts of the bubble, where the interface curvature changes rapidly.

Figure 6.19 shows the temporal evolution of δ/D_h at two fixed locations in the wavy section: a crest and a trough. At the crest location, the film thickness increases clearly with increasing γ , with the ordering $\gamma = 0.08 > \gamma = 0.04 > \gamma = 0.02 > \gamma = 0$ over most of the plotted range. This indicates that waviness promotes liquid retention at the crest. At the trough location, the effect of γ is weaker for the lower waviness cases, which remain close to the straight-channel result over much of the time range. The largest waviness case, $\gamma = 0.08$, shows the strongest deviation, especially toward the later part of the interval.

Figure 6.18: Dimensionless film thickness, δ/D_h , as a function of axial position, x/D_h , at selected times.

Figure 6.19: Dimensionless film thickness, δ/D_h , as a function of normalized time, t/T_{ref} , at the crest and trough locations.

Figure 6.20 presents the same crest and trough measurements as a function of the bubble center position, x_c/D_h . This representation compares the film thickness at the same bubble location for different values of γ . The crest plot confirms that increasing γ leads to a thicker liquid film at the crest, with $\gamma = 0.08$ producing the largest film thickness throughout most of the bubble motion. In contrast, the trough plot shows a much weaker dependence on γ for $\gamma = 0, 0.02$, and 0.04 , while $\gamma = 0.08$ again shows a noticeable increase toward the later part of the bubble passage.

Figure 6.20: Dimensionless film thickness, δ/D_h , as a function of bubble center position, x_c/D_h , at the crest and trough locations.

Overall, the results show that the effect of γ on the liquid film is location dependent. Increasing waviness produces a clear increase in film thickness at the crest, whereas the trough region is less sensitive for low and intermediate values of γ . Therefore, increasing γ strengthens the spatial non-uniformity of the liquid film within the wavy section, with the strongest film accumulation occurring near the crest region. One plausible explanation for the thicker liquid film at the crest is the presence of vortical structures ahead of the bubble in these crest and trough regions. These vortices may induce local recirculation and oppose the forward drainage of the liquid film, thereby promoting liquid accumulation near the crest. As a result, the crest region retains a thicker film instead of exhibiting the local thinning expected from geometric effects alone.

6.5.3 Effect of Width

Since the channel width controls the degree of confinement around the vapor bubble, it can influence both the rate of evaporation-driven bubble growth and the resulting bubble volume. Figure 6.21 compares the influence of channel width on the bubble growth rate and bubble volume ratio at three different values of γ . For each γ , the left panel shows the bubble growth rate and the right panel shows the bubble volume ratio. Specifically, Figs. 6.21(a) and (b) correspond to $\gamma = 0.02$, Figs. 6.21(c) and (d) correspond to $\gamma = 0.04$, and Figs. 6.21(e) and (f) correspond to $\gamma = 0.08$. Overall, these plots illustrate how variations in channel width affect both the instantaneous growth behavior and the relative bubble volume, and how this effect depends on the imposed γ value.

Across all cases, evaporation begins at approximately $x_c/D_h \approx 3.5\text{--}4.0$; before this location, the bubble growth rate remains nearly zero, and the bubble volume ratio stays close to unity.

6 Numerical Investigation of Bubble Growth in Straight and Wavy Mini-channels

Figure 6.21: Effect of channel width on bubble growth rate and bubble volume ratio at fixed γ .

In Fig. 6.21(a), after evaporation starts, the bubble growth rate increases continuously with bubble center position for $\gamma = 0.02$. For the same x_c/D_h , the widest channel, $w = 1.50$ mm, shows the highest growth rate, followed by $w = 1.33$ mm and $w = 1.25$ mm. In Fig. 6.21(b), the bubble volume ratio for $\gamma = 0.02$ increases rapidly after the onset of evaporation. The wider channel produces a larger bubble volume ratio at the same normalized bubble center position, with $w = 1.50$ mm showing the steepest increase. In Fig. 6.21(c), the growth rate for $\gamma = 0.04$

follows the same width-dependent trend. The $w = 1.50$ mm case rises most rapidly and remains above the other two cases, while $w = 1.25$ mm gives the lowest growth rate over most of the plotted range. In Fig. 6.21(d), the bubble volume ratio for $\gamma = 0.04$ increases monotonically for all channel widths. At comparable x_c/D_h , the largest channel width gives the highest volume ratio, whereas the smallest width shows the slowest increase. In Fig. 6.21(e), the growth rate for $\gamma = 0.08$ again increases after evaporation begins. The $w = 1.50$ mm case gives the highest growth rate, while the $w = 1.25$ mm case remains the lowest and shows more visible fluctuations near the later part of the curve. In Fig. 6.21(f), the bubble volume ratio for $\gamma = 0.08$ increases for all three widths. The widest channel again gives the highest volume ratio at the same x_c/D_h , followed by the intermediate and smallest widths. Although the smallest-width case extends farther downstream, its volume ratio remains lower than the wider cases at comparable positions. Overall, increasing the waviness parameter from $\gamma = 0.02$ to $\gamma = 0.04$ does not significantly change the main width-dependent trend; in both cases, the wider channel consistently produces a higher bubble growth rate and a larger bubble volume ratio at the same x_c/D_h . However, at the largest waviness, $\gamma = 0.08$, the growth-rate curves become more fluctuating, and the overall growth level is reduced compared with the lower- γ cases, especially at comparable bubble center positions. This indicates that stronger waviness modifies the local evaporation and confinement conditions, but it does not reverse the channel-width effect: the widest channel still promotes the fastest bubble growth and the largest volume increase.

Effect on Nusselt number Nu

To investigate the effect of channel width on the local thermal response at a fixed waviness amplitude of $\gamma = 0.08$, the wall superheat ratio and the local Nusselt number are plotted as functions of the dimensionless bubble center position, x_c/D_h , as shown in Fig. 6.22. The quantities are evaluated at a fixed probe location on the heated wall, at the streamwise midpoint of the heated section. Thus, the plots represent the local wall response at this selected position as the bubble moves downstream.

Figure 6.22(a) shows that the wall superheat ratio, ΔT , generally increases as the bubble center moves downstream. This indicates that the wall-temperature difference at the selected probe location increases as the bubble passes through the heated region. The three channel widths show very similar trends, although the wider channel, $w = 1.50$ mm, gives slightly higher values over part of the intermediate range. Overall, the influence of width on ΔT is relatively weak compared with the overall increase caused by the downstream motion of the bubble.

Figure 6.22(b) shows that the local Nusselt number is initially high when the bubble center is

Figure 6.22: Effect of channel width on the wall superheat ratio and local Nusselt number at $\gamma = 0.08$.

near the beginning of the plotted range. As the bubble moves downstream, the local Nusselt number decreases rapidly at first, then more gradually, approaching approximately 20–25 in the later region. This trend indicates that the local heat transfer intensity at the selected wall-probe location is strongest when the bubble is closest to the probe’s influence region and decreases as the local wall superheat increases. The curves for different widths remain close to each other over most of the range, showing that at $\gamma = 0.08$, the channel width has only a modest influence on the local Nusselt number at this probe location.

The local Nusselt number decreases as the bubble center moves downstream, indicating that the local heat transfer intensity at the selected wall probe location is highest during the early stage of bubble passage and decreases as the wall superheat increases. For a fixed waviness amplitude, increasing the channel width generally increases the local Nusselt number. Relative to the reference width of $w = 1.33$ mm, the wider channel, $w = 1.50$ mm, increases the mean local Nusselt number by approximately 13.31%, 11.28%, and 8.57% for $\gamma = 0.02$, 0.04, and 0.08, respectively. This indicates that the wider channel enhances local heat transfer, though the magnitude of this enhancement decreases with increasing waviness amplitude.

For $\gamma = 0.08$, the smaller channel width, $w = 1.25$ mm, produces nearly the same local Nusselt number as the reference case, with a mean difference of only -0.24% . Thus, at this waviness amplitude, reducing the width from 1.33 mm to 1.25 mm has a negligible effect on the local Nusselt number, whereas increasing the width to 1.50 mm produces a more noticeable enhancement. Since the local Nusselt number is inversely related to the wall superheat ratio, the lower values of ΔT^* observed for the wider channel correspond to the higher local Nusselt number.

Overall, the results suggest that channel width influences the local heat transfer behavior, but the effect is moderate at the selected probe location. The wider channel tends to improve the

local Nusselt number, while increasing waviness appears to reduce the additional benefit obtained from increasing the width.

6.5.4 Effect of Width

In this final part, an overall comparison is presented to examine the effect of channel width, and hence aspect ratio, at a fixed waviness amplitude. The results are plotted as functions of the dimensionless bubble center position, x_c/D_h , so that the bubble dynamics and the local thermal response can be compared under different width conditions.

Figure 6.23(a) shows the normalized bubble volume growth rate as a function of x_c/D_h , while Fig. 6.23(b) presents the corresponding bubble volume ratio. These two plots show how changing the channel width affects the evaporation-driven bubble growth and the overall bubble expansion as the bubble moves downstream.

The local thermal response is shown in Figs. 6.23(c) and 6.23(d). Figure 6.23(c) presents the local Nusselt number evaluated at the selected heated-wall probe location, while Fig. 6.23(d) shows the corresponding wall superheat ratio. The probe is located at the streamwise midpoint of the heated section. Therefore, these plots describe the local wall response at a fixed position as the bubble passes through the heated region.

In Fig. 6.23(a), the bubble growth rate ratio increases after the bubble reaches the heated region, indicating stronger evaporation-driven growth downstream. The curves show that the channel width affects the magnitude of the growth rate. Wider channels generally promote a stronger bubble growth response over a large part of the plotted range, although the curves do not collapse exactly because both the hydraulic diameter and confinement change with width.

Figure 6.23(b) shows that the bubble volume ratio increases continuously with x_c/D_h for all channel widths. This confirms that the bubble expands as it travels through the heated section. At comparable bubble center positions, the wider channels generally produce larger bubble volume ratios, indicating that reduced confinement and a larger hydraulic diameter support stronger bubble expansion.

In Fig. 6.23(c), the local Nusselt number is high at the beginning of the plotted range and decreases as the bubble moves downstream. This indicates that the local heat transfer intensity at the selected wall probe location is strongest during the early part of the bubble passage and then weakens as the local wall superheat increases. The curves for different widths remain relatively close together, indicating that the width effect on the local Nusselt number is present but moderate at this probe location.

Figure 6.23: Effect of channel width on bubble-growth and local thermal quantities as a function of bubble center position.

Figure 6.23(d) shows the opposite trend to the Nusselt number. The wall superheat ratio increases with the bubble center position, meaning that the temperature difference at the selected wall location increases as the bubble moves downstream. Since the local Nusselt number is inversely related to the wall superheat ratio, the increase in ΔT is consistent with the decreasing trend observed in Fig. 6.23(c).

Overall, increasing the channel width enhances the bubble expansion and generally increases the bubble growth response. However, its effect on the local thermal quantities at the selected probe location is more moderate. The Nusselt number decreases downstream for all widths, while the wall superheat ratio increases, showing that the local heat transfer intensity reduces as the bubble progresses through the heated region.

The local Nusselt number decreases as the bubble moves downstream in most cases, indicating that the heat transfer intensity at the selected wall-probe location is strongest during the early stage of bubble passage. The cases with $w = 1.25, 1.33,$ and 1.50 mm show similar behavior, suggesting that moderate variations in channel width have only a limited influence on the local

Nusselt number. However, the $w = 2.00$ mm case shows a pronounced increase in the local Nusselt number, especially in the intermediate range of x_c/D_h , due to the corresponding reduction in wall superheat ratio. Since the local Nusselt number is inversely related to the wall superheat ratio, the lower values of ΔT for this case result in a higher heat-transfer coefficient.

In contrast, the widest channel, $w = 3.00$ mm, does not provide a sustained enhancement in local heat transfer. Although it exhibits a high Nusselt number at the beginning, the value decreases rapidly and remains lower than the reference case over much of the plotted range. This indicates that increasing the width beyond a certain level can weaken the local heat transfer response at the selected probe location. Therefore, the effect of channel width on local heat transfer is non-monotonic, with the intermediate wide channel showing the strongest enhancement.

7 Conclusion

The thesis objectives were to develop and validate a two-dimensional transient numerical model of a PHP with a wavy evaporator section and to compare its behavior with that of a reference geometry. The study aimed to analyze the evolution of the liquid-vapor interface, oscillatory motion, liquid-film behavior, flow and temperature fields, thermal performance, and the effects of relevant geometric and operating parameters.

A two-dimensional transient numerical model for two-phase flow was developed using the Volume of Fluid (VOF) method to capture the liquid-vapor interface. A complete two-dimensional validation of the pulsating heat pipe configuration, however, could not be achieved with sufficient reliability within the scope of this work. The unsuccessful validation was mainly associated with pressure instability during the transient simulation. From the solver-code analysis, three plausible contributors were identified: the update sequence for pressure, temperature, saturation properties, and phase-change terms; the global pressure correction applied to closed compressible volumes; and the pathway by which phase-change source terms enter the pressure equation. Although these effects could not be isolated, their combined influence could provide a reasonable explanation for the rapid pressure rise and the PHP validation case's inability to produce a stable, physically meaningful solution.

Because of this difficulty in obtaining a stable, validated, and complete PHP model, the scope of the numerical investigation was narrowed to a representative two-dimensional model of a single wavy minichannel. This simplified geometry captures a local section of a pulsating heat pipe and enables the study of fundamental two-phase flow mechanisms, while considering the novelty of a wavy evaporator section. The wavy minichannel model enabled the investigation of liquid-vapor interface evolution, bubble deformation, bubble motion, and liquid-film formation inside a confined channel. Although this model does not fully capture the operation of a pulsating heat pipe, it remains relevant because local two-phase flow behavior in minichannels helps to improve the understanding of PHP behavior.

The mesh independence study showed that complete mesh independence could not be achieved within the practical constraints of the present numerical setup. The final mesh was selected as a

compromise between accuracy, mesh quality, and computational cost. The chosen mesh provided sufficient resolution to represent the vapor bubble shape, capture the liquid-vapor interface, and describe the main behavior of liquid-film formation, while avoiding excessive cell distortion and computational expense. This balance was especially important for the wavy minichannel geometry, where the wall curvature makes the mesh quality highly sensitive to refinement.

The influence of geometry on bubble dynamics and local heat transfer was studied. The parametric study shows that both the waviness parameter, defined as the ratio of amplitude to wavelength $\gamma = A/\lambda$, and the channel width influence bubble dynamics and local heat transfer, but their effects are not identical. The influence of geometry becomes important mainly after the bubble reaches the heated wavy section.

The effect of waviness is most clearly observed in the bubble velocity and local thermal response. Increasing the waviness parameter $\gamma = A/\lambda$ increases the wall curvature and changes the local confinement along the channel, which redistributes the liquid film and modifies the evaporation rate and bubble acceleration. Among the nominal-width cases, $\gamma = 0.04$ gives the strongest overall enhancement in bubble transport, while $\gamma = 0.08$ produces stronger fluctuations in the velocity and bubble volume growth-rate. This indicates that moderate waviness improves bubble motion, but very strong waviness can introduce additional flow disturbances and unsteady bubble-wall interactions.

The local Nusselt number response is position dependent. In the middle of the wavy section of the geometry, the local Nusselt number generally decreases as the bubble moves downstream, while the wall superheat ratio increases. For the nominal-width cases, the largest waviness case, $\gamma = 0.08$, gives the highest mean local Nusselt number and the lowest mean wall superheat ratio compared with the straight channel. However, in the lower-waviness cases, $\gamma = 0.02$ and $\gamma = 0.04$, no sustained heat-transfer enhancement is observed. The case $\gamma = 0.04$ gives an almost neutral mean response, with only about a 0.5% increase in the mean local Nusselt number relative to the straight channel, while $\gamma = 0.02$ reduces the mean local Nusselt number by about 2.4%. This indicates that the influence of waviness on local heat transfer is position dependent and that only the largest investigated waviness, $\gamma = 0.08$, provides a clear overall enhancement.

The film thickness analysis shows that waviness produces a non-uniform liquid film along the wall. Increasing γ increases the film thickness at the crest location, while the trough location is less sensitive for low and intermediate waviness. The crest-trough comparison also shows that locations with thinner liquid films can produce higher local Nusselt numbers, supporting the interpretation that local liquid-film thinning reduces thermal resistance and enhances heat transfer. However, the observed heat-transfer enhancement cannot be explained only by film

thickness; pre-passage disturbances and recirculation ahead of the bubble also contribute to the local thermal response.

The channel-width study shows that, for the investigated range $w = 1.25\text{--}1.50$ mm, increasing the channel width increases bubble growth and bubble expansion. For fixed γ , the widest case in this range, $w = 1.50$ mm, gives the highest bubble growth rate and bubble volume ratio compared with $w = 1.33$ mm and $w = 1.25$ mm. This indicates that reduced confinement and a larger hydraulic diameter support stronger evaporation-driven bubble growth as the bubble travels through the heated section.

The effect of channel width on the local Nusselt number is smaller than its effect on bubble growth. For $w = 1.25, 1.33,$ and 1.50 mm, the local Nusselt number decreases as the bubble moves downstream, while the wall superheat ratio ΔT^* increases. At $\gamma = 0.08$, reducing the width from 1.33 mm to 1.25 mm produces almost no change in the mean local Nusselt number, whereas increasing the width to 1.50 mm increases it. Relative to $w = 1.33$ mm, the $w = 1.50$ mm case increases the mean local Nusselt number by approximately 13.31%, 11.28%, and 8.57% for $\gamma = 0.02, 0.04,$ and 0.08 , respectively. Thus, the heat-transfer benefit of increasing the width decreases as the waviness parameter increases.

When larger widths are included, the influence of channel width on local heat transfer becomes non-monotonic. The $w = 2.00$ mm case shows the strongest local Nusselt-number enhancement because of the corresponding reduction in wall superheat ratio. In contrast, the widest case, $w = 3.00$ mm, does not maintain a higher local Nusselt number over the plotted range; after an initially high value, the local Nusselt number decreases and remains below the reference case over much of the range. At this largest width, the channel is sufficiently wide that the bubble is less confined by the wavy walls and does not deform significantly with the channel waviness. As a result, the bubble passes through the channel with weaker capillary confinement and reduced bubble wall interaction, which limits the enhancement of local heat transfer. Therefore, increasing the channel width does not always improve local heat transfer, and the strongest local thermal response at the selected probe location is obtained with an intermediate-width channel rather than the widest.

Overall, the study indicates that wall waviness and channel width affect different aspects of the boiling process. Waviness mainly modifies the local flow structure, film distribution, and thermal response, while channel width strongly affects bubble expansion and growth rate. The strongest bubble-growth enhancement occurs for wider channels. In contrast, the local heat-transfer enhancement depends on the combined influence of wall superheat, film thickness, bubble position, and local flow disturbances. Therefore, the geometry should be optimized by considering

both bubble dynamics and thermal criteria, rather than using waviness or width alone as design parameters.

7.0.1 Future Work

Future work could focus on developing a two- or three-dimensional numerical model of a pulsating heat pipe with a modified wavy evaporator geometry. This would require designing a solver that accounts for local variations in thermophysical properties with temperature and pressure within the PHP system. Such an approach would allow the dynamic behavior of the working fluid, including phase change, pressure oscillations, and temperature-dependent property variations, to be captured more accurately.

Bibliography

- [1] *Computational Engineering — Introduction to Numerical Methods*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin/Heidelberg, 2006.
- [2] B. Agostini, M. Fabbri, J. E. Park, L. Wojtan, J. R. Thome, and B. Michel. State of the Art of High Heat Flux Cooling Technologies. *Heat Transfer Engineering*, 28(4):258–281, Apr. 2007.
- [3] A. Ahmadpour and S. M. A. Noori Rahim Abadi. Thermal-hydraulic performance evaluation of gas-liquid multiphase flows in a vertical sinusoidal wavy channel in the presence/absence of phase change. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 138:677–689, 2019.
- [4] M. Asadi, G. Xie, and B. Sunden. A review of heat transfer and pressure drop characteristics of single and two-phase microchannels. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 79:34–53, Dec. 2014.
- [5] E. Babu, H. Reddappa, and G. Gnanendra Reddy. Effect of Filling Ratio on Thermal Performance of Closed Loop Pulsating Heat Pipe. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 5(10):22229–22236, 2018.
- [6] I. H. Bell, J. Wronski, S. Quoilin, and V. Lemort. Pure and pseudo-pure fluid thermophysical property evaluation and the open-source thermophysical property library coolprop. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 53(6):2498–2508, 2014.
- [7] S. S. Bertsch, E. A. Groll, and S. V. Garimella. Review and Comparative Analysis of Studies on Saturated Flow Boiling in Small Channels. *Nanoscale and Microscale Thermophysical Engineering*, 12(3):187–227, Sept. 2008.
- [8] P. Błasiak, M. Opalski, P. Parmar, C. Czajkowski, and S. Pietrowicz. The Thermal—Flow Processes and Flow Pattern in a Pulsating Heat Pipe—Numerical Modelling and Experimental Validation. *Energies*, 14(18):5952, Sept. 2021.
- [9] J. Brackbill, D. Kothe, and C. Zemach. A continuum method for modeling surface tension. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 100(2):335–354, June 1992.

- [10] P. Charoensawan, S. Khandekar, M. Groll, and P. Terdtoon. Closed loop pulsating heat pipes. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 23(16):2009–2020, Nov. 2003.
- [11] K.-H. Chien, Y.-T. Lin, Y.-R. Chen, K.-S. Yang, and C.-C. Wang. A novel design of pulsating heat pipe with fewer turns applicable to all orientations. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 55(21-22):5722–5728, Oct. 2012.
- [12] D. A. Drew. MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF TWO-PHASE FLOW. 2026.
- [13] I. W. Eames, N. J. Marr, and H. Sabir. The evaporation coefficient of water. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 40(12):2963–2973, 1997.
- [14] H. Enwald' and E. Peirano. EULERIAN TWO-PHASE FLOW THEORY APPLIED TO FLUIDIZATION.
- [15] S. Fang, C. Zhou, Y. Zhu, Z. Qian, and C. Wang. Review on Research Progress of Pulsating Heat Pipes. *Inventions*, 9(4):86, July 2024.
- [16] M. Fazli, S. A. A. Mehrjardi, A. Mahmoudi, A. Khademi, and M. Amini. Advancements in pulsating heat pipes: Exploring channel geometry and characteristics for enhanced thermal performance. *International Journal of Thermofluids*, 22:100644, May 2024.
- [17] A. Ferrari, M. Magnini, and J. R. Thome. Numerical analysis of slug flow boiling in square microchannels. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 123:928–944, Aug. 2018.
- [18] L. Goldstein and E. Sparrow. Mass-transfer experiments on secondary-flow vortices in a corrugated wall channel. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 19(11):1337–1339, Nov. 1976.
- [19] L. Gong, K. Kota, W. Tao, and Y. Joshi. Parametric Numerical Study of Flow and Heat Transfer in Microchannels With Wavy Walls. *Journal of Heat Transfer*, 133(5):051702, May 2011.
- [20] H. Görtler. NATIONAL ADVISORY COMMITTEE FOR AERONAUTICS TECHNICAL MEMORANDUM 1375.
- [21] P. Gschwind, A. Regele, and V. Kottke. Sinusoidal wavy channels with Taylor-Goertler vortices. *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science*, 11(3):270–275, Oct. 1995.
- [22] R. Gupta, D. Fletcher, and B. Haynes. Taylor Flow in Microchannels: A Review of Experimental and Computational Work. *The Journal of Computational Multiphase Flows*, 2(1):1–31, Mar. 2010.
- [23] S. Hardt and F. Wondra. Evaporation model for interfacial flows based on a continuum-field

- representation of the source terms. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 227(11):5871–5895, May 2008.
- [24] T. Harirchian and S. V. Garimella. The critical role of channel cross-sectional area in microchannel flow boiling heat transfer. *International Journal of Multiphase Flow*, 35(10):904–913, Oct. 2009.
- [25] F. H. Harlow and J. E. Welch. Numerical Calculation of Time-Dependent Viscous Incompressible Flow of Fluid with Free Surface. *The Physics of Fluids*, 8(12):2182–2189, Dec. 1965.
- [26] D. J. E. Harvie, M. Rudman, and M. R. Davidson. Parasitic current generation in Combined Level Set and Volume of Fluid immiscible fluid simulations. *ANZIAM Journal*, 48:868, Jan. 2008.
- [27] C. Hua, X. Wang, X. Gao, H. Zheng, X. Han, and G. Chen. Experimental research on the start-up characteristics and heat transfer performance of pulsating heat pipes with rectangular channels. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 126:1058–1062, Nov. 2017.
- [28] M. Huang, Z. Yang, Y.-Y. Duan, and D.-J. Lee. Bubble growth for boiling bubbly flow for R141b in a serpentine tube. *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers*, 42(5):727–734, Sept. 2011.
- [29] A. M. Jacobi and J. R. Thome. Heat Transfer Model for Evaporation of Elongated Bubble Flows in Microchannels. *Journal of Heat Transfer*, 124(6):1131–1136, Dec. 2002.
- [30] H. Jouhara, A. Chauhan, T. Nannou, S. Almahmoud, B. Delpech, and L. C. Wrobel. Heat pipe based systems – advances and applications. *Energy*, 128:729–754, 2017.
- [31] J. Jung and Y. Jeon. Numerical study on the heat transfer characteristics of three-dimensional pulsating heat pipe. *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology*, 37(9):4869–4876, Sept. 2023.
- [32] S. G. Kandlikar. History, Advances, and Challenges in Liquid Flow and Flow Boiling Heat Transfer in Microchannels: A Critical Review. *Journal of Heat Transfer*, 134(3):034001, Mar. 2012.
- [33] T. Karayiannis and M. Mahmoud. Flow boiling in microchannels: Fundamentals and applications. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 115:1372–1397, Mar. 2017.
- [34] M. N. Kashid, D. F. Rivas, D. W. Agar, and S. Turek. On the hydrodynamics of liquid–liquid slug flow capillary microreactors. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Chemical Engineering*, 3(2):151–160, Mar. 2008.

- [35] C. R. Kharangate, H. Lee, and I. Mudawar. Computational modeling of turbulent evaporating falling films. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 81:52–62, Feb. 2015.
- [36] V. Kumar, Vikash, and K. Nigam. Multiphase fluid flow and heat transfer characteristics in microchannels. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 169:34–66, Sept. 2017.
- [37] C. Kunkelmann. *Numerical Modeling and Investigation of Boiling Phenomena*. Ph.d. thesis, Technische Universität Darmstadt, Darmstadt, Germany, 2011.
- [38] G. H. Kwon and S. J. Kim. Operational characteristics of pulsating heat pipes with a dual-diameter tube. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 75:184–195, Aug. 2014.
- [39] D. Lakehal, M. Meier, and M. Fulgosi. Interface tracking towards the direct simulation of heat and mass transfer in multiphase flows q.
- [40] L. Lin, J. Zhao, G. Lu, X.-D. Wang, and W.-M. Yan. Heat transfer enhancement in microchannel heat sink by wavy channel with changing wavelength/amplitude. *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, 118:423–434, Aug. 2017.
- [41] X. Liu, Y. Fu, J. Wang, H. Zhang, and J. Zhu. Investigation on flow and heat transfer in rectangular cross-section sinusoidal channels. *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, 176:107490, June 2022.
- [42] D. Ma, Y. Tang, and G. Xia. Experimental investigation of flow boiling performance in sinusoidal wavy microchannels with secondary channels. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 199:117502, Nov. 2021.
- [43] M. Magnini. *CFD Modeling of Two-Phase Boiling Flows in the Slug Flow Regime with an Interface Capturing Technique*. Ph.d. thesis, Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna, Bologna, Italy, May 2012.
- [44] M. Magnini, F. Municchi, I. El Mellas, and M. Icardi. Liquid film distribution around long gas bubbles propagating in rectangular capillaries. *International Journal of Multiphase Flow*, 148:103939, Mar. 2022.
- [45] M. Magnini, B. Pulvirenti, and J. Thome. Numerical investigation of hydrodynamics and heat transfer of elongated bubbles during flow boiling in a microchannel. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 59:451–471, Apr. 2013.
- [46] R. Marek and J. Straub. Analysis of the evaporation coefficient and the condensation coefficient of water.

- [47] M. Marengo and V. S. Nikolayev. Pulsating Heat Pipes: Experimental Analysis, Design and Applications. pages 1–62. July 2018.
- [48] S. McKee, M. F. Tomé, V. G. Ferreira, J. A. Cuminato, A. Castelo, F. S. Sousa, and N. Mangiavacchi. The mac method. *Computers & Fluids*, 37(8):907–930, 2008.
- [49] S. S. Mehendale, A. M. Jacobi, and R. K. Shah. Fluid Flow and Heat Transfer at Micro- and Meso-Scales With Application to Heat Exchanger Design. *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, 53(7):175–193, July 2000.
- [50] S. Mirjalili, S. S. Jain, and M. S. Dodd. Interface-capturing methods for two-phase flows: An overview and recent developments.
- [51] K. Nilpueng and S. Wongwiset. Flow pattern and pressure drop of vertical upward gas–liquid flow in sinusoidal wavy channels. *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science*, 30(6):523–534, June 2006.
- [52] T. Nishimura, T. Yoshino, and Y. Kawamura. Instability of flow in a sinusoidal wavy channel with narrow spacing. *JOURNAL OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING OF JAPAN*, 20(1):102–104, 1987.
- [53] O. A. Odumosu, H. Xu, T. Wang, and Z. Che. Growth of Elongated Vapor Bubbles During Flow Boiling Heat Transfer in Wavy Microchannels. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 223:119987, Mar. 2023.
- [54] M. Opalski, C. Czajkowski, P. Błasiak, A. I. Nowak, J. Ishimoto, and S. Pietrowicz. Comprehensive numerical modeling analysis and experimental validation of a multi-turn pulsating heat pipe. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, 159:107990, Dec. 2024.
- [55] L. Pagliarini, N. Iwata, and F. Bozzoli. Pulsating heat pipes: Critical review on different experimental techniques. *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science*, 148:110980, Oct. 2023.
- [56] M. S. Plesset and S. A. Zwick. The Growth of Vapor Bubbles in Superheated Liquids. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 25(4):493–500, Apr. 1954.
- [57] S. Pouryoussefi and Y. Zhang. Numerical investigation of chaotic flow in a 2D closed-loop pulsating heat pipe. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 98:617–627, Apr. 2016.
- [58] S. Pouryoussefi and Y. Zhang. Analysis of chaotic flow in a 2D multi-turn closed-loop pulsating heat pipe. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 126:1069–1076, Nov. 2017.
- [59] D. Qian and A. Lawal. Numerical study on gas and liquid slugs for Taylor flow in a

- T-junction microchannel. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 61(23):7609–7625, Dec. 2006.
- [60] J. Qu, Q. Wang, and Q. Sun. Lower limit of internal diameter for oscillating heat pipes: A theoretical model. *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, 110:174–185, Dec. 2016.
- [61] J. Qu, H. Wu, and P. Cheng. Start-up, heat transfer and flow characteristics of silicon-based micro pulsating heat pipes. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 55(21-22):6109–6120, Oct. 2012.
- [62] Y. Renardy and M. Renardy. PROST: A Parabolic Reconstruction of Surface Tension for the Volume-of-Fluid Method. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 183(2):400–421, Dec. 2002.
- [63] R. Revellin and J. R. Thome. Experimental investigation of R-134a and R-245fa two-phase flow in microchannels for different flow conditions. *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow*, 28(1):63–71, Feb. 2007.
- [64] W. J. Rider and D. B. Kothe. Reconstructing Volume Tracking. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 141(2):112–152, Apr. 1998.
- [65] J. W. Rose. On interphase matter transfer, the condensation coefficient and dropwise condensation. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, 411(1841):305–311, 1987.
- [66] M. Schäfer. *Computational Engineering – Introduction to Numerical Methods*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2006.
- [67] H. Scheufler and J. Roenby. Accurate and efficient surface reconstruction from volume fraction data on general meshes. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 383:1–23, Apr. 2019.
- [68] H. Scheufler and J. Roenby. TwoPhaseFlow: A Framework for Developing Two Phase Flow Solvers in OpenFOAM. *OpenFOAM® Journal*, 3:200–224, Nov. 2023.
- [69] L. E. Scriven. On the dynamics of phase growth. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 10(1-2):1–13, 1959.
- [70] P. Shen, S. K. Aliabadi, and J. Abedi. A Review of Single-Phase Liquid Flow and Heat Transfer in Microchannels. In *ASME 2nd International Conference on Microchannels and Minichannels*, pages 213–220, Rochester, New York, USA, Jan. 2004. ASMEDC.
- [71] S. Sohel Murshed and C. Nieto De Castro. A critical review of traditional and emerging techniques and fluids for electronics cooling. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 78:821–833, Oct. 2017.
- [72] S. M. Sohel Murshed and C. A. Nieto de Castro. A critical review of traditional and emerging

- techniques and fluids for electronics cooling. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 78:821–833, 2017.
- [73] Y. Sui, C. Teo, P. Lee, Y. Chew, and C. Shu. Fluid flow and heat transfer in wavy microchannels. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 53(13-14):2760–2772, June 2010.
- [74] J. Thome, V. Dupont, and A. Jacobi. Heat transfer model for evaporation in microchannels. Part I: Presentation of the model. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 47(14-16):3375–3385, July 2004.
- [75] J. R. Thome. Boiling in microchannels: A review of experiment and theory. *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow*, 25(2):128–139, Apr. 2004.
- [76] J. R. Thome and L. Consolini. Mechanisms of Boiling in Microchannels: Critical Assessment. In S. Kakaç, B. Kosoy, D. Li, and A. Pramuanjaroenkij, editors, *Microfluidics Based Microsystems*, pages 83–105. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, 2010.
- [77] G. Wang and S. Vanka. Convective heat transfer in periodic wavy passages. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 38(17):3219–3230, Nov. 1995.
- [78] H. Wang, Q. Bi, and L. K. Leung. Heat transfer from a 2×2 wire-wrapped rod bundle to supercritical pressure water. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 97:486–501, June 2016.
- [79] H. Wang, S. V. Garimella, and J. Y. Murthy. Characteristics of an evaporating thin film in a microchannel. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 50(19–20):3933–3942, 2007.
- [80] J. Wang, H. Ma, and Q. Zhu. Effects of the evaporator and condenser length on the performance of pulsating heat pipes. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 91:1018–1025, Dec. 2015.
- [81] J. Wang, H. Ma, Q. Zhu, Y. Dong, and K. Yue. Numerical and experimental investigation of pulsating heat pipes with corrugated configuration. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 102:158–166, June 2016.
- [82] L. Wu, J. Chen, and S. Wang. Experimental study on thermal performance of a pulsating heat pipe using R1233zd(E) as working fluid. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, 135:106152, June 2022.
- [83] G. Xia, Y. Tang, L. Zong, D. Ma, Y. Jia, and R. Rong. Experimental investigation of flow boiling characteristics in microchannels with the sinusoidal wavy sidewall. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, 101:89–102, Feb. 2019.

- [84] P. Yang, W. Ling, K. Tian, M. Zeng, and Q. Wang. Flow distribution and heat transfer performance of two-phase flow in parallel flow heat exchange system. *Energy*, 270:126957, May 2023.
- [85] G. H. Yeoh and J. Tu. Basic Theory and Conceptual Framework of Multiphase Flows. In G. H. Yeoh, editor, *Handbook of Multiphase Flow Science and Technology*, pages 1–47. Springer Singapore, Singapore, 2016.
- [86] H. Yu, T. Li, X. Zeng, T. He, and N. Mao. A Critical Review on Geometric Improvements for Heat Transfer Augmentation of Microchannels. *Energies*, 15(24):9474, Dec. 2022.
- [87] J. Yu, S. Hong, S. Koudai, C. Dang, and S. Wang. An Experimental Investigation on the Heat Transfer Characteristics of Pulsating Heat Pipe with Adaptive Structured Channels. *Energies*, 16(19):6988, Oct. 2023.
- [88] J. Zhang, J. Kundu, and R. M. Manglik. Effect of fin waviness and spacing on the lateral vortex structure and laminar heat transfer in wavy-plate-fin cores. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 47(8-9):1719–1730, Apr. 2004.
- [89] S. Zhang, Y. Tang, W. Yuan, J. Zeng, and Y. Xie. A comparative study of flow boiling performance in the interconnected microchannel net and rectangular microchannels. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 98:814–823, July 2016.
- [90] X. M. Zhang. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF A PULSATING HEAT PIPE USING FC-72, ETHANOL, AND WATER AS WORKING FLUIDS. *Experimental Heat Transfer*, 17(1):47–67, Jan. 2004.
- [91] Z. Zhang, X. Wang, and Y. Yan. A review of the state-of-the-art in electronic cooling. *e-Prime - Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy*, 1:100009, 2021.